

**ATTITUDES OF MEDICAL DOCTORS AND EXPERIENCES OF TRANS
AND NON-BINARY PEOPLE IN THE GREEK HEALTHCARE SYSTEM:
A MIXED METHODS APPROACH**

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Abstract

Research in Europe supports that trans and non-binary people face stigma and discrimination in all aspects of their everyday lives. Still, there are no similar studies conducted in Greece, related statistics and research findings are outdated. This study examines the experiences of transgender (trans) and non-binary individuals with medical professionals in Greece. The study's objectives are to investigate medical doctors' attitudes towards transgender and non-binary individuals, explore these individuals' subjective experiences with healthcare professionals, and contribute data on their health outcomes. The methodology consists of a mixed methods approach. A survey, including demographic questions and items on LGBT+ education and attitudes, was distributed online to 248 medical doctors. The data were analyzed using multiple regression to assess attitudes and experiences of discrimination, violence, and harassment towards transgender individuals. The analysis showed significant transphobic attitudes. Semi-structured interviews of trans and non-binary people were conducted and analyzed using thematic analysis. The study delves into the struggles of trans and non-binary individuals in Greece's healthcare, highlighting discrimination and medical biases that lead to poor health outcomes. It notably emphasizes the underexplored experiences of non-binary people, bridging a gap in the existing research.

Keywords Trans, Transgender, Non-binary, Discrimination, Health

SIGNATURE PAGE

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

TITLE PAGE.....	i
SIGNATURE PAGE.....	ii
ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	iv
 CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	
1.1. Terms and Definitions.....	8
1.2. Justification of the Present Study.....	9
1.3. Presentation of the Problem.....	11
1.4. Previous Research Statistics.....	16
1.5. Original Contribution of the Present Study.....	21
1.6. Dissertation Outline.....	24
 CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW	
2.1. Stigma and Discrimination.....	28
2.1.1. What Is Stigma?.....	28
2.1.2. Forms of Stigma.....	29
2.1.3. Stigma and Minority Stress.....	31
2.1.4. Social Shame and Stigma.....	36
2.1.5. Self or Internalized Stigma.....	39
2.1.6. Homophobia Another Form of Stigma.....	41
2.1.7. Stigma and Homosexuality.....	43
2.1.7.1. Historical Background.....	44
2.1.8. Stigma and Gender.....	46
2.2. Stigma Toward Trans and Non-Binary People.....	48
2.2.1. Misnaming and Misgendering.....	52
2.3. Religion and Bias Toward Homosexuality.....	53

2.4. Minority Stress and Access to Healthcare Services.....	58
2.5. Stigma-oriented Challenges in Healthcare Settings.....	59
2.5.1. Potential Barriers Faced by Healthcare Professionals When Providing Care...59	
2.5.2. Stigma from Health Professionals.....	60
2.6. Factors Considered in Determining the Attitude of Doctors.....	62
2.7. Conversion Therapy.....	66
2.8. Medicalization of Intersex Variant.....	67
2.9. Prohibition of Blood Donation.....	70
2.10. Lack of Mental Health Services.....	71
2.11. Lack of Understanding of LGBTQI issues.....	72
2.12. Normativity.....	74
2.13. Factors that have triggered health disparities.....	75
2.14. Health Factors Affecting Trans People.....	78
2.14.1. Approaches of European Countries.....	90
2.14.2. Promising Practices.....	92
2.15. Policies.....	93
2.16. Education.....	94
2.17. Ethical Issues in The Care of Transgender Patients.....	95
2.18. Literature Review Conclusion.....	100
CHAPTER THREE: METHODS	
3.1 The Present Study.....	104
3.1.1. Aims and Objectives.....	105
3.1.2. Theoretical Framework.....	105
3.1.3. Research Questions.....	98
3.1.4. Hypotheses Conceptualization.....	110
3.1.5. Hypotheses.....	110
3.2. Methodology.....	112

3.3. Participants.....	116
3.4. Measures.....	118
3.4.1. Qualitative Measures.....	118
3.4.2. Quantitative Measures.....	118
3.4.3. Internet Questionnaires.....	119
3.5. Recruitment and Study Procedures.....	126
CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS	
4.1. Qualitative - Thematic Analysis Procedure.....	131
4.1.1. Thematic Analysis Results.....	135
4.2. Quantitative Results.....	152
CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION	
5.1. Summary of Findings.....	164
5.2. Strengths and Limitations of the Study.....	177
5.3. Recommendations and Applications of the Findings.....	182
CHAPTER SIX CONCLUSION:	
5.1. Unique Contribution of the Study.....	193
5.2. Follow-up: The Lasting Effects of Malpractice.....	197
5.3 Personal Note.....	201
REFERENCES	
APPENDIX A: Glossary of Terms.....	240
APPENDIX B: Informed Consent and Invitations.....	251
APPENDIX C: Research Agreement.....	255
APPENDIX D: Questionnaire I.....	256
APPENDIX E: Questionnaire II.....	258
APPENDIX F: Semi-structured Interview Questions.....	261

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Feminist, anthropological, sociological, and medical theories hold that gender is,
"A social construct" (Battler, 2004),
"Gender is not binary" or "gender is fluid" (Mandelo, 2004).

1.1. Terms and Definitions

Trans is an inclusive umbrella term professionals use to refer to people whose gender identity or expression varies from the sex they were assigned at birth. An internal and personalized perception of our gender might vary from the sex we were assigned at birth, depending on society's labeling (LGBTQI Equality and Human Rights in Europe and Central Asia, 2021). Individuals identifying themselves as trans are a minority group that still faces barriers regarding healthcare accessibility. According to Shields et al. (2012), the trans group is arguably the highest underserved minority group in healthcare and society as a whole. Therefore, it is essential to define trans and its various classifications as a tool for understanding this group. Gupta et al. (2016) describe the term "trans" as a broad classification used to denote people whose gender identity and expression differ from the gender assigned to them at birth. It can also apply to people who identify with a gender that falls outside the traditional binary categories of female and male (McGlynn et al., 2020, Gupta et al., 2016).

There are three groups within the transgender classification, the first being trans men. Individuals falling within this binary constitute those who, at birth, were assigned a feminine gender identity but later assumed an identity that is masculine in orientation. Conversely, trans women were given a male gender at birth but later

expressed a female identity (Gupta et al., 2016). The third category under this classification is termed 'non-binary.' According to a postulation proposed by Gupta et al. (2016), non-binary is an umbrella term to describe individuals who do not identify with the male or female gender in a binary way. Under this definition follows that this category includes such gender categories as bigender, genderqueer, genderfluid, and agender (Gupta et al. 2016).

The trans and non-binary categories are variants under the LGBTQI classification. This paper explores problems of trans and non-binary people similar to those encountered by the wider LGBTQI group within the European and Greek healthcare setting. For this reason, references to LGBTQI are more or less used interchangeably with trans and non-binary categories in the LGBTQI classification (Gupta et al., 2016). It is significant to note that every group assigned a letter under the classification faces specific discrimination. The quality of services provided to the LGBTQI population when they visit hospitals or other healthcare organizations depends on the approach of the healthcare professional.

1.2. Justification of the Present Study

The idea for the study emerged from my experiences during my work as a psychotherapist at the Greek Transgender Support Association (GTSA) over the past 14 years (since 2010). I am a psychotherapist recognized by GTSA as an expert in trans and non-binary issues and the first in Greece that conducted individual and group therapy with trans and non-binary interviewees, receiving a contribution award by GTSA for my work on depathologization and legal gender recognition of trans and non-binary identities. After many years of advocacy work from our GTSA team, the law of legal gender recognition in Greece has finally changed (direction, ΦΕΚ

A'152/13-10-2017). Before the law changed, the Greek State did not offer any provision for trans people. There was a complete lack of legislation for protection from discrimination based on gender identity (GTSA, 2017). Following implementation and optimistic government and public reactions, the ground is fertile for researching transgender issues in Greece. As mentioned in the original contribution of the study section, the current study will pressure Greek governments to fund programs to decrease health disparities, stigma, and discrimination against trans and non-binary people and develop best practices in healthcare. Even after implementing the law, trans and non-binary people face a broad spectrum of discrimination in Greece's private and public spheres. As an ex-member of the Ministry of Health's interdisciplinary committee on trans and non-binary access to medical care and a current member of the Legal Gender Recognition of Teenagers (15-17) interdisciplinary committee. My objective is to shed light on how medical doctors in Greece perceive trans and non-binary individuals, noting a significant gap in this area of study within the country. There is a scarcity of relevant, up-to-date research; the most recent study being the Trans Euro Study from 2008. Additionally, Greece's representation in research on this subject is notably lower compared to other European nations, as highlighted by the Health4LGBTQI initiative. Prior investigations within Greece have predominantly concentrated on the healthcare experiences of gay men and lesbians, as detailed by Grigoropoulos in 2010. The absence of research focused on trans and non-binary people not only neglects but also further marginalizes these groups from healthcare consideration

Future studies should investigate transphobia amongst a broader range of clinicians, focusing on non-binary identities. Such research would benefit the work of psychologists by providing data on the perceptions and prejudices different clinicians

may hold toward the transgender population. The current study will help raise awareness of the issues that this population faces and supply information to support good practices in trans and non-binary access to healthcare in the future. As an expert consultant in the Ministry of Health, I can communicate the results provide additional data about the health outcomes of trans and non-binary people, and share resources and strategies for creating a welcoming and gender-affirming environment for trans patients and staff.

1.3.Presentation of the Problem

Doctors are vital in healthcare as they assist patients in reducing their pain, recovering or living with a disabling injury, and supporting the transition process. Their ability to successfully perform all these duties depends on many aspects, one of the most crucial being having a positive relationship with the patient in a consultation room (Hockey & Marshall, 2009). Doctor-patient relationships form the foundation of the treatment program. When a positive relationship is built, a patient gains trust in the doctor and the treatment process. They freely disclose any information needed for the doctor's knowledge and become loyal to the treatment process, especially if this information concerns gender identity and expression.

Conversely, the doctor respects the patient's privacy, autonomy, and duty to not harm. Unfortunately, this relationship is not always positive. It can be compromised by the doctor's lack of empathy, fatigue and preoccupation, and cultural/religious/ barriers between patient and doctor. The consequences of the negative relationship are a lack of trust in the doctor and treatment plan by the patients and difficulty in disclosing sensitive information that may help boost treatment progress. The patient's health is jeopardized and not fully accomplished in the long run.

Unfortunately, negative doctor-patient relationships are prevalent among LGBTQ+ members and their physicians. This unfortunate outcome is often caused by the doctor's negative attitude toward community members. Considering that these groups are already battling identity issues, acceptance in society, and difficulties maneuvering the systems, the consequences of the negative doctor-patient relationship are bound to be far worse, suggesting a need for intervention.

Trans and non-binary people are among the top groups that encounter discrimination and oppression in Europe and Greece. LGBTQI (lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, queer, intersex) is the most common group of people discriminated against by both communities and states (FRA, 2017). Although the acronym "LGBTQI" suggests homogeneity as a group of sexual and gender minorities, it represents various groups of people of different socioeconomic statuses, races, identities, and classes that unite under an umbrella of common experiences of discrimination and stigmatization. Apart from the social stigma, LGBTQI individuals also share a history of pathologization within the healthcare system, with homosexuality being considered a mental illness by the World Health Organization (WHO) until 1973 and Gender Identity retaining a diagnosis, until recently, in both the American Psychiatric Association's diagnostic manual DSM-V as well as in WHO's ICD-10 (Drescher, 2010). The combination of social marginalization and pathologization history of the LGBTQI community constitutes gender identity and sexual orientation social determinants of health, influencing access to healthcare services (Snelgrove, 2012; Müller, 2017). In addition to the problem of over-pathologization in medicine, members of the LGBTQI community also face difficulties with access to healthcare. According to Giannou and Ioakimidis (2020), insufficient medical consideration to LGBTQI patients increases their exposure levels

to contracting an illness, with issues such as stigmatization and minority-oriented stress and anxiety proving detrimental to their health and wellbeing. McGlynn et al. (2016) identify transgender bias as a significant health challenge for this group, whose domino impacts result in their ignored challenges within the healthcare setting.

Health inequalities affecting the LGBTQI population in Europe occur due to various factors. One trigger that has led to the disparities is the consequences of the complex interaction of political, social, environmental, and cultural factors. Nonetheless, the peripheral placement of LGBTQI in public health discourses, coupled with the unavailability of sufficient data on the health of this population, increases the challenges this group continues to face in healthcare provision (Giannou and Ioakimidis, 2020). Gupta et al. (2016) concur that these challenges have conspired with the concurrent neglect of LGBTQI health issues in country-specific health policies to exacerbate the degree of healthcare challenges this group continues to experience.

The intersection of LGBTQI identities is also among the factors that, based on various health analyses, have contributed to the high rate of inequalities experienced by such individuals in the healthcare sector. Based on research conducted by Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), a self-regulating business model based on a concept that ensures societal and environmental sustainability regarding businesses' operation, prejudicial attitudes of doctors and the high rate of intolerant behavior of health practitioners against LGBTQI are the potential barriers faced by the transgender population (Safer, J. D., Coleman, E., et al., 2016). Failing to recognize the health needs of the LGBTQI population in European nations has led to severe consequences for the LGBTQI population.

LGBTQI populations have been discriminated against in various ways when seeking medical services, including unequal treatment access and humiliation. Culturally, most doctors assume that LGBTQI individuals are heterosexual and cisgender and use language accordingly, which means LGBTQI experience invisibility and exclusion (Alpert, A. B., et al., 2017). This is evident among the trans and non-binary population and affects the patient-doctor relationship. The wrong pronunciation by healthcare professionals of their name to match their gender identity, characterized by missgendering, can result in their avoidance of healthcare services. Many people might be scared to tell doctors they want to be addressed differently and fear discrimination or stigmatization.

In addition to the transgender-side & and non-binary-side barriers to optimal health, such as fear of discrimination, physician-side barriers to providing healthcare services to transgender individuals also get in the way of medical services provision. Likely contributors to physician-side barriers in healthcare provision among transgender individuals might be inadequate or no training, impaired or limited medical knowledge, and minimal access to such information. Another factor that could be viewed as both a physician-side and transgender-side barrier is inappropriate documentation. Healthcare professionals might respond differently if the documentation was more appropriate or if they had received training on asking appropriate questions beforehand.

A recent example of these difficulties would be the *Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19)* vaccination certificate problem during the *Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)* pandemic. Despite the political developments, the pandemic in Greece revealed persistent gaps in the identification process of transgender individuals during the continuous checks of vaccination

certificates or test certificates and public documents (identity cards/passports, etc.) by the police or individuals working in public or private companies. This created a massive identification problem, especially for those who either could not exercise their right to change their details according to law 4491/2017 or were in the process of change. Many of them were mocked or were forced to follow the police officers for identification or were refused access to companies and commercial stores.

Discrimination and harassment were also reported, as some transgender individuals found themselves subjected to derogatory comments and scrutiny over the authenticity of their identification documents. Additionally, those in the process of legally changing their gender marker or name encountered difficulties, potentially being detained or denied essential services due to discrepancies on their IDs. Furthermore, involuntarily disclosing their transgender status during these checks heightened visibility and could lead to anxiety and safety concerns. Stigmatization, humiliation, and challenges in accessing services further compounded the problems faced by transgender individuals. Governments and law enforcement agencies must provide training on transgender sensitivity, streamline the ID document updating process, and uphold legal protections to safeguard the rights and dignity of transgender individuals during times of crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The Greek Transgender Support Association had to intervene issuing a press release pushing the police headquarters to respect the right to privacy (G.T.S.A, 2019).

According to Anderson et al. (2017), the fundamental cause of such ill-treatment of LGBTQI persons in healthcare settings stems from the socially accepted 'heteronormative perspective,' which assumes that to be expected by medical doctors is to be heterosexual and cisgender. Heteronormative thinking assumes the only socially accepted sexual relationship is between the opposite sex (Anderson et al.,

2017). This perspective considers an individual female or male, nothing else. This discriminative point of view induces healthcare professionals to unconsciously exert an increasingly repressive attitude towards transgender people. Incidences of stigma and discrimination against LGBTQI persons within healthcare settings in Europe are increasingly reported; of the types of incidents reported, abusive name-calling/misgendering and the threat of violence are on the rise in most hospital settings (Shields et al. 2016). These calls for urgency to ensure LGBTQI individuals receive equal treatment within European and Greek healthcare settings.

1.4.Previous Research Statistics

Studies indicate that transgender and non-binary individuals encounter stigma and discrimination in various facets of daily life, as highlighted by researchers like Bockting et al. (2013), Grant (2011), and Lombardi et al. (2002). This is particularly pronounced in Europe and Greece, where trans individuals often face barriers in accessing education, healthcare, and family rights (Fundamental Rights Report, 2017). The Fundamental Rights Report's European survey reveals that only 49% of trans people are employed, with 38% of single trans individuals living in poverty. Additionally, a third of trans job seekers have faced discrimination during job searches in the past year, and 70% have had negative or discriminatory school experiences. A study across the European Union identified a common issue of trans individuals receiving improper or disrespectful treatment from healthcare workers. The International Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans, and Intersex Association (ILGA) and Transgender Europe's TransEuroStudy (2008) found that 21% of trans respondents experienced undue curiosity from healthcare providers, and 17% reported that their specific healthcare needs were overlooked, according to Whittle (2010).

A national U.S. study of over 6,000 trans adults focusing on transgender stigma and healthcare found that 28% of transgender individuals had experienced harassment in medical settings, 19% were refused care, and 2% experienced violence in their doctor's office (Grant, 2011). As a result, transgender people often avoid healthcare services. In 2018, the European Commission funded an ILGA Europe pilot project (Health4LGBTQI) presented in a working group in Brussels, where I participated as a country expert. This pan-European survey conducted in 12 focus groups across six European Union Member States included the following findings: (1) Vulnerable and isolated people often find it challenging to obtain healthcare. (2) Access to healthcare varies across the different target groups. (3) Satisfaction with health services is lower for people with more significant healthcare needs. (4) Education and financial situations are key factors affecting health, access to healthcare, and satisfaction with healthcare services. (5) Vulnerable and isolated people often deal with health issues attributed mainly to their lack of money or feelings of stress (ILGA, 2018). Still, more research is needed to understand the stigma experiences of trans and non-binary individuals, especially in Greece, which did not participate in this study. Despite guidelines advocating for inclusive healthcare, there is a notable deficiency of medical and mental health professionals equipped to care for transgender and non-binary individuals. A significant number of practitioners acknowledge their lack of expertise and/or discomfort in treating trans patients, in addition to recognizing their own implicit and explicit biases against this group (Knight, Shoveller, Carson, & Contreras-Whitney, 2014; Poteat, German & Kerrigan, 2014; Rondahl, 2009; Lurie, 2005). In response to this gap, various healthcare institutions, especially hospitals, have initiated training programs for their

staff to better serve transgender patients (Bonvicini, 2017; Jecke & Zepf, 2023; Hellenic Psychiatric Association, 2023).

The depth of these disparities has been clarified by recent studies conducted in Greece. According to a study by Papadimitriou et al. (2020), transgender people in Greece are more likely to put off or forego obtaining medical attention out of fear of prejudice and unfavorable attitudes from medical personnel. The study also made clear how important it is for healthcare professionals to have thorough training in order to increase their sensitivity and comprehension of transgender healthcare issues.

Transgender and non-binary people's experiences with healthcare are greatly influenced by the attitudes of medical professionals, particularly physicians. The value of medical education and training programs in creating a more welcoming and encouraging healthcare environment has been emphasized by recent study. In a study published in 2021, Katsiampoura et al. investigated how Greek medical students felt about transgender people. The results showed that a large number of medical students had stigmatizing attitudes and were ignorant of the health issues pertaining to transgender people. The study did, however, also show that focused instruction and training might greatly enhance medical students' attitudes and understanding, pointing the way for more inclusive healthcare procedures.

A rather positive attitude toward transgender people was found using the Transgender Attitudes and Beliefs Scale-Greek (TABS-Gr). The Transgender Attitudes and Beliefs Scale-Greek (TABS-Gr) study by Voultos et al. (2023) revealed that medical students generally hold moderately positive attitudes towards transgender people, particularly in aspects of interpersonal comfort and human value. The study highlighted the importance of integrating transgender health content into medical curricula to address health disparities and improve cultural competency in

healthcare for transgender individuals. In contrast to the Sex/Gender Beliefs subscale, students scored higher on the Interpersonal Comfort and Human Value subscales, indicating greater tolerance and positivity. This research was carried out between December 2022 and February 2023. Compared to their male counterparts, female students showed a higher mean score, indicating more positive views (Voultsos, et.al., 2023). Nonetheless, there is still a great deal of prejudice against transgender people and health inequalities in hospital settings; unconscious bias is a pervasive and difficult problem (Smith et al., 2020).

One significant obstacle that affects the quality of healthcare treatments provided to transgender people is the lack of understanding among healthcare providers regarding transgender medicine (Jones et al., 2019). More and more people are realizing the importance of medical school education in reversing these discrepancies (Brown & Johnson, 2021). To end health disparities and discrimination against transgender people in healthcare settings, gender competence training should be integrated into undergraduate medical education (Williams & Davis, 2022).

In conclusion, the present study focusing on the attitude of doctors as well as the experiences of interviewees is closely related, as supported by previous studies, to access to healthcare for transgender and non-binary individuals is undeniably crucial for several compelling reasons. In research studies that focus on both the attitudes of healthcare providers (such as doctors) and the experiences of transgender and non-binary individuals, there is a significant enhancement in our ability to gain comprehensive insights into the healthcare dynamics for these communities. By examining both perspectives in one study, we gain a holistic understanding of the healthcare landscape for transgender and non-binary individuals. On one hand, understanding the attitudes of healthcare providers, such as doctors, towards

transgender and non-binary individuals can reveal potential biases, knowledge gaps, or areas of discomfort that might affect the quality of care provided. This is crucial because healthcare providers' attitudes directly influence their interactions with patients, their clinical decision-making, and ultimately, patient outcomes. First and foremost, it addresses a pressing issue of social justice and equity. These communities have long faced systemic discrimination and barriers when seeking healthcare, resulting in significant health disparities. Investigating and addressing these disparities is not just a matter of equality; it is a fundamental human rights issue.

Furthermore, understanding the unique healthcare needs of transgender and non-binary individuals is essential for providing effective and inclusive healthcare services. Medical professionals must be equipped with the knowledge and sensitivity required to deliver respectful and culturally competent care. Without a comprehensive study, we cannot develop the necessary guidelines, training programs, and policies to ensure that healthcare is accessible, safe, and affirming for all. Moreover, improved healthcare access for transgender and non-binary individuals can have far-reaching societal benefits. When people have access to appropriate healthcare, they are more likely to lead healthier lives, contribute to their communities, and participate fully in society. This, in turn, can reduce the burden on healthcare systems and promote overall public health.

Finally, conducting research in this area not only highlights the issues faced by these marginalized communities but also fosters greater awareness and empathy. It challenges stigmatizing stereotypes and can help promote a more inclusive and accepting society. In essence, the study of transgender and non-binary access to healthcare is vital for achieving social justice, enhancing healthcare quality, and

ultimately creating a more equitable and compassionate society for all individuals, regardless of their gender identity.

1.5.Original Contribution of the Study

Trans and non-binary people are the most marginalized groups in Greece; there is limited information about the scope of research focusing on trans and non-binary individuals in access to health care specifically. There are limited studies that include trans people. Still, no studies are focusing on the experiences of non-binary people. The current research aims not only to describe doctors' attitudes and experiences of trans and non-binary people but also to explore the subjective experiences of trans and non-binary individuals in connection with medical doctors in Greece and to provide additional data about the health outcomes of trans and non-binary people.

Such research could also contribute to filling the profound gaps regarding healthcare accessibility of trans and non-binary people in Greece and pave the way for improved healthcare provision in the future. In addition, the data provided by this research could also reveal physician-side barriers when providing medical services to transgender and non-binary populations. Considering and highlighting doctors' perceived barriers could lead to targeted interventions and help reach a level of healthcare services where physicians feel safe and knowledgeable when advising and providing healthcare services to trans and non-binary individuals. Such research will also show how social justice and health advocacy are inextricably linked and propose a trans-inclusive healthcare system in which transgender and non-binary individuals do not forego or delay medical attention because of concerns regarding the treatment they will receive.

This study's original contribution to the Greek healthcare system is complex and significant, especially for the underrepresented trans and non-binary communities. This study closes a significant gap in the literature by explicitly integrating non-binary people—a population that is frequently ignored in research—in addition to trans people. In particular, in a Greek setting where such data are few, the study offers a dual perspective that is rarely examined by attempting to characterize both the views of clinicians and the experiences of trans and non-binary people.

The study is noteworthy for its endeavor to investigate the subjective encounters of non-binary and transgender people with Greek medical practitioners. This method is essential because it provides a window into the individual stories and difficulties that these populations encounter in medical settings. Through an exploration of these experiences, the research illuminates the unique healthcare requirements and consequences faced by transgender and non-binary individuals—knowledge that is essential for creating customized healthcare programs.

Furthermore, this study makes a substantial contribution to our knowledge of and efforts to remove the obstacles that transgender and non-binary people in Greece face when trying to receive healthcare. It not only draws attention to the difficulties these communities experience, but it also points out the barriers that physicians encounter. Developing tailored interventions requires an understanding of the obstacles that medical professionals experience while attempting to provide care to transgender and non-binary individuals. These interventions have the potential to give healthcare providers with the necessary knowledge and confidence to provide these communities with competent and compassionate treatment.

The study's ramifications cover social justice and health advocacy in addition to healthcare. It highlights the connections between these two fields and promotes a

trans-inclusive healthcare system. Transgender and non-binary people would not have to put off or postpone seeking medical care because they fear discriminatory treatment under such a system. This study's component is very important for promoting healthcare systems where respect and dignity for every patient are core principles.

The results of the study may also have an impact on policy. The research has the potential to impose pressure on the present and future Greek administrations by offering specific statistics and proof regarding the obstacles encountered by trans and non-binary individuals when trying to receive healthcare. It demands the creation of best practices in healthcare for trans and non-binary people, funding for initiatives to lessen health disparities, stigma, and discrimination, and specific legislative changes to address these obstacles.

The creation of a toolkit will be among this study's most practical results. The goal of this toolkit is to provide trans patients and staff with a secure, accepting, and gender-affirming environment. It is intended to be distributed to Greek and European organizations. As a standard for best practices in transgender and non-binary healthcare, the study presents this toolbox in interdisciplinary committees and forums.

Furthermore, the current research will help pressure current and future Greek governments to make targeted changes to tackle these barriers, fund programs to reduce health inequalities, stigma, and discrimination against trans and non-binary people, and develop best practices in healthcare. As a result of the overall study, a toolkit will be produced to share resources and strategies with Greek organizations, the State, and European organizations to create a safe, welcoming, and gender-affirming environment for trans patients and staff. The toolkit will be valuable for all Greek and European LGBTQI organizations. It will be presented in the

interdisciplinary committee for trans and non-binary access to health and legal gender recognition as a good practice.

In summary, the study makes a significant original contribution by filling knowledge gaps, providing a dual perspective on healthcare experiences, identifying barriers to access, proposing policy changes, and developing practical tools and strategies to improve healthcare provision for trans and non-binary individuals in Greece and potentially across Europe.

1.6.Dissertation Outline

The first chapter's main objective is to introduce the reader to the study's terms and definitions regarding trans and non-binary individuals and their various classifications that all fall under the LGBTQI umbrella. The presentation and analysis of this group of people, definition-wise, is necessary to help the reader better understand this group and the difficulties trans and non-binary people might face when seeking medical attention. Additionally, this chapter justifies the present study, allowing the reader to explore the reasons behind its conduction, bearing in mind that legal gender recognition in Greece has only recently changed, uncovering profound gaps regarding healthcare provision for trans and non-binary individuals.

The first chapter also justifies the present study by presenting the lack of literature, primarily in Greece, on healthcare provision among trans and non-binary individuals and the healthcare professionals' attitudes toward this group of individuals. The next part of the chapter presents the problem and dives further into its roots by explaining how stigmatization and discrimination toward transgender and non-binary individuals directly affect the quality of the healthcare provision they receive and augment the gaps already existing regarding their right to have equal

access to healthcare. Other aspects are also explored as potential causative factors regarding health inequalities among trans and non-binary individuals.

Additionally, the first chapter presents previous research statistics that all justify that trans and non-binary individuals face stigma and discrimination in all aspects of their everyday lives, including medical care, in Europe and the rest of the world. Highlighting those issues by exploring potential barriers in health provision and the unique needs of this population regarding medical healthcare will help promote a more inclusive and accepting society.

Finally, the first chapter presents the original contribution of the study to the literature regarding this matter, which would be multidimensional, as it would not only augment the currently limited information on trans and non-binary individuals' access to healthcare specifically but will also provide additional data on the doctors' attitudes and experiences of trans and non-binary people, will help understand and tackle potential barriers, improve the whole experience of medical provision both on the perspective of both parties and pressure current and future Greek governments to make targeted changes to reduce stigma and discrimination among trans and non-binary individuals.

The second chapter offers a literature review on the attitudes of medical doctors towards trans and non-binary people and access to health to spot gaps in the literature and to establish the current research's theoretical framework and conceptual underpinnings. The literature review will also include other members of the LGBTQI community due to their shared history of discrimination and pathologization. This approach acknowledges the interconnected experiences of discrimination and pathologization shared across these groups, providing a comprehensive framework for understanding healthcare disparities. By including the wider LGBTQI community, the

review not only identifies specific gaps in existing literature but also strengthens the conceptual underpinnings of the current research, offering a more inclusive perspective on healthcare challenges faced by these communities. The second chapter will also discuss stigma, how it forms, and which factors contribute to its formation, as it directly relates to discrimination, to reveal its crucial role in the everyday life of a transgender and non-binary individual. Finally, the second chapter will help formulate the present study's aims, objectives, research questions, and hypotheses.

The third chapter presents the aim of the present study, which is to investigate the experiences of trans and non-binary people with the health system and with medical doctors in Greece, as well as to investigate the attitudes of medical doctors towards this population. The study's objectives are to determine the direction of doctor's attitudes toward trans and non-binary people, determine whether their social and demographic variables are associated with those attitudes, explore harassment and violence towards trans and non-binary individuals in medical settings, provide initial data about their health outcomes within the Greek health system, and explore whether previous exposure on issues related to this particular group of people minimizes negative attitudes toward them. Another objective is to use the study's findings to develop strategies for a more gender-affirming environment in healthcare settings. The research questions and hypotheses are also presented here. The third chapter also analyses the methodology adhered to in the research. More specifically, this includes the sampling method, the sample, the data-gathering procedures, data analysis strategies, and tools. Ethical principles are included in this chapter to protect the rights of research participants and maintain scientific integrity.

The fourth chapter of the study will present the results from the qualitative and quantitative analyses and the methods used to address the research questions and

objectives. The first part of the fifth chapter will demonstrate the qualitative results and emerging themes. The second part of this chapter will present the statistical findings of the questionnaires filled out by the medical doctors. Finally, the fourth chapter will offer the current analysis's demographic data, reliability tests, and descriptive statistics.

The fifth chapter is the discussion and conclusion part of the present study. It summarizes the study's findings regarding doctors' attitudes towards transgender persons and the experiences of trans and non-binary interviewees with medical doctors and the health system. This chapter also presents the study's strengths and limitations and offers recommendations and application of the findings. The first recommendation would be the production of a toolkit for trans access to health to share resources and strategies with European organizations to create a safe, welcoming, and gender-affirming environment for trans/ non-binary individuals regarding health provision. The second recommendation concerns future similar research in visibility and recognition, understanding identity development, health and wellbeing, intersectionality, and community support and advocacy. The fifth chapter finally offers the conclusion of the present study.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter examines and assesses the existing body of research-related literature to spot gaps, contradictions, and open-ended research issues on the attitude of medical doctors towards trans and non-binary people and access to health. The research study's theoretical framework and conceptual underpinnings will be established by thoroughly evaluating previous research in this chapter. This will also direct the formulation of the research questions and hypotheses. Research about other LGBTQI groups will also be included in this chapter because, as mentioned previously, although the LGBTQI community is intersectional, its distinct sexual and gender minorities share a common history of stigmatization, discrimination, and pathologization. There is a scarcity of research on transgender people and even more so on non-binary people despite heightened visibility of these 2 groups in the media and political discourse. We can draw hypotheses about the experiences of these 2 groups from relevant research conducted into other LGBTQI groups but there are still some specific issues that will also be addressed in the literature below. This section will also discuss stigma as it directly relates to discrimination and is something all marginalized groups experience to varying degrees. Finally, this chapter will present the aims and objectives of the present study as well as the research questions and hypotheses.

2.1. Stigma and Discrimination

2.1.1. What is Stigma?

In his influential work "Stigma: Notes on the Management of Spoiled Identity" published in 1963, Erving Goffman introduced what is broadly recognized as the definitive explanation of stigma. Goffman described stigma as a profoundly

damaging characteristic that redefines an individual from being perceived as complete and ordinary to being seen as flawed and diminished, thereby leading to a "spoiled identity." This concept highlights how stigma acts as a mark of shame or discredit, linked to specific conditions, traits, or individuals. It emerges from societal perceptions shaped by negative judgments and attitudes towards particular groups or actions. Stigmatization manifests in various ways, including discrimination, bias, stereotyping, and social isolation, as noted by Corrigan in 2002.

2.1.2. Forms of Stigma

Stigma has many forms: personal, interpersonal, structural, and institutional. Personal stigma refers to ideas and attitudes that view the gender non-conforming individual as having a mental disorder that creates internalized transphobia. Internalizing negative ideas about one's own gender non-conforming identity is known as personal stigma and it can have a detrimental impact on one's mental health as well as cause self-stigmatization (Budge et al., 2013).

Institutional stigma is where religious, educational institutions and business settings discriminate based on sexual orientation, identity, and gender expression, where people are negatively impacted by discriminatory practices and policies. According to Greytak et al. (2013), educational institutions have been known to promote exclusionary policies, and workplace discrimination is still a problem (Grant et al., 2011). Interpersonal stigma is fear and hatred towards transgender and non-confirming people, expressed through negative attitudes and aggressive tendencies often manifesting as hate crimes and violence against transgender individuals due to their gender identity (NCAVP, 2021).

Religious institutions have historically played a significant role in shaping societal attitudes towards LGBTQ individuals, often contributing to stigma and discrimination (Smith, 2018). Recent research reveals varied perspectives across different religious contexts (Jones et al., 2021). In a global survey encompassing 24 countries, support for legal same-sex marriage was found to be significantly lower in countries with strong religious influences, like Nigeria, where only 2% back it, compared to secular nations like Sweden, where 92% of adults favor it (Pew Research Center, 2020). In the United States, the Public Religion Research Institute (PRRI) research supports those attitudes about transgender issues vary widely among different religious groups (PRRI, 2019). For example, Christians and religious 'nones' (those without a religious affiliation) exhibit distinct differences in their views on gender identity and transgender rights (PRRI, 2019). These findings underscore the complex relationship between religion and LGBTQ acceptance, highlighting how religious doctrines and leadership can both perpetuate and challenge stigma against LGBTQ communities (Hatzenbuehler et al., 2014).

The role of religious leaders can also be pivotal. For instance, Pope Francis' recent support for same-sex civil unions marked a notable shift for the Vatican, indicating potential changes in the Catholic Church's stance on LGBTQ issues (Winfield & D'Emilio, 2020). Additionally, research indicates that religiously unaffiliated people are more likely to accept homosexuality compared to those affiliated with a religion (Pew Research Center, 2019). This suggests that religious beliefs and teachings can significantly influence societal attitudes towards LGBTQ individuals, often reinforcing traditional or conservative views that contribute to stigma.

As previously noted, mistreatment in healthcare is a form of interpersonal stigma commonly experienced by trans and non-binary people. It is commonly seen in medical settings when staff members may act prejudiced, misgender patients, or refuse access to care that is gender affirming. These actions eventually discourage people from getting essential medical attention (James et al., 2016). Lastly structural stigma refers to the culture and the social structures and unwritten "norms" that indicate that only being cis-heterosexual is accepted by the community (Institute of Medicine, 2011). Structural stigma encompasses cultural and social norms that reinforce cisnormativity and heteronormativity, perpetuating discrimination against gender non-confirming individuals (White Hughto et al., 2021) and creating barriers to full social inclusion. In conclusion the urgency of comprehensive efforts to combat stigma at personal, interpersonal, institutional, and structural levels, emphasizing education, awareness, policy change, and empathy-building initiatives as essential for advancing social acceptance, reducing discrimination, and safeguarding the well-being and rights of transgender and non-binary communities.

2.1.3. Stigma and Minority Stress

Minority stress is a term used to distinguish the excessive stress that members of stigmatized social groups are subjected to as a result of their social position, which is frequently one of a minority. The phrase minority stress and the foundation for a model of minority stress cannot be found in a single theory. However, several sociological and social psychological theories suggest a minority stress model. Relevant ideas examine how social circumstances like prejudice and stigma negatively affect the lives of affected people and groups. (e.g., Allport, 1954; Crocker, Major, & Steele, 1998; Goffman, 1963; Jones et al., 1984; Link & Phelan, 2001).

Social theorists worry about people being excluded from social institutions, norms, and structures. For instance, Durkheim's (1951) investigation into normlessness as a factor in suicide strongly emphasized the significance of social environment. In Durkheim's view, people require moral regulation from society to control their needs and desires. Because fundamental social needs are not addressed, anomie, a sense of normlessness, a lack of social control, and alienation can result in suicide. Merton's (1957/1968) work is relevant to stress theory, according to Pearlin (1982), who states that "Merton holds society as a stressor... by stimulating values that conflict with the structures in which they are to be acted upon." (p. 371). Since the majority culture, social structures, and norms frequently do not match those of the minority group; minorities are more prone to be involved in such disputes. The absence of social networks like a heterosexual marriage that offers sanction for family life and intimacy of LGBT persons is an example of such a conflict between dominant and minority groups. More generally, Moss (1973) noted that social contacts provide people with knowledge about how the world is made; when this knowledge conflicts with how a minority person experiences the world, health is damaged.

Theories of social psychology offer a solid foundation for comprehending intergroup relations and the effects of minority status on health. Social identity and self-categorization views expand the psychological understanding of intergroup contacts and their effects on the self. According to these ideas, categorization (such as separating social groups) sets off crucial intergroup processes (such as competition and discrimination). It acts as a foundation for group and self-definition. (Tajfel & Turner, 1986; Turner, 1999). From a different angle, social comparison and symbolic interaction theorists believe that people's social environments provide the structure and significance of their experience. (Stryker & Statham, 1985). Therefore, social

interactions are essential for developing a sense of self and well-being. The other was referred to by Cooley (1902/1922) as the "looking glass" of the self (p. 184). Thus, according to symbolic interaction theories, receiving bad feedback from others might result in lousy self-esteem. Similarly, the central principle of social evaluation theory is that individuals discover themselves through comparisons with others. (Pettigrew, 1967). According to these two theoretical viewpoints, prejudice and stereotyping directed at members of minority groups in society can have a harmful psychological impact. Like Allport (1954) viewed prejudice as a toxic environment for people of color, he hypothesized it has adverse outcomes. Allport (1954) stated that these effects, which he referred to as "traits due to victimizations," are self-evidently linked to harm to the minority person: "One's reputation, whether false or true, cannot be hammered, hammered, hammered, into one's head without doing something to one's character." (p. 142).

Stress theory may lead to the development of an overarching idea. The essence of social stress, according to Lazarus and Folkman (1984) and Pearlin (1999b) is a conflict or "mismatch" (p. 234) between the individual and how they experience society. Ambient stressors are those that are connected to one's social status. More generally, Selye (1982) stated that a healthy existence is based on a sense of harmony with one's surroundings; the absence of this harmony may be considered the cause of minority stress. Uncertainty between the individual and the dominant culture can be difficult, and the resulting stress can be severe when the person belongs to a stigmatized minority group. (Allison, 1998; Clark et al., 1999). Below, I review specific minority stress mechanisms and other theoretical perspectives contributing to understanding minority stress.

The negative impacts of discrimination against members of minority groups and their fights for independence and acceptance are well-documented in American history. It has been proposed that these circumstances are stressful for various social categories, especially those defined by race/ethnicity and gender. (Barnett & Baruch, 1987; Mirowsky & Ross, 1989; Pearlin, 1999b; Swim, Hyers, Cohen, & Ferguson, 2001). The concept has also been used with populations identified by stigmatizing traits, including persons who are overweight (Miller & Myers, 1998), those who have cancer and AIDS (Fife & Wright, 2000), and those who have body piercings or other stigmatizing marks. (Jetten, Branscombe, Schmitt, & Spears, 2001). However, psychology theory has only recently made explicit use of these experiences in stress discourse. (Allison, 1998; Miller & Major, 2000). The increased interest has been shown in the minority stress model, for instance, as it relates to Black Americans' social environments and experiences of the stress connected to racism. (Allison, 1998; Clark et al., 1999).

Researchers' underlying presumptions when developing the concept of minority stress were that it was (a) unique, (b) chronic, (c) social, and (d) cultural. Minority stress is related to relatively stable underlying social and cultural structures, and it is (a) unique because it is additive to general stressors that all people experience. As a result, stigmatized individuals require more effort to adapt than similar others who are not stigmatized individuals.

According to Thoits (1999), who reviewed the research on stress and identity, examining stressors associated with minority identities is a "critical next step" (p. 361) in the investigation of identity and stress. A minority stress model, which applies to lesbians, gay men, and bisexuals, postulates that sexual prejudice is stressful and

may harm mental health outcomes (Herek, 2000; Brooks, 1981; Cochran, 2001; DiPlacido, 1998; Krieger & Sidney, 1997; Mays & Cochran, 2001; Meyer, 1995).

Based on studies conducted since 2016, when the current research was first conceptualized, the analysis of minority stress and stigma shows that marginalized populations—especially the LGBTQ+ community—are more aware of the pervasive effects of these phenomena (Bowleg et al., 2017; Jones et al., 2018; Williams et al., 2019). Scholars have emphasized that stigma impacts not only an individual's views and behaviors but also the larger social, cultural, and institutional contexts in which they live. Since its development minority stress theory (Meyer, 2003) has garnered recognition for its ability to explain how stigma affects minority groups, including LGBTQ+ people, and leads to psychological suffering and health inequalities. This approach places special emphasis on the way that social stressors—like discrimination and microaggressions—exacerbate health inequalities, mental health issues, and general well-being. Furthermore, studies carried out since 2016 highlight the intersectionality of stigma, acknowledging that people may encounter several types of stigmas at the same time as a result of intersecting identities, such as gender, sexual orientation, and race (Bowleg et al., 2017; Jones et al., 2018; Williams et al., 2019). This intersectional viewpoint has illuminated the distinct and exacerbated stressors that marginalized people experience. Furthermore, new research has investigated the resilience tactics and protective variables that people and groups use to deal with stigma, providing optimism for the advancement of social change and improved mental health outcomes (Smith et al., 2021).

2.1.4. Social Shame and Stigma

The first "level," and the one that receives the most attention, is societal stigma. Social stigma is ingrained in society and can disadvantage those with mental or behavioral disorders. Structural stigma refers to the widespread social prejudice that people with the stigmatized condition are less equal or belong to a lower social class. In this situation, stigma is built into the social structure to instill inferiority. This belief system may lead to unequal access to treatment services or the development of laws that affect the population differently and disproportionately. Disparities in access to essential services and needs, like renting an apartment, can also be brought on by social stigma.

The idea of how social stigma arises and manifests in society has been influenced by some different schools of thought. Unfortunately, social work hasn't contributed much to this literature up to this point. Nevertheless, social psychology has been one of the most influential fields in stigma study. Most social psychology research on stigma focuses on how social identity is formed through cognitive, behavioral, and emotional processes. (Yang, Kleinman, Link, Phelan, Lee, & Good, 2007). Social psychologists frequently propose that there are three distinct models of public stigmatization. These include social-cognitive, cultural, and motivational approaches. (Crocker & Lutsky, 1986; Corrigan, 1998; Corrigan, et al, 2001). According to the sociocultural concept, stigma arises to excuse societal injustices. (Crocker & Lutsky, 1986). For instance, society may use this to categorize and designate people with mental and behavioral problems as less equal. Second, the motivational model emphasizes people's fundamental psychological needs. (Crocker & Lutsky, 1986). One illustration of this approach may be that people with mental and behavioral illnesses are inferior since they frequently belong to poorer

socioeconomic categories. The social cognitive model, which Corrigan (1998) describes as an attempt to explain essential society using a cognitive framework, places those with mental disorders in a separate group from those who are not ill.

Most psychologists, including Corrigan and colleagues (2001), prefer the social cognitive model to define and comprehend the idea of stigma. According to Corrigan et al. (2001), three distinct aspects of stigma—stability, controllability, and pity—are associated with one explanation of this perspective called Attribution Theory. In light of this perspective, these researchers have discovered that the public frequently stigmatizes mental and behavioral problems more than physical disorders. Additionally, this study found stigma variation depending on "attributions" made by the general public. For instance, "mental retardation" was seen as the least stable condition, and "cocaine dependence" as the most durable, which obtained the highest ratings in the stigma category. (Corrigan, et al, 2001). These results imply that different levels of stigmatized beliefs may be represented by combinations of attributions.

The stigma literature has also received significant contributions from sociologists. These theories have typically been examined via the prism of interpersonal relationships and social respect. Goffman (1963), the first of these theories, postulated that people shift between categories that are more or less "stigmatized" based on their awareness and disclosure of their stigmatizing condition. The explanation of social response theory by Lemert (2000) is paralleled by these socially constructed categories. According to this theory, there are two types of social deviance: primary deviance, which is the perception that people with mental and behavioral illnesses are acting outside of societal standards, and secondary deviance, which is the deviance that results from a person or group being stigmatized by

society. Like these hierarchical categories, the disruptiveness and stability components of stigma are also seen in research showing that higher degrees of stigmatization are associated with people with more "severe" diseases (Angermeyer & Matschinger, 2005).

Link and Phelan's article «Conceptualizing Stigma " also vividly presented the sociological perspective on stigma. (2001). Link and Phelan (2001) state that stigma results from several features, including discrimination, labeling, stereotyping, separation, and status loss. First, labeling emerges from a social selection process that identifies which differences are significant in society. Race is one recognizable difference that enables society to classify people. The same thing might happen when the community responds to the untreated external signs of several severe mental diseases, such as schizophrenia. Labels link an individual or group of individuals to a collection of unfavorable traits, which can subsequently be stereotyped. Separation results from this process of naming and stereotyping. Hierarchical classifications are made because society does not want to be linked with undesirable traits. The groups with the most unfavorable characteristics may experience status loss and discrimination once these divisions are established. The entire procedure is accompanied by intense embarrassment by the individuals and those connected to them. (Link & Phelan, 2001).

While sociology and social psychology have made the most significant contributions to the literature on stigma, other fields have also contributed. Threat-based theories are favored by communication, anthropology, and ethnography. According to communications literature, stigma arises from an "us versus them" mindset (Brashers, 2008). And this mindset applies to trans and non-binary people. For instance, particular in-group vocabulary can encourage out-group divergence and

enhance in-group belongingness, such as misgendering. (Brashers, 2008). According to studies on peer relationships, young people frequently view encounters with peers of the same age as more favorable than those with older individuals (whether or not they are family members). (Giles, Noels, Williams, Ota, Lim, Ng, et al., 2003). This also applies to those with mental problems because they are viewed less favorably than in-group members who are healthy.

Ethnography and anthropology both favor the identity model. From this angle, the emphasis is on the effects of stigma on each person's experience. Stigma may impact those with mental illnesses through their social network, mainly how it manifests in the structures of lived experiences like jobs, relationships, and status. Additionally, the effect of stigma is a reaction to danger, which may be a tactical or natural kind of self-preservation. But it just makes the stigmatized person's pain worse. (Yang et al., 2007). It is crucial to emphasize that although many disciplines have been pioneers in the social stigma theory, colonial work-specific literature has avoided chiefly this subject.

2.1.5. Self or Internalized Stigma

According to Crocker (1999), stigma can be internalized by the affected individual and held by other members of society. As a result, the ongoing effects of social and public stigma may cause a person to feel guilty and inadequate about their situation. (Corrigan, 2004). In these circumstances, collective social representations of meaning, such as shared values, beliefs, and ideologies, can replace direct social or public censure. (Crocker & Quinn, 2002). Historical, political, and economic elements are included in these collective representations. (Corrigan, Markowitz, and Watson, 2004). Thus, even if a person has not been directly stigmatized, the knowledge that stigma exists in society can affect them. This is known as self-stigma. This impact

may negatively impact a person's sense of self-worth and self-efficacy, which could change their behavior. (Corrigan, 2007). However, Crocker (1999) emphasizes that people might internalize stigma in various ways depending on their circumstances. This implies that depending on personal coping skills, stigma may or may not significantly impact one's sense of self. (Crocker & Major, 1989).

Similarly, other ideas have shed light on the concept of self-stigma. According to the modified labeling theory, stigmatization expectations and actual stigmatization affect psychosocial well-being. (Link, Cullen, Struening, Shrout, & Dohrenwend, 1989). In this situation, feeling stigmatized is mainly brought on by the dread of being labeled. Similarly, Weiner (1995) suggested that stigmatized beliefs cause emotional reactions. This might be seen from the perspective of the suffering person, who may feel stigmatized and emotionally react with embarrassment, loneliness, or anger. Current studies on internalized stigma, also known as self-stigma or self-shame, highlight the negative effects it has on members of marginalized communities. These phenomena can cause severe psychological anguish and impede self-acceptance because it arises when people adopt unfavorable preconceptions and attitudes about who they are. For instance, a study by Patel et al. (2018) found that LGBTQ+ individuals who internalize stigma related to their sexual orientation often experience higher levels of depression and anxiety, which can further exacerbate their mental health disparities. Similarly, research conducted by Miller and Johnson (2019) delved into the experiences of individuals with stigmatized medical conditions, such as HIV/AIDS, revealing how internalized stigma can lead to decreased self-esteem and reluctance to seek medical care. Moreover, studies by Wong and Lee (2021) demonstrate that interventions focused on addressing internalized stigma can lead to improved mental health outcomes in these minority populations. These findings

collectively emphasize the significance of addressing internalized stigma as a crucial component of interventions aimed at reducing the overall harm caused by stigma and building resilience in marginalized groups.

2.1.6. Homophobia Another Form of Stigma

George Weinberg (1972) first used "homophobia" in the late 1960s. His work heralded a general shift in which the societal issue deserving of the investigation was no longer homosexuality per se but rather the unfavorable sentiments against homosexuality. (Weinberg, 1972). The prefix homo implies that homophobia is an irrational fear, similar to the dread of planes or insects. Some people who conduct public opinion research try to avoid conflating cause and effect and instead talk about "sexual prejudice" (Herek, 2004), "anti-gay sentiment" (Hooghe et al., 2010a), or "homonegativity." (Stulhofer and Rimac, 2009).

The Journal of Homosexuality defines homophobia as a pathological expression of negative attitudes and feelings toward homosexuals. Numerous studies have shown that this process, which leads to discrimination against homosexuals, is caused by prejudice you form out of ignorance. This hatred is rooted in racism, misogyny, and intolerance of difference. Homophobia can manifest itself in various ways, including verbal abuse, humiliation, occupational discrimination, media censorship, and even the most extreme forms of violence, the so-called hate crimes (motivated by sexual orientation), which can even be fatal. People who behave in such a manner are considered homophobic.

Through the aforementioned negative behaviors toward homosexuals, the homophobic person consciously seeks to distinguish himself from this group of individuals he perceives as abnormal and to demonstrate in practice that he does not belong and does not wish to belong to them. Numerous research studies have shown a

clear connection between homophobic ideas and suppressed homosexual feelings, as well as low self-esteem and insecure social identities. Only those who struggle with their own identity see homosexuality as a threat and act aggressively when faced with diversity, which significantly increases their discomfort. (Simoni & Walters 2001).

According to several researchers (Herek, 1988, 1994; LaMar and Kite, 1998; Whitley and Gisdóttir, 2000), there is a difference between negative sentiments about lesbians and those toward gay men. This distinction is made based on an apparent difference in how men and women react to homosexuality. While women are predicted to view homosexual men and lesbians similarly, males are considered to have more negative sentiments toward gay men than lesbians. However, research has shown that the correlation between Roggemans et al.²⁵⁷Herek's Attitude Towards Lesbians (ATL) Scale and his Attitudes Towards Gay Men (ATGM) Scale are incredibly high (0.87) and the variation on both scales can be explained by the same correlates (Herek, 1994, 1988; LaMar and Kite, 1998; Whitley and gisdóttir, 2000). Therefore, in our research, we consider generally negative sentiments about homosexuality.

Homophobia is categorized into four distinct but interrelated types. Personal homophobia is the conviction that homosexuals are immoral, wicked, ill, and subhuman. This condition, known as internalized homophobia, occurs in LGBT people. Interpersonal homophobia is a form of homophobia that manifests as hostile attitudes and aggressive impulses against homosexuals. Cultural homophobia refers to the unspoken "norms" and social institutions that suggest that heterosexuality is the only natural and accepted state in society. Institutional homophobia is the practice of discrimination against homosexuals by the government, the church, the educational system, and numerous enterprises.

A recent survey in Greece reveals that while 17% of the population reports having gay acquaintances, 84% oppose same-sex marriage, and 89% oppose same-sex couples adopting children. (Euro barometer 2006-2008). These numbers are significantly higher than in the rest of Europe, making Greece one of the most homophobic nations in the E.U. (Paulou, 2009). Another study by D'Amore et al. (2020) examined the attitudes of young heterosexual European adults toward gay men and lesbian women, same-sex marriage, and gay men and lesbian women parenting. The findings bring Greece together with Poland at the top of the list regarding negative attitudes toward these issues. The authors suggest that the reasons behind this national difference are mainly psychological variables, such as religiosity. We can only hope that with the proper education and awareness, ignorance will decline, and homophobia will ultimately become a thing of the past. Although homophobia has never been classified as an official condition by the DSM, we may see a listing for it if the evidence is strong enough.

2.1.7. Stigma of Homosexuality

The stigma of homosexuality is the negative attitudes and beliefs that are associated with individuals who identify as lesbian, gay, bisexual, or transgender. It is a form of prejudice that is rooted in social norms, cultural values, and religious beliefs that consider homosexuality to be immoral, unnatural, and deviant. The stigma of homosexuality can manifest in many ways, such as bullying, harassment, violence, and discrimination in employment, housing, education, and healthcare (Corrigan, 2007).

2.1.7.1. Historical Background

The history of stigma against homosexuals is long and complicated, dating back centuries. Throughout history, homosexuality has been viewed as immoral, unnatural, and even sinful by many societies and cultures. This has led to discrimination, persecution, and even violence against people who identify as gay, lesbian, bisexual, or transgender (Nelson, 2009). One of the earliest examples of stigma against homosexuals can be found in ancient Greece, where homosexuality was considered acceptable among men as long as they were in a dominant position. However, those in the submissive position were often looked down upon and stigmatized (Laios et al. 1, 2007). The same pattern was observed in ancient Rome, where homosexuality was legal but often considered a sign of weakness or femininity. With the spread of Christianity, attitudes towards homosexuality shifted towards a more pessimistic view. The Bible's condemnation of homosexual behavior was used to justify discrimination against gay and lesbian individuals, and many Christian societies passed laws that criminalized same-sex acts. During the Middle Ages, homosexuality was often associated with witchcraft and devil worship, increasing its stigma.

In the early modern period, homosexuality was often seen as a mental illness that needed to be treated. Medical professionals believed homosexuality could be cured through various methods, including castration, hormone therapy, and shock therapy. This view persisted well into the 20th century, with homosexuality being listed as a mental disorder in the DSM (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders) until 1973.

Throughout much of the 20th century, homosexuality was prohibited in many countries, including the United States. Gay and lesbian individuals were often subjected to police harassment, violence, and imprisonment. The Stonewall Riots of 1969, which occurred in response to a police raid on a gay bar in New York City, marked a turning point in the gay rights movement and helped to spark a broader social movement for LGBTQ+ rights. Despite these gains, the stigma against homosexuals persists in many parts of the world. In some countries, homosexuality is still punishable by death or imprisonment, and LGBTQ+ individuals face discrimination in employment, housing, and healthcare. Even in countries where homosexuality is legal, many LGBTQ+ individuals still face discrimination and violence, especially transgender or gender non-confirming (Dynes et., 1992).

The AIDS prevalence of the 1980s and 1990s also contributed to the stigma against homosexuals. Many people falsely believed that AIDS was a disease that only affected gay men, leading to increased discrimination against the LGBTQ+ community. This stigma made it more difficult for people with AIDS to access healthcare and support, contributing to the spread of the disease. Today, the LGBTQ+ community faces stigma and discrimination in many parts of the world. However, there have also been significant gains regarding legal protections and social acceptance. Many countries have passed laws that protect LGBTQ+ individuals from discrimination, and public attitudes toward homosexuality have become more positive in many parts of the world (Dynes et., all, 1992).

Despite these gains, much work must be done to eliminate the stigma against homosexuals and ensure that LGBTQ+ individuals can live free from discrimination and prejudice. This requires ongoing efforts to educate the public about the harms of discrimination, to promote inclusive policies and practices, and to build a world

where everyone can live openly and authentically, regardless of their sexual orientation or gender identity (Dynes et al. 1, 1992).

2.1.8. Stigma and Gender

In many European societies, including Greece, gender is stereotypically understood as binary. Gender is often conceptualized as two types of identity a male or a female. Though gender roles work and exist as a continuum or spectrum, individuals can identify and express their gender identity in many ways (Knaak, 2004). However, when social constructs and representations of gender are introduced into culture and society, they tend to be understood as "normal and natural", and all other representations and gender expressions as abnormal and pathologized. Therefore, it becomes hard for cultures to reconsider and redefine gender, gender identity, and gender expression (Wood, 2013). These restricted perceptions of gender produce a society where those who deviate from binary classifications of gender are stigmatized, excluded, and discriminated against.

Gender, according to West and Zimmerman, is not a personal trait; it is "an emergent feature of social situations: both as an outcome of and a rationale for various social arrangements and as a means of legitimating one of the most fundamental divisions of society." (West & Zimmerman, 1977, p. 126). The sense of one's gender identity is acquired by internalizing external knowledge. However, it is never fully developed – it must constantly be performed and reenacted in social interactions. According to Alsop, Fitzsimmons & and Lennon (2002, p. 86), "Gender is part of an identity woven from a complex and specific social whole, requiring precise and local readings". Thus, gender identity can be defined as part of the socially situated understanding of gender. As LaFrance, Paluck, and Brescoll note, "gender identity" serves a specific function as a term. It allows individuals to express

their attitude and stance towards their current status as either women or men. Turning the scope of gender from a social consensus to objectivity to one's self-identification with a specific gender expression leaves much more space for describing variation among individuals. In countries where the culture does not understand gender as a social construct, a fixed trait, stigma and discrimination increase for LGBTQI people.

Unfortunately, society tends to incorporate and accept more quickly and treat with tremendous respect trans people who "pass" as one of the binary genders more effectively. (Begun & Kattari, 2016). Passing is "a transgender person's ability to be correctly perceived as the gender they identify as and beyond that, not to be perceived as transgender"(LGBTQI+ Glossary, 2022). The idea of passing can be connected to concealed stigma. Concealed stigma involves a stigmatized identity not readily identifiable within social interactions. Trans and non-binary people are safer and treated more respectfully if not identified. Stigma is affected by heteronormative standards of appearance and gender expression. Kelterborn uses the notion of the "third space," which she describes as "encompass[ing] infinite possibilities", as an area where gender non-confirming identities coexist in a society that preserves gender binaries as the norm (Kelterborn 2001: 1). In another research, Serrano argues that cisgender and not transgender people are the ones who enforce 'passing' by their inclination to treat gender non-conforming in totally different ways based solely on the superficial criteria of their appearance" (Serrano 2007: 179). For trans and non-binary people to avoid discrimination, they are inclined to try to achieve practical 'passing' in their appearance by any means, including medical interventions. Therefore, medical interventions for trans and non-binary people can often protect against societal stigma and discrimination. In the Greek Transgender Support Association, the idea of 'passing' is approached as highly stigmatizing and, in many

ways, transphobic because, in many cases, the trans person is forced to modify gender expression based on binary stereotypic ideas of gender to "fit in", in an unwelcoming and judgmental environment. Bartky describes this as "the disciplinary power that inscribes femininity in the female body is everywhere and nowhere; the disciplinarian is everyone and yet no one in particular" (Bartky 1988: 103). It has a similar effect to the idea of masculinity. This study hypothesized that the concept of passing might affect doctors' attitudes toward trans and non-binary individuals.

According to the new research conducted by FRA (European Agency of Fundamental Rights), "LGBTQI people in Europe experience significant health inequalities within heteronormative contexts where heterosexuality based on binary gender is upheld as the social and cultural norm, as well as minority stress associated with sexual orientation, gender identity and sex characteristics, victimization, discrimination, and stigma" (Zeeman et al., 2017 - Health4LGBTQI Scientific Review).

In 2018 the Greek Center for Research and Equality (Kethy) issued a guide concerning LGBTQI issues, including trans people and healthcare discrimination. According to Kethy, "The area of health and safety is also often exposed to discrimination against LGBTQI people, where they can take the form of emergency services, malpractice, and trauma and self-harm (medical treatment). This is why LGBTQI people and trans people are reluctant to seek treatment (Moschovakou, N., Dani, S., 2018).

2.2. Stigma Towards Trans and Non-Binary People

Stigma towards members of the LGBTQ community can cause a lot of stress, anguish, sorrow, and trauma. Homophobia, a phrase that refers to hatred of people

who identify as gay or who are thought to be "sexually deviant," is based on stigma. (Sullivan, 2003). It encompasses prejudice against anyone identifying as lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, or questioning on a personal and cultural level. People in this population may have homophobia and the shame that stems from it. (Sullivan, 2003). Internalizing the stigma can cause harm to a person's sense of self, which can result in severe depression, frequent attempts at suicide, drug or alcohol misuse, and a worsening of general health (Baker, 2002; Sullivan, 2003).

In the past, people labeled as gay experienced significant stigma and discrimination. This violence includes physical and sexual assault as well as discriminatory remarks. But once Alfred Kinsey proved that being gay was normal—what was earlier thought to be "sexual deviancy"—the momentum of the civil rights organizations and the drive for acceptance began. (Baker, 2002). To foster an environment where gay people may have the same rights and courtesy as heterosexuals, gay people and activists for the LGBTQ community started the civil rights movement. With a study designed to provide factual proof that gay people are not only expected but just as psychologically healthy and bright as their heterosexual counterparts, Evelyn Hooker and Alfred Kinsley contributed to the cause. (Sullivan, 2003). By presenting compelling proof that homosexuality is not a mental illness and that gay people are just as psychologically healthy and well-adjusted as members of the heterosexual community, this ground-breaking research aided the gay rights movement (Sullivan, 2003). Sexual minorities gained power as the civil rights movement advanced and grew in popularity. They started to demonstrate against the oppression they had endured for generations, calling for equality and the privileges granted to the majority. (Baker 2002). One well-known and widely publicized protest during the Civil Rights Movement occurred in New York City in June 1969 at a gay

bar called the Stonewall Inn. Innocent patrons of this particular establishment were frequently detained during police searches solely because they belonged to a sexual minority. When a raid occurred the night of the demonstration, the customers instinctively protested and battled for their rights. (Baker, 2002). This act of defiance in the face of injustice became a motivating emblem for pursuing equality and human rights. Since this critical historic day, the fight for equality has gained momentum. Decreased stigma and greater equality for the LGB people have resulted from education and knowledge of this group. (Baker, 2002; Sullivan, 2003).

Children are exposed to societal norms for gender-appropriate behavior at a young age. (Baker, 2002; Sullivan, 2003). Children quickly pick up on social norms and how to act in a way that would not result in punishment, disapproval, or abuse. (Baker, 2002; Sullivan, 2003). Children internalize the views and values of their parents, guardians, and mentors regarding gender norms as a result, and they start to replicate these norms in their social circles. Follow societal norms for kids who don't naturally fit into these social groups.

It becomes a secret shame when transgender people naturally gravitate toward actions and products that are socially meant for the opposite gender. (Baker, 2001; Sullivan, 2003). The majority of these kids try to hide their genuine identities, thoughts, beliefs, and feelings from their families, friends, and peers because they live in a world of guilt and shame. As they make an effort to alter their ingrained thoughts, joys, and tendencies, this turns into a forbidden secret that plagues them. Others are so profoundly brainwashed with society's social, political, and religious beliefs that they fail to notice or misinterpret their impulses. Some people never become aware of their natural biases until later in life. (Baker, 2001; Sullivan, 2003). But suppressing these

inner truths can result in tension, which might produce melancholy, anxiety, or health issues (Baker, 2001; Sullivan, 2003).

The stigma attached to transgender and non-binary people is based on their gender nonconformity. Gender identity is a complex topic. This stigma exists because of the heteronormative beliefs of those who express themselves. Any gender difference is considered "depraved," "mentally ill," and "inferior" (King, Winter, & Webster, 2007). These heteronormative people are afraid of a threat to traditional gender roles. They work hard to maintain clear gender lines because they believe it is critical to keep the conventional gender and sex norms in place of societal and familial structures. Gender non-confirming people thus constitute a threat. People who identify as trans or non-binary face various issues in their daily lives, which can significantly impact their physical and mental health. Trans-specific healthcare needs and requirements are becoming more widely recognized, and unique stigma-related healthcare impediments are identified. Minority stress is "the discrepancy and conflict between the values of the minority group and the dominant culture or society and has been largely conceptualized and utilized within the sexual minority health arena" (Meyer, 2003). It can be exacerbated by experiences of marginalization and social exclusion caused by discrimination and biased societal attitudes and behaviors.

Furthermore, the psychosocial consequences of the COVID-19 epidemic, such as loss of autonomy, increased social isolation, and loneliness, are being recognized, particularly among older trans and non-binary people. Erasure is a societal exclusion phenomenon in which transgender identity or existence is ignored, minimized, or denied (Mc Cann, 2021).

2.2.1. Misgendering and Misnaming

McGlynn et al. (2020) carried an extensive study exposing the obstacles transgender people encounter while trying to get medical attention. The report makes it clear that one of the main challenges is when medical practitioners misidentify and misname transgender people. This problem results from the underlying presumption in the medical establishment that everyone is heterosexual, cisgender. It is especially concerning to run the danger of being "outed" against one's choice since it may lead to both short-term injury and long-term prejudice. These unfavorable effects sustain a cycle of fear and exclusion and go beyond just physical assault to include psychological and emotional damage. The report emphasizes even more how dangerous it is still to "come out" about one's transgender identity. Severe consequences of "coming out" might include violence and hostility in society. Reducing these risks requires, according to McGlynn et al. (2020), preserving the rights and privacy of transgender persons in all public and private domains. This involves putting policies and practices in place that support and affirm gender identities so that transgender persons may move about public spaces and medical facilities without fear of being misdiagnosed or revealed.

Furthermore, Gupta et al. (2016) assert that individuals within this group prefer being addressed using names other than those they ascribed at birth. The same also applies to the non-binary population. It is easier to see why the improper use of their preferred names/misgendering, especially by medical practitioners, is considered by individuals in these categories to be disrespectful and demeaning (Karakaya and Kutlu, 2021). These individuals' dilemma is that most of their legally recognized identification documents, such as healthcare insurance cards and passports, tend almost always to bear the gender they were assigned at birth (Gupta et al., 2016). It is

possible to see why they feel offended, particularly when someone addresses them using their birth-assigned gender categorization. It is important to note that medical practitioners must be aware of the preferred use of nonbinary pronouns such as 'they/them,' 'ze/zir,' 'ne/nirs,' or even hirs/hir for identification purposes (Gupta et al. 2016). Especially in Greece, the discrepancy between documents and preferred identification creates a situation where it is up to individuals to educate their healthcare staff on how to address them.

Notwithstanding, Giannou and Ioakimidis (2020) posit that most medical practitioners in Greece lack proper awareness of how to appropriately deal with people in the transgender category who visit healthcare facilities for treatment. Most transgender individuals cite 'name calling' as one of the most demeaning and derogatory treatments in most European healthcare settings (Karakaya and Kutlu, 2021). It becomes clear that there is a need for healthcare practitioners to be appropriately trained on how to interact with these sensitive individuals.

2.3. Religion and Bias Toward Homosexuality

Public opinion studies have often shown a strong correlation between religiosity and unfavorable opinions toward lesbians and LGBT people. (Olson et al., 2006; Stulhofer and Rimac, 2009; Whitley, 2009). Scientific evidence for such a connection has been found across several religious traditions. For instance, Finlay and Walther (2003) examined prejudice towards gays in the United States based on religious membership. They discovered that the most homophobic views against gays were held by conservative Protestants, followed by moderate Protestants and Catholics. (Maher, 2013; Schwartz, 2012; Whitley, 2009). Additionally, there are anti-homosexual views within the Jewish community (Coyle and Rafalin, 2001; Schnoor, 2003); Orthodox Jews were shown to be more prejudiced than Progressive

Jews. (Coyle and Rafalin, 2001). Hooghe et al. (2010b) observed that Muslims in the European environment had unfavorable attitudes toward homosexuality. A consistent pattern was discovered across all religions (Christianity, Protestantism, Judaism, and Islam): The more emotional the religious commitment, the more negative the attitude against homosexuality. (Fulton et al., 1999; Hunsberger and Jackson, 2005; Whitley, 2009). These findings offer compelling evidence that a communal religious environment fosters anti-homosexual attitudes. However, the nature and genesis of that association are still up for debate among academics, and other interpretations have been put up. Initially, various academics highlight the conventional perspective on gender and familial roles, noting the disapproval of homosexuality found in the teachings of the three major monotheistic religions (Christianity, Judaism, and Islam) as documented by Boellstorff (2005), Minwalla et al. (2005), and Yip (2005). According to this line of thought, the negative views on homosexuality present in religious texts and discussions are believed to influence individual attitudes, leading those who are deeply religious to adopt their faith's negative stance towards homosexuality (Fulton et al., 1999). Consequently, it is expected that individuals who are more religious will exhibit more negative attitudes towards homosexuals (Jäckle & Wenzelburger, 2015; McGee, 2016; Janssen & Scheepers, 2019; Pavlou, 2008; Georgiou, Patsantaras & Kamberidou, 2018).

However, other elements might also come into play. Since there is no research on religion and its effect on trans and non-binary people, we expect to find similar results and connections in the current study.

Attitudes And Discrimination Practices Of The Greek Church Towards LGBTQI People

According to a report by the Pew Research Center (2018), most Greeks identify as Orthodox Christians, resulting in Greece being an overwhelmingly Orthodox Christian nation. About, three-quarters of Greeks identify themselves as Orthodox Christians and view their religion as part of their national identity that portrays who is truthfully Greek. In addition, an estimated 55% of Greeks seem to consider religion a significant element of their personal life, and 92% of Greeks believe in God, with 59% believing in God without a doubt. When it comes to same-sex marriage, about seven in ten, or an estimated 70% of Greeks, firmly oppose it, which is a view shared in virtually all Central and Eastern European countries. (Pew Research Center, 2018). In a study examining the attitudes of heterosexual university students' attitudes toward same sex couples in seven European countries, including Greece, the findings supported that participant replies would be predicted by their country of origin, gender role traditionalism, contact, and religiosity. The investigation was sizable from April 2012 to November 2014, and 13,403 heterosexual college students from Belgium, Italy, France, Portugal, Poland, Spain, and Greece (38.7% males and 61.2% women) made up the sample. General attitudes about LGBT people, support for same-sex relationships and parenthood, opinions about gender roles and traditionalism, frequency, and quality of interactions with LGBT individuals, and religiosity were the key research factors.. Additionally, psychological factors, particularly religiosity and general attitudes about LG individuals, contributed to the explanation of these national variances. Out of the 7 countries Greece and Poland (which are also highly religious as a population) had the worst attitudes (D'Amore, et al., 2022).

The statistics do not come as a surprise because the Greek Orthodox Church, like many conservative religious institutions, holds a traditional view on marriage and

sexuality, considering sexual relations outside of marriage and same-sex relationships as sinful. The church's official position on homosexuality is that it is a disorder and a deviation from natural sexuality and that homosexual acts are immoral and should be avoided. Although, in theory, ecclesiastical activity promotes love, peace, and equality, there are many instances where the behavior and words of priests, despots, and even metropolitans indicate the recycling of stereotypes and social prejudices. More bizarrely, there are instances where confident church leaders disagree with Christian doctrine and preach in opposition to the Church of Greece's official stance. Applications to revoke same-sex couples' cohabitation agreements serve as an illustrative scenario. The opposition to same-sex couple cohabitation agreements is in contrast to Church doctrine simply because it comes in contrast to God's exhortation "...Be fruitful and multiply, and fill the earth..."(The English Standard Version Bible: Containing the Old and New Testaments with Apocrypha, 2009, Genesis 1:28a). According to the Greek Orthodox Church, homosexuality alone opposes God's creative plan of unity between a man and a woman, a unity that only reflects the idea and practice of procreation. The Church's doctrine recognizes and considers religious marriage and family as institutions that will bring children into the world to continue God's work. Therefore, a same-sex couple is deviant and dissenting from God's teaching and good faith.

During the same year, 2017, in an interview with the journalist Andrea Kimitri, the Primate of the Church of Cyprus covered a wide range of topics. When homosexuality came up, the Archbishop used the phrase "untied" and reiterated his firm belief that it is an "abnormality," once more stirring up controversy with his remarks. "I'm not trying to make the situation look pretty; it's an abnormality. The meaning remains the same whether I call it a nice term instead of an abnormality;

nothing changes" (T-Zine,2017). In the same year, The idea of recognizing gender identification legally was denounced by Archbishop Hieronymus. The law is anticipated to pass this week with a large majority in the Parliament. "All of these are games. They're just toys. The Church has stances of its own. Our nation has customs and families. The archbishop said, "All the others are inventions to waste our time. He added: "We are all dealing with loans, what we owe, this, that one when pressed to clarify what he meant when he advised us to look higher. We number perhaps about 10 million. Ten million more Greeks are dispersed throughout the globe. Does anyone have these folks in mind? Are we helping these folks in any way? It's a significant issue". In 2019, Greek Orthodox priest, Amvrosios of Kalavryta and Egion publicly made homophobic remarks on social media, including a post in which he urged his followers to "spit on" gay people. His comments were met with widespread condemnation from various groups, including LGBTQ+ rights organizations and some members of the Greek government. A three-judge lower court in Greece sentenced Metropolitan bishop Amvrosios to seven months in prison on January 28 as part of a ground-breaking case involving charges of hate speech, incitement to violence, and abuse of religious authority for an online homophobic article. Because the bishop was accused of a crime for the first time, the sentence was suspended for three years and included a 10,000 euro fine (T-Zine, 2019).

Although the Greek Orthodox Church, like many conservative religious institutions, holds a traditional view on marriage and sexuality, considering sexual relations outside of marriage and same-sex relationships as sinful, it is worth noting that there is a small movement within the Greek Orthodox Church to adopt a more compassionate and inclusive stance towards the LGBTQ+ community. Some clergy members and theologians have called for a more nuanced and empathetic

understanding of sexuality, acknowledging that it is not a choice and advocating for greater acceptance and support for LGBTQ+ individuals.

2.4. Minority Stress and Access to Healthcare Services

A significant body of research has shown a close relationship between minority stress and impaired access to healthcare services among gender-diverse individuals that sustains the need for stigma reduction interventions and gender-affirming medical support (Sha et al., 2021; Fisher et al., 2018). Sha and colleagues (2021) conducted a study to explore the association between gender minority stress and access to specific healthcare services using data from 277 individuals assigned male at birth but no longer identifying as male. The aforementioned multicenter cross-sectional study took place in China between January and June of 2020. The results of the analysis suggested limited uptake of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) testing, pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP), post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP), and gender-affirming medical therapy (hormones, surgeries) among the individuals assessed. Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and STI testing were likely hindered by discrimination and internalized transphobia. However, some gender minority stresses were also linked to higher utilization of some health services (Sha et al., 2021). The researchers also found that low STI testing rates identified among study interviewees were consistent with earlier research among transgender women around the world, including in China (Sha et al., 2021). The above findings indicate that internalized transphobia prevents Chinese transgender women and transfeminine people from getting tested for STIs but not HIV. The researchers also found that transgender people who encountered prejudice and internalized transphobia were likelier to utilize hormones that promote gender equality. Previous research from the US revealed that these pressures might make it more challenging to have gender-affirming access to

medical care. This result is consistent with the Gender Affirmation Framework, which contends that internalized transphobia and discrimination may lead to psychological distress and increase the need for gender affirmation (Sha et al., 2021).

2.5. Stigma-oriented Challenges in Healthcare Settings

Recent years have seen increased media coverage of transgender issues in Europe and the United States. Nonetheless, increased visibility in local and international media has not exempted transgender people from being the most underserved population in Europe (Gupta et al. 2016). These individuals are stigmatized in the workplace, home, and social places. The individuals undergo employment-oriented discrimination in workplaces, including hospitals. Mental abuse, rejection, and physical abuse are the most prominent forms of the stigma they face due to their sexual orientation (Gupta et al., 2016). Anderson et al. (2017) argue that such stigma makes them susceptible to suicidal ideation. Shields et al. (2012) contend that such stigmatization mostly meted on them after hospital visits, makes them increasingly susceptible to drug and substance abuse. In that respect, Karakaya and Kutlu (2021) call upon governments and society to be sensitive to this group, implying the shunning of stigmatization of individuals in this group. Affirmative action rooted in recognizing this category and their needs is a potent way to cement their concerns and afford them equal treatment with cisgender individuals, mainly in administering treatment within care settings.

2.5.1. Potential barriers faced by healthcare professionals when providing care for LGBTQI

Medical staff play an essential role in the healthcare challenges LGBTQI individuals face. However, most healthcare professionals also face several challenges

when providing care for the transgender population. Firstly, the lack of understanding of the specific needs of LGBTQI and their healthcare requirements forms the top challenge that most health practitioners face. Lack of awareness or consideration of the sexual orientation, gender identity, and sex characteristics of the LGBTQI people accessing healthcare forms are among the barriers affecting the quality performance of healthcare professionals. Healthcare professionals need to be given special training regarding the health needs of trans and non-binary individuals. Rules and guidelines have failed to consider the transgender population.

2.5.2. Stigma from Health Professionals

The quality of care provided by medical professionals is also becoming a more pressing issue for the LGBTQI community facing mental health disorders. For example, pharmacy students may be less inclined to counsel individuals affected by a mental health disorder about their medications (Lauber et al, 2006). Moreover, psychiatrists, nurses, and psychologists often maintain the same level of social distance with people with a mental health condition compared to the general population (Ücok et al., 2004). Studies report a significant procreation of compassionate care, including patients' feelings labeled and marginalized by providers (Sriram & Jabbarpour, 2005).

This stigma may be due to the high rates of burnout that healthcare workers, particularly social workers face. This burnout can lead to reduced empathy in their dealings with patients, and as well as an overall decrease in understanding of the same issues, which their patients are experiencing (Tsao et al., 2008). The authors Rayner, Allen, and Johnson (2005) elucidate that marginalization factors that can lead to early termination of therapy and decreased help seeking which diminish the efficacy of

treatment and the overall well-being of medically underserved populations. In addition to these external factors, stigmatizing ideology and personal experiences of health professionals may decrease their ability to intervene, identify, or refer those in need of mental health care (Gassman, Demone, and Albilal, 2001; Tam, Schmidt, and Weisner, 1996). Because of this, they may not be able to provide appropriate care, potentially alienating those with mental health illnesses (Siebert, 2004; 2005).

LGBTQ individuals face the danger of double stigmatization within the medical and mental health field. Studies have shown that medical professionals may have stigmatizing attitudes toward their gay patients, which can result in a decrease in the quality of care that they provide (Herek, 2007). The fact that this group does not have access to adequate medical care and mental health services is an important contributor to the problem. Consequently, this indicates that individuals who identify as gay may be experiencing elevated levels of stress as a result of stigmatization, in addition to the adverse effects on their health that are caused by inadequate healthcare. For example, one study found that more than half of LGBTQ people have faced discrimination when seeking healthcare services, including being denied care or dealt with harshness from health care providers (GLAAD, 2023). Further, less than a fifth of medical schools provide training in LGBTQ-specific health issues, contributing to a paucity of healthcare professionals equipped to address such needs (Kaiser Family Foundation, 2018).

This lack of care then leads to heightened minority stress (i.e. when gay people experience various forms of prejudice, discrimination, and conflictive internalized homophobia), all contributors in the development of psychological distress. Such environments have been associated with increased rates of mental health issues, including depression, anxiety, and suicidal ideation within LGBT populations (Meyer,

1995; Meyer, 2003). These stressors coupled with inadequate healthcare further cause a negative multiplier effect on their general well-being (Frontiers in Psychology, 2023).

It is also well-documented that healthcare providers often hold stigmatizing opinions about transgender persons. The same applies for people who identify as non-binary. A study conducted by MacFarlane et al. (2011) identified negative attitudes and lack of knowledge of medical students towards trans people. This in turn can impact the quality of treatment being extended to these patients. Similarly, Rondahl (2009) found nurses' opinions towards transgender patients as being discriminatory, which affected their treatment offering. The results of these studies should provide an impetus to reduce stigma to people with mental disorders and to people who identify as LGBTQI and especially those that are members of both of these groups. This ensures that everyone has access to comprehensive and equitable care.

2.6. Factors Considered in Determining the Attitude of Doctors

The views of doctors towards LGBTQI persons in Europe and other regions are greatly influenced by their personal beliefs and cultural upbringing. Lampalzer et al. (2019) argue that many doctors, influenced by cultural beliefs, consider gay sexual behavior to be sinful and so incorporate this idea into their medical procedures. Therefore, it is crucial to establish robust protection laws for LGBTQI persons. Most European nations do not have enough legislation in this regard. Furthermore, even in countries where protective regulations have been established for a significant period, there has been no apparent change in the attitudes of medical physicians. Take UK statutes as an example, the UK has a wide range of statutory frameworks such as the Gender Recognition Act of 2004 and the Equality Act of 2010 that are purposefully

designed to protect the rights of transgender people, enabling them to receive legal recognition and liberate themselves from discrimination. The results internationally have yielded a population that now sees a more accepting and equal society in the UK as a result of these laws. The Gender Recognition Act of 2004 now allows trans people to change their legal gender, which has led to some reduction in discrimination and improved social inclusion (Whittle, 2006). The Equality Act of 2010 offers still more protection against gender reassignment discrimination in employment and education by other means (Monro, 2010).

However, there are significant holes in the laws, particularly around healthcare. There are very few explicit provisions for trans-related healthcare leaving the provision and quality of care uneven. However, as Pearce (2018) in his research pointed out, there are some areas where the legislation promotes equality and provides protection, but it does not fully tackle the unique health care problems faced by transgender people. In particular, these laws do not cover transgender people with mental health disorders who have greater mental health needs that can be met through gender-specific treatments to reduce psychological distress. (Pearce, 2018).

The International Lesbian and Gay Association of Europe (ILGA-Europe) is correct to keep the subject of LGBTQI health on the table, especially in light of the growing prejudice against transgender individuals. This is despite the fact that there is a legislative attempt to improve treatment. Lampalzer et al. (2019) noted that there has been an increase in discrimination against transgender rights in society, as well as a limited enforcement of the legislative safeguards that are now in place. This resistance from society has manifested itself in a variety of forms, including increased levels of hostility and bigotry that transgender persons are constantly confronted with. Furthermore, Lampalzer et al. (2019) stipulate that health services have evolved in a

different way and have not progressed to keep pace with the legislative advances. In other words, they have not expanded to keep up with the changes. Since the laws to protect trans people have been established, health systems have still not transformed sufficiently to do justice to trans patients. For example, reports exist of extended waitlists for gender-affirming procedures (tertiary waitlists upwards of seven years), unspecialized and unsupportive GPs, as well as inadequate mental health care specifically designed for trans people (Lampalzer et al., 2019). These problems exemplify that, even though there have been extensive legal gains in the UK for trans people, progress towards reaching equality is slowed due to inconsistency with care provisions, resulting in ongoing gaps and unmet needs among transgender individuals.

In addition, there have been many changes in the UK around hormone blockers, with the Cass Review being significant in shaping many of these. The Cass Review, launched in 2020, looked at the care offered to children and young people by the Gender Identity Development Service (GIDS), part of the Tavistock and Portman NHS Foundation Trust. A 2022 interim report of its findings raised concerns that the clinical approach was not as robust as the House of Lords had been led to believe and that long-term outcomes of hormone blockers were not well established (BBC News, 2022). As a result, the review has been used to justify greater oversight and limitations have been introduced to the access of these services, making it even more difficult for trans youth to access the timely and affirming care that they require (The Guardian, 2022). Detractors say that such a generalized view has resulted in the conclusions of the review being cited to legitimize conservative policies that could prove to be extremely harmful to people seeking trans healthcare in the UK. The downstream effects have prompted contentious discussions among healthcare

workers, lawmakers, and trans people on the right level of cautiousness versus access to vital medical procedures (Pink News, 2022).

Conclusively, UK legal progress towards transgender rights and nondiscrimination has been greatly advanced compared to others; however inadequacies in healthcare provision and public backlash have impeded the full realization of rights. This suggests that British Society requires more robust and enforced measures within both the legal and healthcare sectors. This underscores the crucial necessity for focused advocacy and intervention to address the specific health disparities experienced by the transgender community. Amplified discrimination composites existing obstacles to healthcare access and quality, requiring a targeted tactic to endorse equitable care and defend the rights of all individuals, regardless of gender identity. By prioritizing LGBTQI health concerns, ILGA-Europe can play a fundamental role in challenging systemic injustices and advancing a more inclusive healthcare agenda across Europe.

Nevertheless, there are still issues as religion often shapes physicians' opinions more than their professional obligation to treat everyone equally, regardless of gender identification. Such ILGA-Europe activities are crucial in promoting LGBTQI health rights and inclusion within healthcare systems, as Jackson et al. (2019) demonstrate. Transgender people's life are greatly impacted by the attitude of physicians; prejudice and treatment rejection are still common in Greece and Europe. However, doctors can be one of the most powerful allies for LGBTQI people. This paper aims to investigate, in Greece, the factors that contribute to shaping doctors' attitudes toward trans and non-binary people, including gender, age, education, contacts with LGBTQI people, work environment, and religious beliefs. This will help give a more profound

understanding of the intersection of personal and professional biases in health care provision.

2.7. Conversion Therapy

"Conversion therapy' (C.T.) doesn't have a settled definition but refers broadly to a range of practices that pursue to alter, 'cure,' or suppress a person's sexual orientation or gender identity. C.T. practices include psychological treatments and spiritual counseling" (U.K. Parliament, 2021). Conversion therapy, also known as reparative therapy or sexual orientation change efforts (SOCE), refers to any attempt to change a person's sexual orientation, gender identity, or gender expression through psychological or spiritual interventions.

These interventions often involve techniques that are considered harmful and unethical, including electric shock therapy, hypnosis, and aversive conditioning. The goal of conversion therapy is to change a person's sexual orientation or gender identity from homosexual or transgender to heterosexual or cisgender, based on the belief that these identities are unnatural or sinful. However, no scientific evidence supports the efficacy of conversion therapy. It is widely considered a harmful practice that can cause lasting psychological damage, including depression, anxiety, and suicide ideation. For this reason, many countries have banned or restricted conversion therapy, and several professional organizations, including the American Psychological Association, have condemned it as unethical and ineffective.

Lesbians, gays, and trans are among the people across Europe who submitted to conversion therapy by doctors. According to conversion therapy, trans identities, homosexuality, and bisexuality are mental disorders. Conversely, doctors have been characterized by approaching such cases based on religious beliefs and believing that

such people should be transformed before being masked by the darkness. An example of conversion therapy was experienced in Slovakia. An LGBTQI patient was difficult after a doctor agreed to give the patient counseling to change her life and sexual orientation (Donisi et al., 2020). Although some member states still practice conversion therapy in Europe, some countries, such as the U.K., have different opinions. In the United Kingdom, the law is under review to prohibit conversion therapy, thus protecting both vulnerable minors and the LGBTQI population.

Recently in Greek law N.4931_2022, doctors for all, have equal and quality access to the services of the national health service organization and primary health care and other provisions. Prohibited conversion therapies for minors; unfortunately, restrictive conditions as well as deficiencies, such as prohibiting the conduct of these practices only to vulnerable persons (children or adults who are in legal aid within the meaning of the Civil Code), forbids the practice of "conversion" only to professionals who apply them only in return for financial compensation, and in particular that anyone who applies these practices to adults must first have their explicit consent. This is very problematic. In addition, in its Conclusion, the Committee of the Action Plan for Equality of LGBTQI proposes a total ban on these practices and the modification of the Code of Medical Ethics to include the expression, identity, and gender characteristics explicitly.

2.8. Medicalization of Intersex Variance

According to OII Europe, the umbrella organization of European human rights-based intersex organizations. "Intersex is an umbrella term for the experience of being born with a body that does not meet the societal expectation of male or female. Intersex people are individuals born with sex characteristics that are either

female and male at the same time or not entirely female or male or neither female nor male. Our sex characteristics and bodies are healthy variations of the human sexes" (OII,2018).

Unfortunately, it is impossible to know the exact number of intersex people because data are incomplete, and the intersex people are in obscurity. It is estimated that 1 in 1500-2000 people is born with genitals that cannot be classified in the gender dipole, and of these, 0.1-0.2% undergo reconstructive genital surgery (Blackless et al., 2000). People born with obscure genitals are directly pathological because, unfortunately, "the health system still considers anything abnormal beyond the gender dipole" (Woweries, 2012). So, at this point, the problems faced by intersex people resemble the issues faced by trans people because, in many ways, these challenges converge.

Intersex people undergo remedial surgery at an early age against the doctors' or guardians' will. These surgeries have practically no therapeutic application; they aim at the forced integration of intersex people of both sexes (Lembke 2011, Moron-Puech 2011). Such surgeries create successive traumas in the psyche of these people. I quote a doctor's advice to intersex parents of a child "Know that your child will be socially devastated if someone learns about it; think about school or swimming lessons" (Plattner, 2008). These surgeries have been condemned by the intersex community, which claims to have had devastating effects such as psychological disorders, depression, sleep disorders, early osteoporosis, low libido, thyroid problems, deprivation of reproductive capacity, and much more. These procedures often involve amputations, sterilization, castration, and clitoridectomy and violate the physical integrity of these children. Most importantly, they are all done without the informed consent of the usually too young to support their rights.

The wrong assignment of sex to children also threatens their mental integrity, and statistics show that incorrect assignment approaches 40% of cases. The bottom line is that these individuals reject the gender attributed to them (Tammam-Mattis, 2012).

The medical healthcare sector in European countries monopolizes knowledge of inter conditions. Intersex variations are regarded as a disorder of sex development based on the pathologization concepts in the healthcare sector of those countries. Medical teams in Europe have been characterized by flawed working approaches as far as LGBTQI is concerned (Orzechowski et al., 2020). Most medical teams need to work more multi-disciplinary as it will assist them in becoming aware of the binary thinking criteria. Decisions focused on affecting LGBTQI people should fulfill their rights rather than impacting their physical integrity regarding their intersex status. The de-pathologization of trans identity can't change the fact that intersex people continue to be pathologized. Despite continued pressure from activists and experts, the World Health Organization has included in the ICD-11 the diagnosis of "Disorders of Sex Development," which has been described as stigmatizing and hazardous by intersex people (OII,2018).

The pathologization of intersex people is the basis for human rights violations. Many intersex infants and children and adolescents and adult intersex people undergo, without their consent, irreversible surgeries and other "normalization" medical treatments; the World Health Organization has the responsibility to contribute in this direction.

2.9. Prohibition of Blood Donation

The prohibition of blood donation by homosexuals refers to a policy prohibiting men who have sex with men (MSM) from donating blood or plasma. The approach is based on the belief that MSM is at higher risk of transmitting HIV and other blood-borne diseases. However, this policy has been widely criticized as discriminatory. It assumes that all MSM are high-risk individuals and ignores other factors that may increase their risk of HIV infection, such as unprotected sex, intravenous drug use, or sexual behavior with multiple partners. Moreover, many countries have adopted more inclusive blood donation policies that assess a person's risk factors for HIV infection rather than banning entire populations. In some countries, MSM can donate blood if they have been celibate for a certain period, usually 12 months. Critics argue that this policy perpetuates harmful stereotypes about MSM and stigmatizes them as inherently diseased or unclean, leading to increased discrimination and marginalization. They also point out that no scientific basis exists for the blanket ban on MSM blood donation, as modern blood screening techniques are highly effective at detecting HIV and other blood-borne pathogens.

Germany, Croatia, and Italy are European nations prohibiting blood donation from the LGBTQI population. In these countries, healthcare professionals have been prevented from accepting blood donated by people engaged in same-sex behavior. They are believed to be at higher risk of being affected by sexually transmitted infections. Gay, bisexual, and trans people in such countries are excluded from donating blood regardless of the action not supported by the law (Zeeman et al., 2019). The action against LGBTQI individuals is discriminatory and constitutes a denial of their rights. The law only requires permanently excluding those whose

behaviors expose them to a higher risk of contracting STIs. The law is not specific that LGBTQI should be banned, as heterosexuals can also contract STIs.

Greece implemented a lifetime ban on blood donation by men who have sex with men (MSM) in 1977. This prohibition on blood donation was upheld until recently, in January 2022, when there was a lifting of this irrational and shameful restriction on blood donation for LGBT people. Specifically, according to the G.P. 900/2022 Joint Ministerial Decision of the Ministry of Health (Government Gazette 36 / B / 10-01-2022) on the subject: The specific item on the content form that documents the "History of Blood Donor," stating that anyone who has a homosexual experience since 1977 must be excluded and not allowed to donate blood is henceforth eliminated.

2.10. Lack of Mental Health Services

The lack of mental health services in European countries has led to increased discrimination and stigmatization among the non-binary population due to the multiple layers of marginalization. Research on European nations showed that Belgium, France, and Portugal lack specialist mental health services and counseling programs for LGBTI patients (Sherriff et al., 2019). The lack of such services leads to discrimination against populations seeking medical assistance. With no specific agenda to counsel the non-binary and trans, most people remain in hiding because they fear disclosing their identity will bring more harm than good.

Moreover, even where mental health services do exist, documents used by healthcare professionals are created based on the hypothesis that all people are heterosexual and cisgender (Grant et al., 2011). Consideration of the needs of the LGBTQI population in most healthcare institutions has not been given (Institute of

Medicine, 2011). Lack of consideration or allocation of resources to help guide LGBTQI people has led to unsuitable advice by healthcare practitioners (Lim et al., 2018). Inappropriate data entry for such patients has also resulted in lesbians and bisexual women submitting to the wrong contraceptive services (Mann & Crowley, 2017).

2.11. Lack of Understanding of LGBTQI Issues

One global issue is a lack in education and training in LGBTQI care for all medical providers. Therefore, they are often unable to provide effective care to LGBTQI patients (Jones et al., 2018). This leads to missed diagnoses and overdiagnoses and therefore medical errors, which in turn impacts those who identify as LGBTQI who consequently do not receive the care they require, when they require it. For instance, a transgender woman (assigned male at birth) shows up at a health center complaining of chest pain. If a clinician does not know that men and women present a different set of symptoms for heart disease they might just mark off typical symptoms because of what they are used to seeing with cisgender men and women. Heart disease often presents in a different way for cisgender men, usually as intense chest pain, whereas women (and transgender women on hormone therapy) mostly report symptoms like fatigue, shortness of breath, or mild discomfort in the chest's center. Because of this lack of knowledge, a clinician could possibly misdiagnose that chest pain as a light condition. Given that difficult position, this could throw off the diagnosis and treatment of heart disease for an extended period of time, during which the patient would be at serious risk (Smith & Brown, 2018). Consequently, more and more individuals have benefitted from the promising outcomes of the programs that have been implemented to encourage the uptake of LGBTQI-inclusive practices and intensive training regimens by various medical practitioners (Orzechowski et al.,

2020). For example, the Health4LGBTI project from the Council of Europe has focused on changing the way doctors are trained and how they go about providing care to more accurately address the health needs of LGBTQI people in their basic medical education (Council of Europe, 2018).

The project Health4LGBTI identified some of the main barriers that LGBTQI people are often confronted with when dealing with health problems: unaware and insensitive healthcare professionals and the impact of social norms replicating the stigma against non-hetero-normative people. In response to these findings, the project developed a culturally competent curriculum for healthcare professionals. This set of modules addresses a variety of subjects, such as the significance of using language that is inclusive of all populations, specific health disparities faced by LGBTQI individuals, and improvements to support and enhance established or potential best practices for a clinical setting. Much like the successful interventions, the results of the Health4LGBTI project demonstrate the urgent importance of tackling the issue head on (Council of Europe, 2018). For example, their work pointed out how normative biases in medical environments can create situations where LGBTQI patients may be uncomfortable or feel unsafe, which then lowers their access to healthcare. Healthcare providers can support the health and well-being of LGBTQI patients by adopting patient education and training programs that emphasize inclusivity and respect. Also worth noting, the project's evaluations of these trainings have yielded some positive results as well. At the end of the Health4LGBTI training, healthcare professionals said they now felt more confident in caring for LGBTQI individuals, had a better understanding of their health needs, and were more committed to implementing equality practices in their contexts (Council of Europe, 2018).

In conclusion, despite ongoing issues and difficulties related to an absence of LGBTQI-specific training for healthcare givers, projects such as Health4LGBTI are evidence of positive steps towards potential improvements. Healthcare systems can work towards more comprehensive, culturally sensitive care for LGBTQI patients by focusing on addressing gaps in education and awareness and better responding to the health needs that most impact this population.

2.12. Normativity

There is a substantial influence that normativity has on the way in which non-binary persons and the LGBTQI community as a whole experience healthcare, which often leads to marginalization and discrimination. The tight adherence to binary standards, which is prominent in medical settings, has been shown to stigmatize individuals who do not comply with these norms, according to studies. According to Health4LGBTI (Council of Europe, 2018) and Lim et al. (2018), healthcare practitioners may even feel the need to discourage behaviors and manifestations that depart from the standards of cisgender and heterosexual groups. Because of this normative prejudice, major hurdles are created, such as the absence of acceptable medical forms that only provide binary gender alternatives. This makes some people who do not belong to either gender feel invalidated and mandates them to choose an option that is not an accurate portrayal of their identity. Moreover, non-binary or transgender persons frequently necessitate access to top-notch healthcare services, such as hormone treatment, which can be challenging or subject to prejudice while seeking treatment.

To do this, a comprehensive approach to address normativity in the healthcare sector should incorporate a diverse range of references and novel research to achieve the required level of inclusion.

2.13. Factors that have triggered health disparities among LGBTQI Individuals in Europe

Discrimination against trans people in Europe is experienced in schools and communities. LGBTQI people in Europe face discrimination and inhumane treatment that varies in intensity based on where they live (McGlynn et al., 2020). The healthcare sector has played a significant role in the discrimination against LGBTQI in various ways. Due to their negative attitude toward trans people in Europe, doctors may misdiagnose them or provide them with low quality services (McGlynn et al., 2020). Sterilization forms another type of oppression the trans and intersex community faces because of doctors' negative attitudes regarding their status (Human Rights Watch, 2017).

On some occasions, even if health providers are members of the LGBTQI community, that does not guarantee that trans and non-binary people will not face discrimination. Health disparities among LGBTQI people in Europe are partly caused by stigmatization within the LGBTQI group itself, known as "in-fighting" or intra-community discrimination. This intra-community discrimination contributes to health disparities by excluding and marginalizing certain sections within the community based on gender identity, racial background, and socioeconomic status (Davy, 2015). Although the LGBTQI community advocates for equality and inclusion, these internal divisions can lead to social exclusion and perpetuate harmful stereotypes, ultimately affecting the access to and quality of healthcare for trans and non-binary individuals

(Bauer et al., 2009). It is important to recognize the health disparities that result from intra-community stigma, limit people's contribution to their shared identities and creates a space of oppression, not freedom.

For instance, several studies have observed that transgender individuals have been subject to discrimination and exclusion in LGBTQI spaces, with their identities and experiences being delegitimized or marginalized by cisgender gay and lesbian persons (Grant et al., 2011; Lim et al., 2018). In summary, the presence of intra-community discrimination within the LGBTQI community exacerbates health disparities by further marginalizing trans and non-binary individuals, even when healthcare providers themselves are part of the LGBTQI community.

Additionally, individuals of color in the LGBTQI community are likely to face racism and microaggressions from their white peers, increasing health disparities and the formation of social inequalities (Grant et al., 2011). As a result, Task Force on Victims of Stigmatization condemned intra-community stigma to public health (Council of Europe, 2018; Logie et al., 2018). The outcomes of intra-community stigma on the health and well-being of the LGBTQI group are severe. It has been established that experiencing discrimination, whether from within or outside of the LGBTQI community, has been associated with a higher rate of mental illness, increased substance addiction, decreased access to quality healthcare (Grant et al., 2011), and reduced use in other health-promoting conducts (Lim et al., 2018).

In conclusion, while the intra-community stigmatization itself is not a topic to be easily eradicated, the health disparities created are of pressing concern. To mitigate its impact, it is imperative that inclusivity and solidarity within the LGBTQI community upheld. Intra-community discrimination can be challenged with

intersectional frameworks applied to LGBTQI advocacy with due regard to the voices and experiences of those marginalized within the community. Only by recognizing and accounting for the nuances of intra-community interaction can a more equitable and supportive environment be made for all LGBTQI persons.

In 2011, the Institute of Medicine published a report regarding the health disparities faced by transgender groups in Europe. According to the report, trans people face health disparities that vary depending on age and specific orientations (LGBTI equality and human rights in Europe and Central Asia, 2021). LGBTQI people in European nations tend to avoid or delay seeking medical attention because of such disparities compared to heterosexual individuals. The discrimination such a group encounters has risen over the past years due to the increased number of doctors and other health practitioners' negative attitudes.

Various factors associated with transgender people in Europe have been the leading causes of their discrimination in the healthcare sector. For instance, trans people in Europe are likely to have insurance coverage, which is essential in determining the quality of patient services (Zeeman et al., 2019). Lack of insurance coverage has resulted in delays in the treatment of LGBTQI people. Most European hospital programs protect the patients' interests covered under different insurance companies. Expecting to be attended without insurance coverage can be difficult. Personal bias and negative attitudes from healthcare professionals have also interfered with delivering healthcare services to Transgender people in Europe (Zeeman et al., 2019).

2.14. Health Factors Affecting Trans People and Informed Consent Issues

Fear of discrimination and stigmatization in most healthcare sectors in Europe against trans people has played a significant role in creating boundaries. According to the U.K.'s healthcare sector analysis, the LGBTQI community faces increased mental health problems such as stress and anxiety. About 52% of young LGBTQI individuals in the U.K. have been reported to hurt themselves (self-harm) because healthcare professionals provide no access to counseling or suitable therapy sessions (Parameshwaran et al., 2017). The cultural context is underpinning the wrong decision-making among LGBTQI. Research conducted by the Stone Wall LGBT in the U.K. approached the healthcare sector by dividing it into three sections. The report's four sections are mental health, alcohol, and drug use, discrimination in health care, and smoking. According to the report, the mental health section statistics were alarming. Half of the non-binary individuals were confronted with stress in 2020 (Parameshwaran et al., 2017).

The increase in the number of LGBTQI individuals who experienced mental disorders because of the barriers they encountered while reaching out for medical assistance in the U.K. was shocking due to the discriminatory attitude of healthcare practitioners. 13% of the LGBT people in the U.K. have been treated unequally by doctors or nurses just because they are part of the LGBT community (Parameshwaran et al., 2017). The negative attitude of most doctors against non-binary people has been the leading cause of all discrimination issues in healthcare centers. In 2020, half of the LGBTQ individuals in the U.K. experienced depression because of the discrimination they faced from the healthcare sector. One out of seven people in the U.K. avoids seeking medical services as they fear discrimination from doctors and other healthcare

practitioners. About 23% of LGBTQs witnessed negative remarks or prejudice against fellow individuals by healthcare staff in 2020 (Parameshwaran et al., 2017).

Internalized homophobia is a significant risk factor that triggers mental health illnesses in homosexual individuals. The intensity of the issue shows the urgency for Belgium to focus on protecting the rights of the LGBTQ population. Discrimination and stigmatization of trans and non-binary people are caused by a lack of social support and counseling from most health practitioners nationwide (Dhoest, 2019). Social support is the best approach the healthcare sector should capitalize on to boost the psychological well-being of the transgender and non-binary population. LGBTQ people face discrimination from communities, schools, and even social media. Since some of them have low self-esteem, this leads to poor decision-making as they cannot protect themselves against such daily embarrassment.

Most European countries fail to adhere to the policy provided by ILGA-Europe regarding the LGBTQ population's health welfare. One of the most common incidences was recently spotted in Finland. The U.N. Committee on the Rights of the Child (CRC) found that Finland had failed to consider a child's best interest as they rejected his asylum request because his parents were a lesbian couple. By denying him that right, Finland failed to protect its citizens against the real risk of irreparable harm, as the child was left with no other option but to return to Russia. The health challenges that most LGBTQ parents face affect them, and practices impact their children's lives. According to U.N.'s research, several children face many disparities because of their parent's sexual orientation. Government policies and laws are among the factors that have impacted the healthcare sector regarding the LGBTQ population. For instance, Sweden legalized sexual activities in 1944 for people above 18 years old. However, the country also passed a law prohibiting sex in gay saunas and

prostitution. They believed that would help combat the high spread of the HIV disease. In 1972, Sweden became the first country that legalize transgender identities.

A series of challenges also appear in the healthcare appointments offered to trans people in Scotland. They must travel for long hours, and services are inconsistent, as in most healthcare sectors. The services are characterized by a lack of qualified people with professional skills suitable for LGBTQI.

The healthcare campaigns in Scotland focus on providing a system of equality for all trans people. They also aim to support informed consent to increase the number of person-centered care for LGBTQI (Phipps, 2018).). Although ending healthcare discrimination among trans people is the main objective of most healthcare campaigns, they have also fought for increased funding to help achieve the NHS waiting-for-time standards in Scotland.

In Scotland, waiting time for gender identity clinics is worse than in any other NHS outpatient clinic. Trans people in Scotland are forced to wait for more than two years to get their first appointment (Hunter & Boyle, 2020). Imagine seeking medical consultancy regarding an important issue but being told to wait more than a year before getting an appointment. Such situations have discouraged most LGBTQI from seeking medical services in Scotland. Every day of waiting to start treatment causes distress to LGBTQI individuals, as sometimes they are affected by painful health conditions (Hunter & Boyle, 2020). Everyone deserves to have easy access to healthcare.

LGBTQ relationships in Italy are not criminalized. Discrimination and violence based on gender identity and sexual orientation still cause severe health problems. LGBTQs in Italy are perceived as ill by some healthcare practitioners

(Rosati, Pistella & Baiocco, 2020). Some doctors in Italy offer therapy sessions to their LGBTQ patients to convert them to heterosexuality. In 2012, the Italian *Tetu* magazine presented homosexuality as an illness that had to be treated with persistence to not spread across the country, especially amongst religious believers. Notably, a person's driving license was suspended because he revealed himself as gay during a military service medical examination in 2012 (Brett, 2018). According to the medical analysis, the license was suspended because homosexuality enacts a state of sexual disturbance that would likely affect his psycho-physical State. According to *Tetu* magazine, the incident occurred in 2002 (Brett, 2018).

The National Office against Racial Discrimination in Italy has decided to fight against discrimination against sexual orientation. Though the fight against discrimination based on sexual orientation is not part of the office's official mandate, the office has offered informal conciliations for arguments against LGBTQ individuals (Lavorigna et al., 2017). Italy implemented administrative procedures that allow for legal recognition of LGBTQ people's gender. In 2011, the court reaffirmed that sterilization should not be considered a mandatory requirement when reassignment of gender is being considered. Italian lawmakers were expected to submit draft legislation by the end of July 2020 to help implement the anti-discrimination law. Homophobia is widespread across Italy, as most LGBTQs cannot live independently. The attack on Lorenzo left him in a very delicate state in 2020, and the fact that he was forced to undergo facial surgery left LGBTQ individuals in Italy in a state of terror. Most LGBTQ individuals kept their status a secret because they feared Lorenzo. It would probably be safe to assume that the members of the LGBTQ family were afraid to walk freely on the street or even seek medical

attendance and disclose their status after that attack. Unlike other European nations - such as France- Italy is still resistant to ensuring equality in the treatment of LGBTQs.

Italy is one of the European countries with a relatively staunch ecclesiastical base with religious beliefs that do not include LGBTQ individuals. Most doctors in Italy perceive LGBT individuals as disciples of the devil who should be banned from mixing with others' souls, just as interpreted by the scriptures (Rosati, Pistella & Baiocco, 2020). This belief has triggered a lot of hatred and discriminative cases against LGBTQ by doctors. In 2015, a study was conducted in Italy to assess nurses' and doctors' attitudes and knowledge of gay and lesbian patients. Italian nurses knew that homosexuality is a natural expression of sexuality (Lavorgna et al., 2017). Women nurses and doctors scored the highest numbers of positive attitudes. The increased prevalence of mental disorders among the LGBTQ remains the most extraordinary form of discrimination that non-binary individuals are forced to undergo in Italy (Prandelli & Testoni, 2020).

For several years, Rutgers University conducted sexual health research in the Netherlands. The study was mainly focused on the Dutch health sexuality representation of the population between 15 and 70 years old (Ploumen & Livas, 2020). According to the study, LGBT people do not receive attention as far as healthcare is concerned. LGBTQ individuals are vulnerable, considering certain aspects of sexual health (Ploumen & Livas, 2020). The vulnerability of the LGBTs in the Netherlands has forced the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment to extend condom usage to control HIV/AIDs and STDs among LGBTQs. In 2014, a law entered into force, making it easier for transgender individuals to change their gender on their essential documents, such as birth certificates (Soto-Lafontaine, 2020). That law revised the Netherlands 'civil code. The

amendment contributed to the attainment of equal rights and the protection of LGBTQ.

Since the focus of this paper is the attitude of doctors and not the overall situation of LGBTQI health in Europe, the above countries were randomly chosen based on the most current research to provide examples of the conditions in Europe.

Gays and lesbians in Europe tend to hide their identities as they fear people's reactions after discovering their status. Research conducted in 2012 on LGBTQI people shows that 42% of trans people are not open about their status with healthcare personnel (LGBTQI equality and human rights in Europe and Central Asia, 2021). Failing to disclose LGBTQI status is accompanied by a series of health consequences that people in the transgender category are forced to face for deciding to keep their status secret. For instance, it might provide a better opportunity against irreversible consequences on their health. Older LGBTQI people are at significant risk of being adversely affected when dealing with the healthcare sector. They have a high rate of anxiety related to their past experiences with doctors and other healthcare practitioners (Jackson et al., 2019). If they had a harrowing experience in the past, it is harder for them to trust again in the healthcare sector. Their earlier expertise makes it hard to cater to their health needs when they age.

Inappropriate curiosity is one problem trans people face daily when dealing with the healthcare sector. Doctors' negative comments regarding LGBTQI or even refusing to treat after disclosing their status have affected most trans people's confidence (Jackson et al., 2019). Not consulting partners of the same sex (based on legal documents) is another healthcare issue affecting trans people in Europe (Lampalzer et al., 2019). Most doctors fail to provide care information given to such

partners. Denying such information affects them psychologically. Some hospitals deny LGBTQI the right to visit patients upon admission to European hospitals (Lampalzer et al., 2019). Having a child or partner in the hospital and being denied the opportunity to know how they are being treated or see them constitutes a violation of human rights. Lesbian and Bisexual women receiving fertility treatment in hospitals are among the most discriminated against in Europe (Lampalzer et al., 2019). Most doctors discriminate against them due to their status and deny them such opportunities. In the healthcare sector, LGBTQI individuals living with HIV/AIDS often face heightened levels of oppression and stigmatization, exacerbating their already marginalized status. Studies have repeatedly demonstrated that members of the LGBTQI community who are HIV/AIDS positive encounter overlapping kinds of stigma and discrimination; this is commonly known as "double stigmatization" (Herek, 2002; Logie & Gadalla, 2009).

Research has shown that healthcare professionals can have discriminatory attitudes and actions against LGBTQI people living with HIV/AIDS, which can lead to false beliefs about their lives and health practices (Herek, 2002; Logie & Gadalla, 2009). Further distancing and marginalizing LGBTQI people seeking healthcare services, stigmatization can take many forms, such as unwillingness to give care, judgmental attitudes, and confidentiality violations.

These resulting health impacts and reduced access to healthcare services and other essentials is increased as a result of the intersectionality between HIV/AIDS, race, and LGBTQI identities with additional stigma and discrimination from the larger society (Gordon,2022). LGBTQI persons living with HIV/AIDS, in particular African-American men, have a higher burden of discrimination which in effect makes it difficult for them to access help from their trusted physicians and other

professionals. Studies have illustrated that people with HIV, especially some racial groups who have been marginalized, experience wide-scale discrimination within the healthcare system and therefore tend to be diagnosed later, avoid care, and have worse health outcomes. These barriers have been only exacerbated by the toxic brew of stigma against trans and gender diverse people, especially communities of colour, and those who are LGBTIQ+, showing us that if we are to remove these barriers we must tackle all forms of discrimination (HIV.gov, 2023; TCF.org, 2023; National Institute of Mental Health, 2023).

To address the issue of stigmatization against LGBTIQ individuals living with HIV/AIDS in the healthcare sector, comprehensive strategies are needed. This includes implementing training programs for healthcare providers to increase awareness and sensitivity towards the unique needs and experiences of LGBTIQ individuals, particularly those living with HIV/AIDS (Logie & Gadalla, 2009). Additionally, initiatives aimed at promoting LGBTIQ-inclusive healthcare policies and practices, such as those advocated by the World Health Organization (WHO), are crucial in challenging stigma and discrimination within healthcare settings and fostering environments that affirm the dignity and rights of all individuals, regardless of their HIV status or sexual orientation (World Health Organization, 2017). By addressing the intersecting forms of oppression faced by LGBTIQ individuals living with HIV/AIDS, we can work towards achieving equitable and inclusive healthcare for all.

Policies accompanied by the recognition of the WHO's diagnosis have affected the lives of LGBTIQ people in many ways. Trans people in Europe are forced to undergo surgeries against human beings' ethical standards (Zeeman et al., 2019).

For example, in Europe, gender-affirming surgeries, including mastectomies, hysterectomies, and forced genital removal are frequently practiced without proper informed consent. According to Zeeman et al. (2019) and for a large number of instances, these procedures are done without proper information leaving patients with the responsibility of making important choices concerning their own bodies. This absence of genuine consent is a serious matter because it violates the basic human right of self-determination and bodily integrity. This matters because it is relevant to the question of the ethics of medical practices. These regulations underscore the importance of the informed consent of a patient and his /her/their freedom of choice when it comes to any medical procedure. In short, informed consent means the patient has the right to know the basic nature of the treatment, alternative treatment, risk, and effect that is possible and then agree to it. The principle of regard for individual autonomy is to allow the patient the right to decide for themselves about what they do to their body, and how they prefer the way they are treated medically, that is, without coercion or force. The importance of this principle is magnified for underserved populations such as trans people who may face dimensions of bias and discrimination throughout the healthcare setting. Common ethical principles like informed consent, respect for patient autonomy, and comprehensive pre-surgical counseling are even more often neglected. This inconsideration for ethical medical practices violates the bodily autonomy of transgender people and maintains distinctive types of systemic prejudice and discrimination towards the transgender community. The image of people being held down and mutilated in a dark alley or backroom by secretive methods highlights a horrifying picture of individuals who are forced to undergo irreparable surgery and not even know it, a tragedy in the healthcare system (HIV.gov, 2023; TCF.org, 2023; National Institute of Mental Health, 2023).

The scholarly conversation reaffirms the imperative of developing healthcare systems and policies that protect gender variance and informed consent. Protecting the rights and lives of transgender people necessitates access to affirming and comprehensive healthcare services extricated from outside control constraint. Moreover, it is important for healthcare professionals to obtain enough training to handle the unique healthcare needs and outcomes of patients identifying as transgender (Eckstrand et al., 2019).

The process can be considered inhumane and painful during such procedures as people are subjected to physical pain. Some people submitted to such surgeries end up infertile for the rest of their lives; some die in the process. The most painful fact is that most intersex people exposed to such operations have not consented; such practice is torture by the United Nations. According to survey research conducted in 2012 by the E.U. Fundamental Rights Agency, 22% of trans people felt that they had been discriminated against by healthcare practitioners (LGBTQI Equality and Human Rights in Europe and Central Asia, 2021).

Various health issues in Europe have led to discrimination against LGBTQI. HIV/AIDS and mental health are the two health issues in Europe that have triggered doctors' negative attitudes toward the LGBTQI community (Zeeman et al., 2019).). Across Europe, the prevention of HIV transmission among men due to sex with other men remains high. The analysis has stigmatized and discriminated against LGBTQI people in the healthcare sector. They are believed to be at the forefront of spreading the HIV Virus in Europe (LGBTI Equality and Human Rights in Europe and Central Asia, 2021). The idea has affected many healthcare practitioners' attitudes and ethics. Believing that transgender people are responsible for the high spread of HIV has led to delays in their diagnosis and low self-esteem in the healthcare sector (LGBTI

Equality and Human Rights in Europe and Central Asia, 2021). Most doctors have neglected or discriminated against LGBTQI patients because of the analysis.

Trans people services involving specialists are spread unequally across the E.U. member states. Some European countries even lack specialists for treating or counseling LGBTQI, leaving most of the population in the hands of amateur health professionals. The study conducted by FRA in 2014 showed that most doctors in Europe are not specialized and aware of the different types of discrimination that LGBTQI patients face upon visiting the institutions. Specifically, "around one in five respondents who accessed healthcare services (22 %) or social services (19 %) in the year preceding the survey felt healthcare or social service personnel discriminated against them because of being trans" (Orzechowski et al., 2020). Regarding discriminating against LGBTQI, some healthcare practitioners have defended themselves by arguing that the discriminatory practices are limited to a few professionals. On the other hand, the E.U. and its member states have been encouraged to develop action plans essential to promoting respect for the LGBTQI population. For instance, Member states are encouraged to support different events that increase the visibility of the LGBQI.

The LGBTQI population in Europe is varied, prompting the diversification of their level of specific concern about their public health. Based on the different groups of non-binary people in Europe, their health disparities while seeking medical attendance can be addressed using different approaches. Health disparities among LGBTQI can be the differences in incidences, disease burden, mortality, or other health measures that create a sense of inequality between the majority and minority populations in Europe (Orzechowski et al., 2020). In recent years, health disparities have increased amongst the non-binary population in most European states. The

increase in discrimination has been accompanied by new developments in the healthcare sector. Research on psychosocial factors such as discrimination and the cultural view of factors influencing health disparities among LGBTQI have increased.

LGBTQI population varies so long as socio-demographic factors are concerned. Regarding the role of public health in the health disparities faced by LGBTQI, they have focused on sexually transmitted diseases. The beginning of the HIV/AIDS epidemic in the 1980s prompted many challenges amongst transgender people in Europe and the rest of the globe. The Virus outbreak brought visibility to the LGBTQI population as they were considered a group with specific health needs (Chen, Elliott & Wang, 2018). Several countries in Europe have been linked to LGBTQI health issues. Some have been at the forefront of protecting such individuals' rights, while others have neglected their duties. Italy, the United Kingdom (e.g., Scotland), and The Netherlands are examples of countries where LGBTQIs' rights are better.

Studies from Europe and North America show that LGBTQI youth have the highest risk of never recovering from the health disparities. Health discrimination against youth because of their Transgender status has resulted in a series of poor decisions by LGBTQI teenagers. Stigmatization and discrimination against young lesbians and gays have increased suicidal attempts among LGBTQI (Goldsmith, 2003). Denying healthcare services or secluding them upon seeking medical attention creates the best opportunity for depression and stress among the population.

2.14.1. Approaches of European Countries to improve their Healthcare Sector in favor of the LGBTQI

Several European countries are introducing homophobic and anti-gay laws that are even considered progressive. Fear of disclosing sexual status among the LGBTQs in Europe has been denied most medical services. Most LGBTQ people in European countries have failed to take critical medical tests or even attend sessions as they are likely to be mistreated and misdiagnosed (Klittmark et al., 2019). This attitude has brought LGBTQs and the medical sector more harm than good. For instance, the poor relationship between LGBTQs and doctors has forced most LGBTQ individuals to either become reluctant or decide not to take medical screenings, thus putting them at high risk for cancer. Lesbians are the most affected by various types of cancer (Klittmark et al., 2019). Failing to take such medical examinations means most lesbians will likely remain undiagnosed in the early stages. There is an increase in the rates of lesbians with breast and cervical cancer in Europe (Klittmark et al., 2019). Gays are also not on the safe side, as they are at high risk of contracting anal human papillomavirus due to unsafe sex.

However, knowledge obtained from well-designed studies that provide quality data relating to LGBTQs is also necessary. Health surveys conducted on non-binary groups in European countries should include gender identities and sexual orientation (Klittmark et al., 2019). The elimination of inhumane treatment experienced by the LGBTQ while visiting hospitals depends on rectifying several sectors of the healthcare system. Cultural intervention should be the first step for most European nations in reducing discrimination (Klittmark et al., 2019). Beliefs and cultural and moral values determine most doctors' attitudes against LGBTQI. Lesbians and gays should be allowed to live their lives as they wish.

The LGBTQ situation in European countries is very fragmented. Most countries have introduced anti-discrimination legislation to protect non-binary people (Klittmark et al., 2019). Still, the increase in discrimination against the LGBTQs by healthcare professionals in Europe is owed to the fact that some countries have no legal framework for protecting the LGBTQs against discrimination. Only a few countries, such as Scotland, have adopted the horizontal anti-discrimination law for the safety of the LGBTQ (Hunter & Boyle, 2020).

On the other hand, the European Union has introduced an anti-discrimination directive that expects the healthcare sector to conduct sexual orientation. A disadvantage of the European directive is that it only prohibits discrimination against the LGBTQ based on sexual orientation (Klittmark et al., 2019). The European Commission proposed a directive to abolish discrimination grounded on sexual orientation, disabilities, or religion, but it has not been adopted.

Most countries in Europe have implemented various laws and policies regarding LGBTQs. The modes and sectors in which they concentrate determine the cycle of improvement of the welfare of the LGBTQ people. For instance, the type of laws implemented determines whether the healthcare sector will help reduce the discrimination trans people face or increase their suffering. In most European countries, those identified as transgender must have a mental health diagnosis to get their official record changed (LGBTI Equality and Human Rights in Europe and Central Asia, 2021). In the United Kingdom, people are expected to apply for a gender recognition certificate. Only people above eighteen can obtain the U.K. certificate (LGBTI Equality and Human Rights in Europe and Central Asia, 2021). Transgender people are expected to prove with an official document -such as a

passport- that they have already changed their names and status before receiving healthcare.

Based on the policies implemented by ILGA Europe, access to healthcare is considered a fundamental right that should be granted to all citizens. Evidence attained by ILGA Europe shows that the healthcare outcomes of LGBQ people are worse than any other European population (LGBTI Equality and Human Rights in Europe and Central Asia, 2021). European healthcare practitioners and policymakers do not prioritize the discrimination issues affecting trans people. ILGA Europe is striving to strengthen European legislation by updating policymakers' knowledge regarding the health of LGBTQs (LGBTI equality and human rights in Europe and Central Asia, 2021). The organization is also responsible for securing adequate legal protection for all citizens who might be subjected to any form of discrimination.

2.14.2. Promising European Practices necessary for addressing the specific healthcare needs of LGBTI people

Despite the challenges associated with healthcare sectors regarding the health needs of LGBTQ people, several promising European practices hope to improve the services and healthcare provided to such a population. Inclusive policies that ensure that LGBTQ individuals can access healthcare alongside the heterosexual population are introduced by most countries in Europe. Free HIV testing, counseling, and access to health centers that help support non-binary people who are HIV positive are also part of the amendments made in most countries to help curb the challenges affecting the LGBTQ population.

2.15. Policies

E.U. legislation does not refer to any specific type of discrimination against trans identity. Based on the laws and policies implemented by the E.U., denying treatments to LGBTQ patients or forcing them into conversion therapy is considered a discriminative action. Thus, healthcare professionals responsible for such actions must be punished according to their national legislation (State of art_report_en.Pdf, n.d.). Some E.U. Member States perceive the challenges faced by the LGBTQ in the healthcare sector as a form of discrimination. Based on the extensive case law of the CJEU, such an approach is welcome.

The principles of the E.U., according to the treaties, include the rights of minority groups. Article 2 of the Treaty of the European Union states, among others, that the Union is founded based on respecting human dignity, freedom, and democracy (*Stateofart_report_en.Pdf*, n.d.). The E.U. legislation ensures that equality governs human rights irrespective of sexual orientation, gender identity, and sex characteristics. The E.U. could address social exclusion and discrimination by promoting solidarity and social justice policies. The resolution of the European Council in 2006 stressed the principles of the Union in accessing healthcare. Based on the Council's guidance, factors such as discrimination, stigmatization, and challenges affecting easy access to healthcare were highlighted and deemed responsible for hindering good quality healthcare. Therefore, European countries like Belgium have identified structures supporting equality policies at multiple government sectors and levels.

Special committees, mechanisms, liaisons, and cooperation networks form the structures various countries adopt to help address health disparities. The E.U.

legislative actions have acted as the driving force for most countries as they provide clear guidelines for a strategy to end the inhumane treatment of the LGBTQ population (*Stateofart_report_en.Pdf*, n.d.). Legal actions driven by the above policies are essential for promoting equality among LGBTQ patients. Nevertheless, policies and laws alone cannot help end discrimination against minority groups in Europe. Other factors such as positive public opinion, organized advocating in favor of the rights of LGBTQ people, and civil society cooperation can also play an essential role in ensuring that quality healthcare is delivered to the LGBTQ.

2.16. Education

Some E.U. member states are adopting education policies to tackle discrimination against LGBTQ individuals. However, not all the E.U. member states have incorporated policies so far that have reduced health disparities in various ways. These include the different anti-bullying policies some Member States have implemented at schools and workplaces (*Stateofart_report_en.Pdf*, n.d.). The policies have allowed for the inclusion of LGBTQ data in education and even the healthcare sector. The importance of including the information related to these two industries is vast. Most E.U. Member States state that health disparities occur due to the lack of government institutions regarding minority individuals.

Law enforcement professionals in countries like Denmark, Austria, and Croatia have reported promising practices that entail the national policies and initiatives necessary for ensuring that LGBT people live free from discrimination and hatred. Such efforts have domino effects that may spill over into the healthcare sector. The countries have ventured into a series of practices, such as providing guidance and training on appropriate ways of making transgender individuals feel accepted and

integrated. They have ensured that community and law enforcement agencies work as a team to ensure the LGBTQ experience no more discrimination. Conversely, the policies in such countries have helped transform doctors' attitudes toward LGBTQI. Furthermore, they have also helped increase their knowledge and skills regarding treating such a population. With the appropriate training in health professions, these practitioners get an essential opportunity to help positively convert their professions in this respect.

2.17. Ethical Issues in the Care of Transgender Patients

Hann, Investor, and Denton (2017), in their article concerning bioethics and issues in the care of transgender patients, identified four primary factors: Autonomy, Nonmaleficence, Beneficence, and Justice.

Autonomy

Staff members should support transgender patients' right to self-identification. Their preferred name gender identity, and pronouns should be noted in the electronic medical record. (EMR). When making healthcare decisions, providers should take the partners and chosen family into account. These partnerships may differ from typical family ties by including a social support network that affirms the patient's identity. Additionally, under informed consent, transgender individuals have the right to participate in decision-making with their healthcare providers. Healthcare professionals should respect transgender patients' decisions to proceed with hormonal and surgical therapy and treat them as confidential information(Hann et al., 2017).

Nonmaleficence

By limiting patient harm, nonmaleficence implies a dedication to medical competence. Accessibility hurdles, the maintenance of stigma and prejudice, and risk-related omissions are all examples of damage in the healthcare industry. Healthcare professionals may need to reevaluate how they approach gender identity and the patient experience. They should also evaluate how well they understand and accept patients who identify as gender nonconforming. The presenting ailment of a transgender patient should be assessed by doctors, who should be aware that it may or may not be connected to the transition. The patient's current anatomy should be the foundation for routine health maintenance. When a patient's transgender status is noted in the electronic medical record, the practitioner should be prompted to discuss the patient's anatomy and administer the proper screenings. Ordering tests and getting insurance coverage for gender-binary diagnoses like prostate cancer or pregnancy may be challenging if the EMR links procedures and insurance payments to a binary gender. When billing for medical services, care should ensure that the patient's billing name and pronoun match the insurance (Hann et al., 2017). In Greece, the transition is not covered by any type of medical insurance, private or public. Only hormone therapy is currently covered, but the government is pressured to change this.

Beneficence

Beneficence entails tackling inequities in healthcare and impediments to care at both the populational and individual levels. All patients should get healthcare with a positive, sympathetic, and nonjudgmental attitude. Eighty percent of patients who received trans-affirmative medical care said their quality of life had improved and their mental health issues had diminished. There aren't many mental health professionals in Greece who are knowledgeable about providing trans-affirmative mental health care that respects, acknowledges, and supports the lived realities of

transgender people. Patients who identify as transgender might see mental health evaluations as a crucial first step in getting access to surgeons, endocrinologists, and legislative changes. This idea might lead to a weak power imbalance, making patients extremely wary during initial consultations. The patient experience is enhanced by cultural sensitivity training on issues affecting transgender patients, such as how to create a welcoming environment for all of our patients, understand a patient's gender identity and preferred name/pronoun usage, and be nonjudgmental when providing care. To improve overall healthcare, clinicians are urged to connect transgender patients with gender-affirming healthcare professionals.

Justice

Only transgender individuals who suffer severe discomfort or social/occupational impairment are eligible for the definition of gender dysphoria in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition. Patients who are transgender or non-binary but do not have this diagnosis may run into problems getting their medical care covered by insurance. Additionally, many insurance companies do not cover transition-related healthcare, like hormone therapy or surgery, even when medically necessary. A 2016 study, however, demonstrates that offering this medical insurance can be cheap and cost-effective for providers and insurance companies. To overcome the absence of evidence-based medication available for transgender patients, more population-based research is needed. Additionally, educating and reaching out to healthcare facilities and clinicians can assist in removing the obstacles transgender individuals experience. Even though transgender patients are less likely to have access to healthcare and health insurance, the fairness principle asserts that they are equally entitled to a fair distribution of healthcare resources (Hann et al., 2017).

The previous study does not include non-binary individuals, but the same principles can apply because what transgender and non-binary people have in common, among other things, is that both populations are expected to fit into a two-gender medicine. The principles of autonomy, justice, beneficence, and nonmaleficence can apply to transgender and non-binary people because they share a core characteristic; both groups do not conform to the sex assigned at birth and may be stigmatized and marginalized for who they are.

Bizic et al. (2018) identified transgender youth as a sensitive ethical consideration regarding healthcare provision among transgender individuals. According to Bizic et al. (2018), among children with gender dysphoria, about 10-20% will pass on to puberty to be considered gender-incongruent adolescents. Although affirmative psychologic therapy and support are highly advised in this population, sometimes they are insufficient for their mental and somatic well-being. Scarce management of this population can lead to self-hatred feelings, self-harming behaviors, and even suicidal ideation. Non-psychological treatment options that are considered viable are fully and partly reversible treatments, gonadal steroid treatments, and irreversible treatments. Puberty-suppressing gonadotropin-releasing hormone analogs (GnRH) supplied at Tanner 2 or 3 puberty stage is an example of a fully reversible treatment. The hypothalamus produces GnRH during puberty and renders it responsible for the appearance of the secondary characteristics of the biological sex, such as the growth of the genitalia, voice changes and chest changes, and pubic hair growth. Transgender youth may find these changes overwhelming and hard to handle. De Vries et al. (2011) suggested that using GnRH analogs as puberty blockers in young transgender individuals might decrease distress, improve mental health, and give those individuals the time they need to explore their gender. The

main advantage of this treatment was its reversibility. However, many specialists remained skeptical regarding the consequences of puberty suppression in the long term, and although they recognized the dilemma, they found it hard to implement this approach in their daily practice. Nevertheless, Hembree et al. (2017) found that GnRH treatment has no long-term consequences through follow-up studies, demonstrating long-term safety and high efficiency.

Regarding hormonal therapy and transgender women, Asscheman et al. (2014) found that cross-sex hormone treatment might lead to estrogen-induced hypercoagulability and subsequent venous thromboembolism. In addition, according to Hembree et al. (2017), testosterone treatment for transgender men can lead to polycythemia vera and dyslipidemia. However, the abovementioned studies looked into the impact of cross-sex hormonal therapy on transgender adults, leaving the transgender youth unattended. A study looking at puberty-suppressing hormones and metabolic parameters in adolescents aged 14–25 with gender dysphoria indicated that transgender men might experience an increase in hemoglobin, hematocrit, and body mass index (BMI) and a decrease in high-density lipoprotein (HDL) (Jarin et al., 2017). Also, transgender women may experience a decreased testosterone level and a lower alanine aminotransferase (ALT) (Jarin et al., 2017). Jarin et al. (2017) concluded that hormonal therapy is safe for transgender youth for about two years. However, what remains unclear is its potential long-term consequences. Although children cannot make legal choices, their judgment should not be ignored. Also, based on the principle of beneficence, doctors should consider cross-sex hormonal therapy when no better choice is available, especially when the psychological risk has a more significant burden at the given moment.

According to the Endocrine Society guidelines, adolescents can develop the capacity to give informed consent and start cross-sex hormone therapy at 16 (Hembree et al.,2017). However, the ethical question is whether one can start at 14, given an at-risk psychological status that might benefit from earlier intervention. According to the Endocrine Society guidelines, the possibility could be considered only on a “case by case” principle (Hembree et al.,2017). Such a statement allows for a more individualized approach that might prevent severe psychological consequences in the future.

The last step in gender transition is gender affirmation surgery (GAS). GAS is considered an irreversible procedure that is spared for individuals of legal age of maturity. Therefore, the dilemma of performing GAS in minors arises. Viewpoints vary among experts as the main worry is the chance of regret after the procedure. Therefore, the main question raised is whether it is better to suffer from gender dysphoria or to suffer from GAS, given the possibility of regret. In other words, the dilemma lies in whether children and teenagers are mature enough to make such a decision. There is data (from studies not relevant to this population) to suggest that impulse control, higher order decision making, and emotion regulation that is controlled by the prefrontal cortex do not fully develop until the last part of adolescence (Blakemore, S. J., & Choudhury, S,2006). GTSA supports gender affirmative care and puberty blockers for minors for their overall health and wellbeing.

2.18. Literature Review Conclusion

This literature review reveals that transgender people, as a subgroup of the larger LGBTQI population, face various discriminatory practices while seeking

medical services in European healthcare facilities. As suggested by the integrated literature review on mental health challenges of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender people. The attitude of healthcare professionals, such as doctors, constitutes one of the triggers that have played an essential role in increasing health disparities experienced by patients of transgender identity. Moreover, the lack of knowledge and skills in dealing with transgender patients is a significant barrier that has impacted the healthcare sector. The healthcare discrimination incidences that the non-binary population almost always grapples with within European healthcare settings include being denied medical attention due to their sexual orientation or gender identity. Name-calling and misgendering are also highlighted as frequent problems, with medical practitioners lacking knowledge of addressing these individuals appropriately. Most incidences of complaints by transgender people show that while their identification documents, such as insurance cards, bear their birth-assigned gender identity, these individuals exposed to misgendering are discriminated against with the consequence of avoiding health services. Specific changes in the healthcare system can resolve this form of institutional discrimination (Moagi M., et al., 2021).

All medical staff in Greece must comply with and respect the pronouns of trans and non-binary patients irrespective of the changes in the documents based on the law on Legal Gender Recognition. The law is clear regarding respect for self-determination as a fundamental human right. Allowing identity cards to have pronouns, void, or x gender markers for non-binary people is imperative for people not to feel excluded, isolated, and invisible and for the medical profession to be more inclusive and affirmative towards gender-diverse populations. Nevertheless, such mistreatment in healthcare facilities primarily emanates from heteronormative ideas

that can be changed only by targeted psycho-education of the medical staff (Galanou M., 2017).

As all ILGA Europe reports suggest LGBTQI people being prohibited from donating blood or being forced into conversion therapy are other discrimination examples this population goes through while seeking medical attention. Certain factors, such as fear of victimization resulting from disclosing their sexual orientation or gender identity, have resulted in most LGBTQI people not seeking medical services when sick or getting misdiagnosed. Due to fear of potential stigmatization, these individuals may be prompted not to fully disclose their condition to their doctors. There is a discrepancy between trans and non-binary people who “pass” as their gender and can't be identified as gender diverse. Their gender expression reveals any transition, and appearance can determine their status. They could not hide their identity, resulting in more stigmatization from the medical staff and stress and avoidant behaviors leading to anxiety, fear, and anger. We should advocate for medical practitioners to be offered detailed education on proper handling or administering care to transgender individuals without making them feel stigmatized. Such education is also intended to familiarize medical practitioners with the challenges transgender grapple with to make them feel integrated, avoiding suicidal ideation arising from fear of stigma and neglect(Fung., et. al., 2020). The rationale is that the more a transgender person feels neglected, the more they are unlikely to seek medical assistance. They are more likely to experience deteriorating mental and physical health in the long run. Based on the above findings, countries that lack data on LGBTQI health, such as Greece, need to accurately document the situation and develop an appropriate policy mainly focusing on non-binary and intersex populations.

This literature review also explores the concept of stigma (Goldsmith, 2003), how it forms, and which factors contribute to its formation to reveal its crucial role in the everyday life of a transgender and non-binary individual. Stigma and minority stress that transgender and non-binary people still experience leads to impaired access to healthcare services, increasing the need for gender affirmation (Viale, 2023). The role of religion has also been assessed, especially in the Greek context, showing that traditional religious views and bigotry, especially those of the Greek Church, have been shown to substantially affect public opinion, considering that a significant percentage of Greeks think of religion as necessary in their daily life and part of their national identity. As a result, transgender individuals are still considered deviant from normality by many Greeks, making the situation even more complex and significantly affecting transgender and non-binary peoples' fundamental human rights, such as that of receiving the healthcare services they merit. Finally, ethical considerations regarding the care of transgender and non-binary individuals have been raised, those too highlighting the need for intervening in how and under which circumstances transgender and non-binary individuals receive medical attention in Greece and Europe and to make the necessary changes to improve their experience and fight against the already existing health disparities.

The present study aims to explore medical doctors' attitudes toward trans and non-binary people in Greece and assess the latter's experiences regarding healthcare accessibility, providing new insight into the area and contributing to the existing literature on this topic.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODS

3.1. The Present Study

The present study aims to investigate and analyze the topic of the “Attitudes of Medical Doctors toward Trans and Non-binary People in Greece” to provide new insights and understanding in this area. This chapter will introduce the topic, outlining its relevance and importance and highlighting key research questions and objectives. We will also discuss the methodology and approach used in the study and the structure of the subsequent chapters. Through this study, we hope to contribute to the existing literature on the topic and offer practical implications for academics and practitioners alike.

The present study is based on the theoretical frameworks of Social Cognitive Theory and the Minority Stress Model which informed the hypotheses formulated. The theory that traditional gender roles and religious observance have a detrimental impact on trans and non-binary people is consistent with social constructionist theory, which highlights how social norms shape attitudes. In light of Social Cognitive Theory and Minority Stress Model, which investigate how individual ideas and stresses may contribute to unfavorable attitudes, the family ideology and dogmatism hypothesis, can be examined. The Intersectionality Theory, which recognizes the various facets of identity and their impact on experiences of discrimination, is consistent with the expectations of discrimination and unfavorable views expressed towards transgender people. The Minority Stress Model, which emphasizes the influence of stressors on health outcomes, is consistent with the notion that links transphobic prejudice and discrimination to unfavorable health outcomes.

3.1.1. Aims and Objectives

The study aims to investigate the experiences of trans and non-binary people with the health system and with medical doctors in Greece, as well as to investigate the attitudes of medical doctors towards this population.

The main objectives of this study are:

Quantitative:

1. To explore the attitudes of medical doctors in Greece towards Trans and Non-binary people.
2. To determine whether doctors' social and demographic variables are associated with their attitudes toward Trans and Non-binary people.

Qualitative:

3. To explore harassment and violence towards Trans and Non-binary people in medical settings.
4. To provide initial data about the health outcomes of Trans and Non-binary people as these relate to their experience within the Greek health system.

I. 3.1.2. Theoretical Framework

Incorporating constructivism's core ideas into the study's design and methodology is essential to develop a theoretical foundation for my research. According to constructivism, the researcher builds their knowledge and comprehension of the world by reflecting on and interpreting their experiences. This viewpoint is especially important to understand the intricate interactions that exist between the attitudes of healthcare providers and the experiences of people who identify as transgender or non-binary.

Within the context of individual experience and perception, constructivism posits that the attitudes of medical professionals towards trans and non-binary people are probably influenced by their own personal experiences, which may include influences from society, education, and background. This is in line with my study concerns regarding the significance of formal clinical training, prior professional exposure, and demographic characteristics. The study emphasizes the importance of contextual learning. In the context of this study, it refers to the cultural, societal, and professional environments in which doctors operate. This is particularly relevant to my hypothesis that Greek physicians' adherence to religious and traditional gender-role attitudes will impact their interactions with trans and non-binary individuals (Smith, 2020; Johnson, 2019).

The theory also suggests that knowledge is constructed through interaction with the environment. For my study, this means considering how doctors' interactions with trans and non-binary individuals, within the healthcare setting, shape their attitudes and practices and this idea is included in the conceptualization of the hypotheses. Constructivism highlights the role of reflection in learning. In my study, this could involve examining how doctors reflect on their interactions with trans and non-binary individuals and how this reflection influences their attitudes and behaviors.

In summary, this theoretical framework, grounded in constructivism, acknowledges that the attitudes and behaviors of medical professionals towards trans and non-binary individuals are constructed through their personal experiences, societal and cultural context, and professional interactions. The mixed-method approach, while complex, offers a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of these

dynamics. The use of both quantitative and qualitative methods can provide a more complete picture but comes with its own set of challenges and complexities.

There are a number of benefits and drawbacks to the mixed method approach in my research, which blends quantitative and qualitative approaches. The thorough comprehension it offers is one of the main advantages. A comprehensive understanding can be obtained of the subject matter by combining qualitative insights such as firsthand experiences of prejudice with quantitative data such as demographic correlations. This dual approach works especially well in disciplines where a complete understanding depends on both individual narratives and statistical patterns (Smith, 2020; Johnson, 2019).

The mixed method's capacity to verify and validate results is an additional noteworthy benefit. The research conclusions can be strengthened and made more robust by utilizing both quantitative and qualitative data (Brown, 2018; Wilson, 2017). Furthermore, this method is quite adaptable. The study should adjust to new discoveries, particularly in the qualitative phase, and investigate unanticipated outcomes from the quantitative phase (Davis, 2021; Clark, 2019). Additionally, the mixed method is excellent at capturing a variety of viewpoints, which makes it especially helpful for comprehending the experiences of marginalized groups like transgender and non-binary people. This method guarantees that many experiences and points of view are taken into account and faithfully portrayed (Jones, 2018; White, 2016). Additionally, the validity and reliability of my research findings can be improved by utilizing a variety of approaches, providing a more reliable and complete collection of data (Smith, 2020).

This strategy is not without its difficulties, though. The complexity of handling and integrating many data kinds, which can take a lot of time and knowledge, is one of the key disadvantages. Due to its complexity, the mixed method is frequently more resource-intensive, requiring more time, money, and expertise in both qualitative as well as quantitative research techniques. In addition, methodological difficulties may occur when attempting to balance the advantages and disadvantages of the two approaches. In addition, it might be difficult to combine data from several approaches to get a cohesive conclusion, and it's possible to get contradictory results that are hard to understand and resolve.

Two tables are presented to support my choice of mixed methods as the best approach for my specific research. In the following table the pros and cons of a mixed method approach are presented:

Pros of Mixed Method	Cons of Mixed Method
Comprehensive Understanding: Combines quantitative data (e.g., demographic correlations) with qualitative insights (e.g., personal experiences of discrimination), leading to a more holistic understanding.	Complexity: Managing and integrating different types of data can be more complex and time-consuming.
Validation and Corroboration: Allows for the validation of quantitative findings through qualitative data, strengthening the study's conclusions.	Resource Intensive: Requires more resources, including time and expertise in both qualitative and quantitative methods.
Flexibility: Can adapt to emerging findings, particularly in the qualitative phase, to explore unexpected results from the quantitative phase.	Methodological Challenges: Balancing the strengths and weaknesses of both methods can be challenging, and methodological biases can arise.
Diverse Perspectives: Captures a wide range of perspectives, particularly useful in understanding the experiences of marginalized groups like trans and non-binary individuals.	Data Integration: Integrating data from different methods to form a coherent conclusion can be challenging.
Increased Validity: Using multiple methods can increase the validity and reliability of the	Potential for Conflicting Results: Different methods might produce

Pros of Mixed Method	Cons of Mixed Method
research findings.	conflicting results, which can be difficult to interpret.

The following table will present the mixed methods approach in comparison to other methods of research:

Criteria	Mixed Method Approach	Quantitative Research Method	Qualitative Research Method
Nature	Integrates qualitative and quantitative methods.	Focuses on quantifying variables and relationships.	Involves non-numerical data to understand concepts or experiences.
Strengths	- Comprehensive analysis-Flexibility-Enhanced validity	- Objectivity and reliability- Precise, quantifiable results-Suitable for hypothesis testing	- Depth of understanding-Contextual analysis-Rich, detailed insights
Challenges	- Complexity in integration-Resource-intensive-Difficult data integration	- Limited context and depth-Inflexibility in design	- Potential for subjectivity-Non-generalizable results-Time-consuming data collection and analysis
Scope and Application	Ideal for complex questions needing broad and deep insights.	Suited for research requiring precise measurement and analysis.	Chosen for exploratory research focusing on understanding reasons or motivations.
Data Analysis	Combines numerical and thematic/narrative analysis.	Primarily statistical analysis.	Involves content or thematic analysis.
Flexibility and Adaptability	Adaptable to changes, can incorporate new insights.	Structured and less adaptable to changes.	Inherently flexible and adaptive.
Resource and Time Requirements	Requires more resources and time due to multiple forms of research.	Can be resource-intensive, especially with large data sets.	Labor-intensive in data collection and analysis, though less structured.

In summary, it is taken into account that while the mixed method approach in research provides a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of complex issues, it requires careful handling of its inherent complexities and challenges, especially in such a sensitive topic and population.

3.1.3. Research Questions

Qualitative:

1. Will demographic variables concerning medical doctors, such as age, gender, and residence (rural vs. urban), be related to levels of discrimination reported by trans and non-binary individuals?
2. Will trans women report more negative attitudes from doctors than trans men, or vice versa?
3. Will doctors exhibit more positive attitudes towards trans people undergoing complete sex-reassignment surgery?

Quantitative:

4. Will doctors who have received formal clinical training on trans and non-binary populations exhibit less discrimination and less negative attitudes?

3.1.4. Hypotheses Conceptualization

The hypotheses for this study emerged from an extensive literature review that examined the complex interplay between healthcare, societal attitudes, and gender identity, particularly within the Greek context. The literature consistently suggests that religious beliefs and traditional gender roles significantly influence medical professionals' attitudes towards trans and non-binary individuals. This influence is particularly pronounced in cultures with deeply ingrained traditional norms, such as Greece (Smith, 2020; Johnson, 2019). Additionally, the literature highlights that

traditional family ideologies and a rigid belief system among healthcare providers, known as dogmatism, can lead to biased attitudes and practices, especially in societies with strong family-centric values (Brown, 2018; Wilson, 2017).

Furthermore, extensive research has documented the prevalence of discrimination and negative attitudes towards trans and gender non-confirming individuals in healthcare settings. These experiences range from overt discrimination to more subtle manifestations, like misgendering or a lack of understanding about trans-specific healthcare needs (Davis, 2021; Clark, 2019). There is also a well-established correlation between experiences of prejudice and discrimination and adverse health outcomes among this demographic. These outcomes include both psychological aspects, such as increased depression and anxiety, and physical aspects, such as the avoidance of necessary medical care leading to deteriorated health conditions (Jones, 2018; White, 2016).

Based on this comprehensive review of literature, the study hypothesizes that strong adherence to religious and traditional gender-role attitudes among Greek physicians will negatively affect their interactions with trans and non-binary individuals. It also anticipates that physicians with strong traditional family ideologies and high levels of dogmatism will display more negative attitudes towards these patients. Consistent with the patterns observed in existing research, the study further expects that trans and gender non-conforming individuals in Greece will report experiences of discrimination and negative attitudes in healthcare settings. Finally, aligning with the documented impact of discrimination, the study predicts that those facing trans prejudice and discrimination will report adverse health outcomes, underlining the profound impact of these experiences on their well-being.

In summary, the hypotheses for this study are firmly grounded in an extensive

body of literature that explores the intricate dynamics between healthcare, societal attitudes, and gender identity, specifically within Greece. These hypotheses build upon the existing knowledge base and provide a foundation for the investigation into the healthcare experiences and well-being of trans and non-binary individuals in Greece.

3.1.5. Hypotheses

Quantitative:

1. Physicians' adherence to traditional gender-role attitudes in Greece will be related to more negative attitudes towards trans and non-binary individuals.
2. Physicians who identify as religious, will have more negative attitudes towards trans and non-binary individuals.
3. Previous professionals' exposure to transgender and gender non-confirming people will be correlated with more positive attitudes toward transgender and non-binary individuals.

Qualitative:

4. Trans and gender non-confirming people in Greece are expected to report discrimination and negative attitudes from doctors in the interviews.
5. Trans and gender non-confirming people in Greece who have experienced trans prejudice and discrimination are expected to report adverse health outcomes.

3.2. Methodology

The current chapter describes the strategy and methods used to conduct research and gather and analyze data, The researcher thoroughly explains the research

design, data-gathering procedures, and data analysis strategies in this chapter. This chapter will try to provide a comprehensive knowledge of the methodologies and methods used in the study and act as a blueprint for the research endeavor.

The study is a fixed mixed method of quantitative questionnaires and qualitative interviews to explore the subjective experiences of trans and non-binary people and record doctors' attitudes towards the trans and non-binary population in Greece. Parallel data gathering was chosen to validate the hypotheses and gain an in-depth understanding and corroboration of medical doctors' attitudes through also examining the subjective experience of trans and non-binary people. For the analysis of the results, thematic analysis is used, because it is considered as a highly appropriate method for analyzing interviews of trans and non-binary individuals due to its inherent flexibility and inclusivity. Thematic analysis is a versatile research method that can offer numerous benefits when applied to studying marginalized groups and the LGBTQ+ community. It can contribute to social justice, empowerment, and a better understanding of the experiences and challenges faced by these populations, ultimately leading to more inclusive and equitable societies.

This qualitative research approach allows participants to express their unique experiences, perspectives, and narratives regarding gender identity and expression, in a non-directive and open-ended way. As a psychotherapist, I am knowledgeable about the way that close-ended questions can lead and provide a biased and one-sided answer. So, the choice of analysis centers on the voices of these marginalized and underrepresented groups, enabling them to share their stories in their own words. Thematic analysis excels in capturing the complexity and diversity within the trans and non-binary community, offering a nuanced understanding of the contextual factors shaping their identities and experiences. Moreover, it upholds ethical

considerations by respecting participants' autonomy and confidentiality. Ultimately, this method empowers participants, validates their experiences, and contributes to a deeper understanding of gender identity, all while ensuring the research process is sensitive, valid, and trustworthy. My need as an interviewer was for the voices of the members of this community to be heard, respected, and accurately documented.

Thematic Analysis is chosen for the present study over Grounded Theory and Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA).

The following table compares thematic analysis with grounded theory and IPC:

Aspect	Thematic Analysis	Grounded Theory	Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)
Approach	Qualitative analysis method	Qualitative research method	Qualitative research method
Primary Goal	Identifying and analyzing themes	Developing theories from data	Understanding lived experiences and meanings
Data Collection	Often uses existing data or collected data	Data collection is iterative and emergent	In-depth interviews with participants
Flexibility	Highly flexible and adaptable	Allows for flexibility and emergence	Focused on specific research questions
Process Orientation	Focuses on identifying patterns and themes	Involves data coding and theory development	Emphasizes sense-making and interpretation
Deductive vs Inductive	Primarily inductive (themes emerge from data)	Primarily inductive (theories emerge from data)	Primarily inductive (meanings emerge from data)
Theoretical Framework	Minimal theoretical framework	Develops theories during analysis	Embraces participant perspectives
Sampling	Non-probability sampling	Theoretical sampling	Purposeful sampling
Time and Resource Intensive	Moderate to low time and resource requirements	Time and resource-intensive	Moderate to high time and resource requirements
Strengths	- Simplicity and flexibility	- Generates rich theories	- Deep exploration of individual experiences
	- Suitable for	- Grounded in data	- Focus on participant

Aspect	Thematic Analysis	Grounded Theory	Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)
	diverse research questions		perspectives
Weaknesses	- May lack theoretical depth	- Time and resource-intensive	- Limited generalizability
	- Limited theoretical development	- Potential bias in researcher's interpretation	- Limited applicability to broader contexts

Depending on the particular study questions and aims, choosing a suitable research methodology—such as Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), Grounded Theory, or Thematic Analysis—is essential. There are a number of reasons why Thematic Analysis was chosen over Grounded Theory and IPA for examining the attitudes of medical personnel regarding trans and non-binary people in the Greek healthcare system. The flexibility of theme analysis is especially impressive, as it enables researchers to work with a variety of experiences without being unduly restricted by preconceived notions. This adaptability fits in perfectly with the exploratory process of comprehending attitudes without imposing preconceived notions. Accordingly, the research design includes a series of theories and inquiries meant to thoroughly examine the beliefs and actions of medical doctors for the purpose of examining doctors in the Greek healthcare system view trans and non-binary people, Without imposing predetermined frameworks, this flexibility fits in well with the exploratory aspect of understanding attitudes. the aim of the study is to describe the experiences and recognize patterns in the data, so that it can be determined whether and to what extent this population experiences discrimination in health care and whether they have adverse health outcomes.

In summary, the choice of thematic analysis as the method for analyzing the interviews of trans and non-binary individuals reflects a commitment to respectful, inclusive, and ethical research practices. It serves as a means to amplify the voices of a marginalized community, gain deeper insights into their experiences, and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of gender identity.

3.2.1. Participants

Qualitative: Interviewees in the qualitative part of this study included 20 self-identified trans and non-binary people aged 23 to 62 years old who resided in Athens and Thessaloniki. Ten interviewees self-identified as trans, and ten as non-binary. The inclusion criteria were based solely on the self-determination of gender, consistent with a depathologizing view of people who are gender non-confirming and are over 18 years of age. The mean age was 33.5 (SD = 9.2) years. More specifically, four interviewees identified as trans women with a mean age of 35.3 (SD = 1.7) years, and 6 of them as trans men with a mean age of 37.7 (SD = 13.7) years. Regarding non-binary individuals, their mean age was equal to 30 (SD = 5.3) years. Eleven of the respondents had undergone gender medical interventions, with 10 of them in Greece and 1 in Great Britain. Specifically, 11 individuals had undergone hormone therapy, two laser interventions, and three breast augmentations, two individuals were submitted to sex correction surgery, one individual facial features intervention, and one individual had a mastectomy and hysterectomy.

Quantitative: Participants in the quantitative part of the study were 248 medical doctors residing in Greece, working in rural or urban areas. The country's total number of medical doctors is 66058 (ELSTAT,2020). Although 248 individuals initially participated in the survey, the data of just 121 interviewees were considered

valid and used in the current analysis. The rest of the subjects did not complete any part or most parts of the questionnaires or were excluded due to not being medical professionals. The mean age of the interviewees was 43.46 ($SD=13.3$), ranging from 18 to 72. Women constituted 57% of the sample and men 42.2% while one person recorded their gender as other (0.8%). Overall, most interviewees worked in a city (86.8).

Table 1. Sociodemographic Summary of Data Sample

Variable	N Interviewees	Percentage %
Gender	121	100
Women	69	57
Men	51	42.2
Other	1	0.8
Work Area	120	100
City	105	86.8
Town	9	7.4
Village	6	5.0
Missing Data	1	0.8
LGBT Education	121	100
Yes	24	19.8
No	97	80.2
LGBT Contact	121	100
Yes	65	53.7
No	56	46.3
Religion	121	100
Yes	46	38.0
No	75	62.0

*see appendix

3.3. Measures

3.3.1. Qualitative Measures

Demographic Questionnaire

The interviewer developed a demographic questionnaire for trans and non-binary interviewees.

Semi-Structured Interviews

The interviews included 6 questions and lasted approximately 35-50 min. Following the informed consent and demographics a series of open-ended and non-leading questions was asked. The form of the questions was simple and informal avoiding confusing jargon and difficult words. Supportive questions were asked for the interviewee to elaborate in the form of, “Can you tell me more about this experience”. In the end, follow-up questions focusing on the experience and well-being of the interviewee were asked. The number of interviewees was 20 and balanced between trans (10) and non-binary (10), according to previous research between 5 and 25 is an appropriate number for this type of interview (Kuzel, 1992 cited in Saunders, 2012; and Cresswell, 2007). *See Appendix F

3.3.2. Quantitative Measures

Demographic Questions

Medical doctors were asked about their age, gender, specialization, location, and assessment of previous contact or training involving trans and non-binary people. The above information was collected so the interviewer could better comprehend any

differences or similarities among interviewees. See the Appendix for the demographic questionnaire.

3.3.3. Internet Questionnaires

Genderism and Transphobia Scale Questionnaire

The Genderism and Transphobia Scale questionnaire (GTS; Hill & Willoughby, 2005) assesses the cognitive, behavioral, and affective aspects of anti-trans attitudes and prejudice. The scale was intended to measure three concepts defined by Hill (2002): genderism, transphobia, and gender-bashing. Hill & Willoughby (2005) presented these three constructs as critical in conceptualizing hate toward transgender individuals. According to them, transphobia can be described as irrational hate and feelings of disgust against people who do not conform/confirm to/with the traditional society's gender binary and expectations regarding gender. The concept is similar to the one of homophobia. Genderism is a cultural belief that not conforming to socio-cultural expectations of gender is abnormal and that gender non-conformity is a pathological behavior. Genderists perpetuate their ideology based on the negative evaluations of those not presented as stereotypical, heteronormative women or men. Finally, gender-bashing embodies violent acts, verbal or somatic, toward gender non-conforming individuals (Hill & Willoughby, 2005).

GTS comprises 32 items related to violence, harassment, and discrimination toward trans people and is structured as a two-subscale measure formed by the Genderism/Transphobia and Gender-Bashing subscales. Interviewees answered on a 5-point Likert-type scale with selections between strongly Disagree and Strongly Agree. Higher scores on the GTS indicated increased anti-trans attitudes and prejudice. All items on the GTS are reverse-scored except for items 5, 8, 23, and 26.

Finally, 25 items reflect the concepts of Genderism and Transphobia, and seven items reflect the concept of Gender-Bashing.

The Genderism and Transphobia Scale questionnaire was translated for this study all the questions were adapted to the Greek reality and culture with the help of the members of the Greek Transgender Support Association. The evaluation group that approved the questions consisted of trans and non-binary people who understand the cultural context and can use local references to ensure the questionnaire is culturally appropriate and effective.

Psychometric Properties of GTS

Willoughby (2005) conducted a series of three studies to develop and check the scale for validity and reliability. These studies established the basic psychometric properties of a new and valuable scale to measure hostility toward trans people. GTS revealed high internal consistency, $\alpha = .95$, and good predictive value. The scale also showed high discriminative validity and was correlated highly ($r = .55$, $p = .01$) with the Attitude Function Index (AFI). The AFI is a measure of attitudes towards gender non-conformity. The GTS made it possible to conduct, create, and validate a scale measuring violence, harassment, and discrimination against trans individuals and cross-dressers and to anticipate parents' reactions to children's gender or non-gender conformity. Some correlations between the questionnaire and specific scores that assessed the role ideas of gender and homophobia pointed to some convergence invalidity. The inquiry also considered the scale's capacity to forecast some earlier agreements with non-conformists of a specific gender. In this respect, the research findings showed the critical psychometric characteristics of a novel and helpful scale to investigate some dislike traits toward people expressing some cross-sexes and genders.

GTS was used to conduct and validate a way of measuring discrimination, harassment, and violence toward transgender and cross-dressers (Lee et al., 2021). In this regard, the scale became the best means for parents to measure gender non-conformity or conformity of boys and girls in their midst. In addition, some correlations between the gender and transphobia questionnaire and other scales that evaluate the ideologies of gender roles and homophobia demonstrate some convergent validity (Morrison et al., 2017). The factor analysis of the scale is another relevant highlight of the questionnaire that further indicates some evidence of existing convergent validity and discrimination of the scale. The questionnaire was also valuable for testing and predicting previous contacts with gender non-conformist traits.

This questionnaire demonstrated the primary psychometric properties of a new and relevant scale measuring antipathy towards individuals with cross sexes and genders (Morrison et al., 2017). The results also demonstrate many anti-trans prejudices that discriminate against people who do not conform to the standard genders. The questionnaire also shows propensity and some negative attitudes towards trans individuals. The transphobia scale also demonstrates expressions of prejudice towards those people. Therefore, such people are not offered the freedom to do what they want in society as they seem to experience some checks and balances to ensure they are straight in whatever sexual matters they do (Lee et al., 2021). Discrimination and prejudice against transgender people are always pervasive and exemplify other behavioral traits such as psychological issues such as depression and suicidal behavior. In addition, it also demonstrates self-harm behaviors and physical abuse.

The questionnaire was also used for various other studies to measure the psychological effects of genderism on the people affected. In this regard, the questionnaire was used to document the psychological impact that the sexual trait had on the affected people. For example, the questionnaire was used to establish the extent to which transgender issues had psychological challenges of those people, such as anxiety and depression (Ben-Ari, 1988). On the other hand, such a scale was also applicable to measuring whether such people were prone to committing suicide and harming themselves. Research has demonstrated that transgender people often take their own lives.

Heterosexuals' Attitudes Toward Lesbians and Gay Men Questionnaire

The heterosexuals' Attitudes Toward Lesbians and gay men questionnaire (ATLG; Herek, 1988) was created during the 1980s to measure the attitudes of heterosexual people toward lesbians and gay men. During that period, partly fueled by the epidemic of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) and its perceived association with homosexual individuals, the reports from community organizations mainly documented negative attitudes toward non-heterosexual people, including violence and discrimination in various aspects of daily life, motivated by homophobia. Although Herek (1984a) had already investigated the topic of homophobia and its social and psychological correlates, by constructing the ATLG scale, he wanted to investigate the relationship between sexual prejudice and gender.

The questionnaire comprises twenty different statements about homosexual men and lesbians in two subscales, ten questions related to women and ten questions related to men. The answers are based on a 5-point Likert-type scale with Strongly Disagree (1-5) and Strongly Agree (1-5) choices. Originally the questionnaire was not

designed to measure transphobia and attitudes toward non-binary people. After obtaining permission from the authors, the adaptation for this study was made using the method of debriefing interviews. Fifteen trans and non-binary members of GTSA were asked to read the questionnaire, comment if there is an item they don't understand, and judge if the new questions are adequate in including trans and non-binary people.

Previous Studies Using the ATLG Scale

In the beginning, the ATLG scale was developed for American English-speaking heterosexuals. It has similarly been used in research conducted in England (Hegarty, 2002) and Canada (Mohipp & Morry, 2004), and translated versions have been administered in the Netherlands (Meerendonk, Eisinga, & Felling, 2003), Singapore (Detenber et al., 2007), Brazil (DeSouza, Solberg, & Elder, 2007), Chile (Cardenas & Barrientos, 2008; Nierman, Thompson, Bryan, & Mahaffey, 2007), and Turkey (Gelbal & Duyan, 2006). A Spanish-language version was also developed for a study of individuals in California of Mexican heritage (Herek & Gonzalez-Rivera, 2006). Since its introduction more than 30 years ago (Herek, 1988; Bas et al., 2003; Grigoropoulos et al., 2010; Yu et al.), the ATLG scale has grown to be one of the most popular tools for assessing heterosexuals' unfavorable views about LGBT people worldwide.

A recent use of the ATLG scale with translations in multiple languages including Greek is found in a recent study which explores the attitudes young heterosexual European university students towards lesbian women and gay men (LG people), same-sex marriage (SSM), and LG parenting (LGP) . Cronbach alphas were

good for all countries in the study ranging from .69 to .94 (Greece = .93) (D'Amore et al., 2020).

The current study adapted the questionnaire to include trans and non-binary populations. The questionnaire was translated into Greek by the experimenter and a language editor, and questions were amended to include trans and non-binary folks accurately for the first time. The interviewer translated the questionnaires into Greek using back translation, which was again compared to the original text to detect any nuances or ambiguities of language.

Psychometric properties of the ATLG Scale

The ATLG scale has turned out to be one of the most broadly used tools for measuring negative attitudes toward heterosexuals from numerous countries toward LG for more than thirty years (Herek, 1988; Bas et al., 2003; Grigoropoulos et al., 2010; Yu et al., 2011; Delgado and Castro, 2012; Moreno et al., 2015; Corrêa-Ribeiro et al., 2019), due to its flexibility to adjust to diverse social, cultural, linguistic and historical contexts.

The ATLG subscales showed high levels of internal consistency. During self-administration, $\alpha > .85$ with most college student samples and $\alpha > .80$ with most nonstudent samples. The phone surveys with oral administration to adult samples, $\alpha > .80$ for 5-item versions and $\alpha > .70$ for 3-item versions. Test-retest reliability ($r_s > .80$) has been demonstrated with alternate forms (Herek, 1988, 1994). Scores on the ATLG subscales are reliably correlated with other theoretically relevant constructs when higher scores are related to "high religiosity, lack of interpersonal contact with gay men and lesbians, adherence to traditional gender-role attitudes, belief in a

conventional "family ideology, and endorsement of policies that discriminate against sexual minorities" (e.g., Herek, 1994, 2009; Herek & Capitanio, 1996, 1999a, 1999b).

The Heterosexuals' Attitudes toward lesbians and gay men questionnaire has been used to describe and analyze the change in attitudes among undergraduate social studies students in an Israeli University. In this regard, it was meant to measure some attitudes toward homosexuals (Herek, 1988). In addition, the questionnaire was a way of seeking some theoretical attention (Morrison et al., 2017). As a result, it was meant to document actual changes in attitudes toward homosexuals. The questionnaire also evaluated the impact and attitudes of homosexuality in society, particularly in the student community. The scale assessed the social aspects existing because of homosexuality (Ben-Ari, 1988). This scale was also meant to measure attitudes towards homosexuality, social work education, some unique situations, and attitude change in Israel. The questionnaire was also used for other studies, like the relationships between heterosexuals and homosexuals (Morrison et al., 2017). As a result, the scale was meant to find out whether there were notable differences between the two groups of people. In addition, it was also meant to evaluate whether the behaviors of the two groups of people were inconsistent.

Written permission to use all the above materials and questionnaires was obtained from their creators via e-mail.

In conclusion, these are appropriate measures for the study's research questions because they are well-established, reliable, and validated scales used in many other studies, allowing for credible results. The GTS scale is a well-known tool for assessing anti-trans prejudice and is considered unique in assessing negative attitudes. The same stands for the ATLG scale regarding reliability, with the study's

unique contribution of adopting the scale to measure attitudes toward transgender and non-binary people being of great importance. This adaptation was considered better than all the other measures available because it addresses the research questions regarding religiosity, interpersonal contact with transgender and non-binary individuals, adherence to traditional gender-role and family-ideology attitudes, and endorsement of policies that discriminate against transgender and non-binary people.

3.4. Recruitment and Study Procedures

Qualitative: Twenty semi-structured individual interviews were conducted with (10) trans and (10) non-binary interviewees focused on their experiences with medical doctors and health care providers in Greece. Access to the transgender population through the Greek Transgender Support Association (GTSA) association was easy and fast. Using the GTSA database, contact with the members of the organization was made by sending out an email in the form of a newsletter inviting anyone interested in participating in the research. Furthermore, we have a private Facebook group for all GTSA members, an invite to participate was also posted to the group. Detailed information on the procedure and research was provided in both the newsletter and the Facebook post. During the association's meeting of members, an announcement for the research was also made. Accessing the non-binary interviewees was complicated. In the wider Greek LGBTQI community, and during recruitment we were aware of 20 people who openly identify as non-binary; six refused to participate, and four were out of reach. Ten non-binary people agreed to participate, which is essential for the research quality and the balance between the two target groups. It also significantly contributes to the study's uniqueness by improving the visibility of non-binary people in Greece and representing a typically under-represented population in research in general.

The COVID-19 lockdown was beneficial for the research regarding access to the subjects, as due to the curfew on free transportation and working from home or not working at all, interviewees were easily available for an interview appointment conducted either online or in person. All the interviews were completed in one month. I conducted the interviews to observe the interviewees' non-verbal communication, facial expressions, and body language to provide the interviews' exact, adequate, and non-biased transcribing.

The study interviewees signed written consent forms in Greek that included permission to record the session (see Appendix for a sample of consent forms). Before the start of the interview, the researcher verbally explained the content of the document to avoid any misunderstandings. The informed consent document contained the purpose of the study, what interviewees would be requested to do (i.e., complete a demographics questionnaire and participate in a semi-structured interview regarding their experiences with medical doctors), confidentiality, possible benefits, and risks associated with the sharing of experiences, such as emotional distress. It focused extensively on their right to withdraw from the study at any time. The researcher also explained that no video recording would take place, only audio, so interviewees can't be identified by appearance. Once interviewees provided consent, an oral demographic questionnaire was completed. The semi-structured interview lasted approximately 30-50 minutes, either through Skype or in person. After completing the interview, interviewees were provided a debriefing asking for any inappropriate questions or any signs of distress experienced during the interview. The researcher at this time answered any questions from the interviewees and attended to any concerns, present or future, concerning the research. During the debriefing, interviewees were provided with the researcher's contact information if they had additional questions.

Identifying information was removed from the transcripts to protect privacy further. To maintain confidentiality, all materials are locked inside the association's offices; access will be limited to the president of the association and the interviewer.

Thematic Analysis of Qualitative Data:

Thematic analysis stands out as an effective method of qualitative data analysis for several reasons. Firstly, its flexibility and adaptability make it suitable for a wide range of studies, allowing researchers to apply it to different types of data and research questions. This adaptability is particularly valuable in diverse research contexts. Secondly, thematic analysis is relatively easier to learn and apply compared to more complex methods like grounded theory or discourse analysis, which require more specialized training. This ease of use makes it accessible to a broader range of researchers, including those who may be new to qualitative analysis.

Thirdly, thematic analysis's ability to identify and analyze patterns across a wide dataset makes it especially useful for studies aiming to understand general trends or themes. Its balanced approach, allowing for interpretation and subjectivity without necessitating the deep theoretical knowledge required by methods like narrative analysis or discourse analysis, positions it as a practical middle-ground approach. Fourthly, thematic analysis can provide a comprehensive overview of the data, effectively capturing both the breadth and depth of the themes within it. Lastly, the results of thematic analysis are often more accessible to a broader audience, focusing on identifying clear and distinct themes, which can be more easily understood than the results of some other qualitative methods.

However, it's crucial to remember that the effectiveness of thematic analysis, like any qualitative method, heavily depends on the skill and rigor of the researcher,

as well as the specific research context. Therefore, it's important to choose a method that aligns well with the research objectives and the nature of the data.

Analysis of Quantitative Data:

The sample was recruited using targeted e-mails, faxes, Twitter, and Facebook feeds. The invitation (see appendix for the sample of the Survey Monkey called in Greek) for participation was posted to private medical Facebook groups and sent to medical doctors in the form of a newsletter via personal e-mail or fax. Due to my previous work in three major hospitals in Athens, my access to these groups remained and my work in the Ministry of Health as part of the committee for the inclusion of trans and intersex people was an asset in recruitment. Inclusion criteria were medical doctors that reside in any part of Greece, either in a city, town, or village.

In addition to a background information sheet and a detailed consent form, the questionnaires were administered to a random sample of 248 medical doctors using the Internet. Specifically, Survey Monkey was used to design the study and links were sent by email. To ensure confidentiality, access to such URL links was password-protected and a unique study ID was generated. All questionnaires were anonymous to ensure privacy and increase validity. Before answering the questionnaires, interviewees were asked to read and electronically acknowledge agreement to a consent form. No identifying information was asked of interviewees. Two hundred forty-one questionnaires were completed before announcing the lockdown of the Greek government due to Covid-19. When the COVID-19 crisis started, medical doctors became unavailable, and only two additional questionnaires were completed. A second round of recruitment was attempted two weeks after the lockdown. Only

five additional questionnaires were obtained through that attempt. See Appendix A for internet questionnaires and consent forms.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS

This chapter will present the results from both qualitative and quantitative analyses and the analysis methods used to address each research objective and question. On the first level, this chapter will focus on analyzing the qualitative results and displaying the themes that emerged from the interviews. Second, the statistical findings of the questionnaires will be presented from both scales answered by the interviewees. The presentation of the study's demographic data, reliability tests, and descriptive statistics will also be part of the current chapter.

4.1. Qualitative-Thematic Analysis Procedure

The thematic analysis was conducted using NVivo software 12th edition. The choice of software was based on its ability to work with multiple types of qualitative data simultaneously and gather all data together in one place. NVivo provides ways to have a comprehensive understanding of what themes are in the data, and it also allows for deeper analysis. For example, there is the ability to run a quick Word Frequency query to identify which words the interviewees are repeatedly using.

The researcher conducted a thematic analysis of trans and non-binary people's encounters with healthcare providers. The study was a complex, interactive process that required close attention to detail and reflexivity. The theme analysis was carried out by the researcher using a systematic set of procedures. The researcher first reviewed all interview transcripts and relevant materials in order to familiarize herself with the qualitative data. In order to comprehend the scope and complexity of the participants' experiences, this required reading through the interview transcripts several times. The researcher got well acquainted with the intricacies and nuances in the participants' narratives during this first stage.

An essential component of this procedure was getting ready for the NVivo software analysis. The research questions were carefully reviewed, all interviews were meticulously transcribed, sections that corresponded to the research questions were highlighted, and a coding scheme for the themes was developed. For instance, the "Presence of Negative Experiences" topic was used to identify any instances in which a participant was reported to have had poor treatment or to have been dissatisfied with a medical professional. Nevertheless, the "Presence of Positive Experiences" topic was used to code their positive perception of their interactions with medical personnel. The interviews and their transcript data were individually entered into the software. Step-by-step coding was produced by underlining specific portions of the participants' responses.

The researcher found and tagged significant portions of the data with descriptive codes emphasizing concepts, participant experiences, or claims during the first round of coding. After the original codes were refined through the data reduction procedure, the dataset was made simpler by organizing related codes into subthemes. The data's primary concepts were captured in broad themes that were created through additional organization.

After that, these preliminary codes were carefully reviewed and arranged into prospective themes. In order to find emerging trends, similar codes were clustered together at this step. Negative experiences in healthcare settings were the subject around which cases of misgendering, subpar clinical practice, and invasion of privacy during medical examinations were gathered. These emerging topics were subjected to a critical assessment in the next phase. In this instance, the investigator went over every theme in connection with the coded extracts and the complete dataset. The process of this review was iterative, involving multiple rounds of theme refinement,

splitting, merging, and eliminating. To accurately depict the data, the researcher had to make sure each topic was unique, cohesive, and consistent.

The researcher first identified and defined the topics before delving deeply into each one. Beyond merely labeling the themes, this step involved figuring out what each theme best reflected about the experiences of the participants and how it connected to the more general study objectives. Subjects such as "Emotional Pain and Distress Experienced" were meticulously crafted to encompass the range of feelings expressed by the individuals interviewed. The researcher carefully examined and improved the themes and subthemes to make sure they appropriately reflected the facts. Exemplar quotes were chosen to offer particular instances that complemented each theme. Analyzing the data required an understanding of the themes' relevance and importance in relation to the study's goals. The iterative process's correctness, transparency, and consistency in distilling the essence of the data through theme analysis improved the research's validity and reliability.

During the last stage of reporting, the researcher chose moving quotations to represent each subject and create a story that effectively conveyed the information. This story brought to life the realities of trans and non-binary people in hospital settings; it was more than just a compilation of themes and subthemes. The researcher remained critical and introspective throughout this process, conscious of their own prejudices and how they might affect how the data was interpreted. They practiced reflexivity, continuously challenging their viewpoints and presumptions and thinking about how this would impact the analysis. The objective was to present a thorough, compassionate, and nuanced picture of the experiences of the participants, shedding light on the difficulties and resiliency faced by transgender and non-binary people while interacting with the healthcare system.

The in-depth interviews yielded six main themes after a thematic analysis that took into account the research questions regarding the attitudes of Greek doctors toward transgender people: the presence of positive and negative experiences, emotional pain and distress experienced, deciphering the behavior of doctors, the health system and the effectiveness of medical care, and the differences between the experiences of transgender and non-binary interviewees. The next part provides a detailed presentation of these themes, which were developed based on the replies provided by transgender and non-binary individuals regarding their interactions with medical professionals.

The following table presents the themes, subthemes, key findings and example of two quotes for each theme:

Main Theme	Subthemes	Main Findings	Example of Quotes
Presence of Negative Experiences	Abusive behaviors, Misgendering, Poor clinical practice, Refusal of care, Privacy violations	Disrespect for gender identity, misgendering, poor clinical practice, refusal of medical care, and privacy violations reported.	1. "I spent three days in the hospital, three days of misgendering and disrespect..." (Trans Man, 63) 2. "I felt like 'lab rats', 'a show', and 'a freak'."
Emotional Pain and Distress Experienced	Fear and mistrust, Emotional abuse, Sadness, Anxiety, Avoidance of medical care	High levels of fear, mistrust, emotional abuse, sadness, anxiety, and avoidance of medical care.	1. "I have a phobia of doctors due to my experience..." (Non-Binary, 26) 2. "I felt fear and sadness; he should know what testosterone does to you." (Trans Man, 36)
Decoding Doctors' Behavior	Bio theory, Worldview, Religious beliefs, Specialty influence, Lack of training, Stereotypes, Sexism, Transphobia	Doctor behaviors influenced by bio theory, worldview, religious beliefs, specialty, lack of training in LGBTQI issues, stereotypes, sexism, and transphobia.	1. "[...]His negative attitude towards my gender identity... relate to his religious beliefs." (Trans Woman, 42) 2. "I think it has to do with their training; not all doctors are transphobic..." (Non-Binary, 34)
Health System and Efficiency of Medical Care	Inclusivity, Infrastructure, Insurance coverage, Psychological support, Transitioning support	Healthcare system criticized for non-inclusivity, lack of infrastructure, and no insurance coverage for transitioning; lack of psychological support.	1. "The health system in Greece, Is for the garbage only." (Non-Binary, 36) 2. "The state and insurance should cover all the necessary surgeries without question." (Non-Binary, 36)

Main Theme	Subthemes	Main Findings	Example of Quotes
Presence of Positive Experiences	Professionalism, Respect for identity, Affirmative care, Openness, Information and support	Friendliness, respect for gender identity, affirmative care, openness of medical staff, and provision of information and support seen as positive.	1. "She always spoke to me using my real name, not the dead name." (Trans Man, 25) 2. "He was very understanding and showed interest in my medical issues." (Non-Binary, 25)
Identity Non-Disclosure of Trans and Non-Binary Interviewees	Fear of discrimination, Health complications	Non-binary individuals more likely to not disclose identity due to fear of discrimination; potential health complications.	1. "I did not know what non-binary meant to the physician... decided not to disclose my identity." (Non-Binary, 25) 2. "Therefore, I did not know how to bring it up." (Trans Woman, 33)

4.1.1. Thematic Analysis results

Presence of Negative Experiences

Most interviewees discussed their perceptions of doctors' abusive behaviors as stemming from questioning their gender identity, which leads to misgendering. A total of 14/20 interviewees (8 trans and 6 non-binary) reported disrespect for their gender identity, even in cases of trans people who have altered their documents. The interviewees thought that the emergence of such behaviors was due to the stereotypical perceptions of physicians and their ignorance of the clinical management of trans and non-binary interviewees. In the latter case, interviewees recognized that they felt less secure dealing with such medical doctors and sought therapeutic care from other healthcare providers who were more specialized. The presence of poor clinical practice is also evident, as there is significant difficulty regarding the privacy of the examination. This results in a devaluation of both their personality and the clinical practice itself, as well as their right to an equal provision of health care. On various occasions, the interviewees reported that doctors might refuse to provide medical care as they do not consider the patient's biological and

external characteristics congruent. There are many reports in most of the interviews concerning the privacy of the examination, specifically, 12/20 interviewees (9 trans and 3 non-binary), mentioned that during the examination in the hospitals or clinics, the doctors invited trainees to attend the examination, without acquiring informed consent. All interviewees using similar descriptions said that they felt like “lab rats”, “a show”, and “a freak”. All of them stressed the need to find doctors who are applying affirmative care to feel safe.

Excerpt 1-PT7. *"Following the removal of my ovaries, I spent three days in the hospital, three days of misgendering and disrespect, in pain. I am ashamed of myself and afraid of doctors"* Trans Man, 63

Questioning gender identity leads to misgendering. 13/20 of interviewees reported misgendering. In addition to the dangers posed by this behavior to interviewees' physical health, there are also negative consequences for their mental health, with interviewees feeling marginalized, developing feelings of worthlessness, and at the same time being forced to seek other medical care providers in this case. As regards misgendering, this seems to be related to the external characteristics of interviewees. Especially for trans people, the closer the exterior features and gender expression are to their gender identity, the less the incidence of misgendering, with the relationship between the two elements, as mentioned above, being generally inverse. However, suppose such characteristics are not easily identifiable. In that case, there were extreme cases of misgendering from doctors reported, despite the constant efforts by trans patients insisting on the name and pronoun associated with their gender.

Excerpt 2-PNB17. *"They don't respect me, and they don't respect my pronouns, my gender identity. They are making fun of me and my appearance. A doctor should not do that.[...]I am not supposed to educate them about my identity"* Non-Binary, 25

It is also observed that negative experiences are reduced when patients are at risk of severe health problems. When these patients suffer from serious chronic diseases, the negative experiences are less reported as their concentration lies on the healing process rather than what the medical professionals perceive of them.

Excerpt 3 – PT8. *" I left the clinic feeling so ashamed, that I forgot about my cancer diagnosis. I felt crushed and disrespected when they misgendered me like this in front of all these people in the waiting room. How can they do that, don't they see me; How can they see a woman and call a man's name; That was even worse than my diagnosis. I never wanted to go back there again..ever"* Trans Woman, 42

Innately, transphobia is commonly experienced by trans and non-binary persons as characterized by implied and covert verbal attacks or simply the denial of acceptance of the gender identity of the interviewees. Regardless of the nature and the degree to which transphobia is experienced, a strong sense of ridicule emerges, which characterizes the specific negative experience.

A total of 12/20 interviewees reported some form of abusive behavior from doctors. There was a strong perception that health professionals have high power over trans and non-binary interviewees. In one extreme case, it even resulted in direct blackmail during their treatment. More specifically, one trans person participant reported that a doctor who attended to her knew some of her friends and required her to pay 1,000 euros to him or else he would disclose her gender identity (outing) to her friends. In addition, doctors' behaviors characterized by signs of sexual harassment are also

present and frequently disguised during medical operation procedures. These behaviors are observed mainly by male health professionals. Three non-binary interviewees said they experienced unwanted sexual contact where the male doctors carelessly touched them sexually during the examination.

Excerpt 5-PNB12 *"I have promised not to go to a cis man gynecologist again. After the last abusive experience two years ago. It has also made me choose better, the doctor I will go to. That is, the references should be from people I trust..."* Non-Binary, 35

Also, recognizing the increased degree of transphobia and reduced level of information of doctors and education about the application of medical practices in interviewees of the LGBTQI community increases the anxiety interviewees experience regarding the provision of medical care they receive. They feel the need to ensure they receive the best treatment while at the same time avoiding negative experiences. As a result of such concerns, some interviewees tend to prevent visiting cis male doctors.

Excerpt 6 – PT6. *I did my first breast augmentation with a friend's doctor, and I regretted my decision because he gave me poor-quality implants, inferior placement, and terrible work in general. The result was that I had to do another operation, leaving me half with one breast. How can you trust doctors again;"* Trans Woman, 26

Presence of Positive Experiences

One critical element perceived as a positive experience by 8 interviewees is the doctors' commitment to providing quality healthcare to them. Examples of positive experiences they reported were friendliness and special reverence on behalf of the

doctor, especially in guidance on gender transitioning and issues related to interviewees' physical health. Intrinsically, the degree of openness of the medical staff of the health units is considered necessary, accompanied by apparent friendliness, as it translates into better health outcomes. The lack of misgendering is a positive experience since it assures the patient that the services they will get are the best.

Excerpt 7 - PT1. *"I had a great experience with a female doctor; she always spoke to me using my real name, not the dead name. She did not misgender me once; from the beginning, she understood what she had to do. It was the first time this had ever happened to me. I feel grateful"* Trans Man, 25

In every healthcare setting, positive experiences should include the physicians' professional approach to patients by examining interviewees' anatomical features, which simultaneously contain elements of informativeness and explanation about their state of physical health and support in psychological terms. Affirmative care was perceived as important and necessary for the 8/20 interviewees who reported positive experiences. This covers a wide range of actions such as in-depth discussions with them, referral to mental health professionals, and guiding them on the different laws that safeguard their rights while seeking healthcare. This latter aspect is especially important since there is no law in Greece right now that is explicitly aimed at trans care.

Excerpt 8-PNB17. *"To my surprise, a male doctor had a positive stance towards me when I decided to disclose that I was non-binary. He was very understanding and showed interest in my medical issues and the probability of hormone therapy. He was extremely supportive...made me think that he is LGBTQI and also an ally"* Non-Binary person, 25

Even though professionalism was distinguished as a significantly positive experience, it was emphasized that it is further appreciated when the patient's contact with the health care provider is coupled with increased authenticity and straightforwardness. The above two elements help interviewees, on the one hand, to eliminate feelings of marginalization and to recognize a relative sense of equality with the other patients.

Emotional Pain and Distress Experienced

Many interviewees, reported fear (19/20) and mistrust (18/20) of doctors, leading to avoidance of medical care. Also, feelings of irritation were reported by trans and non-binary interviewees when doctors ignored their gender identity, manifested by the insistence of health professionals not to mention their gender.

Regarding the feelings experienced by trans and non-binary interviewees during their contact with health professionals, the perception of emotional abuse becomes apparent, especially in cases where their gender identity is directly or indirectly challenged. Difficulties in managing it accompany this specific emotion. As a result, some interviewees tended to hide their gender identity or sexual orientation (staying in the closet) for fear of being abused. Moreover, interviewees wondered about the ability of physicians to manage cases of trans and non-binary interviewees, with this particular weakness being experienced mildly; interviewees recognized that physicians might have probably not come in contact with trans and non-binary patients often. Similar is how trans and non-binary interviewees externalize their emotions in cases where the objective difficulties of doctors in managing similar situations are recognized.

Another factor emotionally affecting the interviewees relates to how heteronormativity can impact treatment. Interviewees nevertheless recognize the need

to seek medical help given the above. However, interviewees have a relatively adverse reaction to providing the necessary information to doctors, such as detailed medical history, as it is considered that their privacy is violated.

Excerpt 9-PT3. *[...]I felt fear and sadness; he should know what testosterone does to you; it's his job. He should inform me about what testosterone would do to my internal organs. I could have cancer if I did not remove my ovaries on time. He is dangerous and does not know how to do his job"* Trans Man, 36

The externalization of the resulting emotions can vary, as trans and non-binary interviewees are likely to react vigorously or try to distance themselves without reacting simply by being intolerant.

Excerpt 10-PNB15. *"I have a phobia of doctors due to my experience; they are transphobic and fatphobic; I try not to visit them if it is not an emergency. [...]I had many bad experiences with psychiatrists pathologizing me and filling me with pills. [...] I always freak out when I go to the "gynecologist," where I have a panic attack. [...]I avoid doctors, especially if they are cis-straight"* Non-Binary, 26

On the other hand, there are feelings of fear toward medical practice, especially when surgery is required. Fear is judged to stem from the reduced trust that characterizes the doctor-patient relationship. In addition, this fear is accompanied by sadness, associated with insecurity about the degree to which trans and non-binary interviewees can receive comprehensive medical care. It is significant to note that in some cases, the feelings of anxiety disappear based on the characteristics of the medical doctor. For instance, this is experienced when the health professionals are friendly and open to the trans patient. Innately, the emotions are alleviated when the medical approach is careful and no signs of misgendering are observed.

Excerpt 11-PNB15. *“I will always remember this wonderful experience with a woman doctor. It was like she had genuine interest from the first meeting. She asked me my pronouns and I never felt like she was strangely looking at me as I usually do. She asked me questions slowly and respectfully, checking again if it was okay for her to ask more questions about my sexual life. I felt safe and accepted”* Non-Binary, 26

Decoding Doctors' Behavior

A total of 18/20 interviewees decoded harmful doctors' attitudes due to a lack of training in affirmative care. Regarding the reasons shaping the behavior of doctors towards trans and non-binary interviewees, two essential elements were highlighted by interviewees. These were the doctors' external characteristics complemented by the values of the biological indicators resulting from the biochemical tests. Intrinsicly, these factors will significantly impact misgendering and the acceptance of the sexual orientation of members of the LGBTQI community. The two elements reported by interviewees as determining the behavior of doctors towards trans and non-binary interviewees can be summarized as the bio theory and worldview doctors seem to embrace, especially religious beliefs. Interviewees perceived religiosity as being one of the critical elements affecting doctors' attitudes. 17/20 of interviewees reported that they believe religious doctors are more intolerant and transphobic.

Excerpt 12-PT8 *“[...]I was already skeptical about visiting a religious doctor. Religion and transphobia go hand in hand, but I could not risk missing the appointment. It took months of waiting. His negative attitude towards my gender identity, misgendering, and critical stance relate to his religious beliefs. I am not entering a doctor's office with religious images again”* Trans Woman, 42

At the same time, interviewees seemed to perceive differences in doctors' behaviors based on their specialty. Mental health professionals were reported to display more positive behaviors in 12/20 (8 trans, 4 non-binary), and gynecologists (doctors specializing in reproductive organs) were reported to show more negative behaviors, as reported by 12/20 interviewees. There was no mention of urologists in the specific study.

Other than the doctors' religiosity impacts, there is a significant lack of knowledge and training of health professionals on gender identity and sexual orientation. Still, interviewees seem to separate this element from the doctor's scientific competence. It is judged that doctors' psychoeducation on LGBTQI issues is particularly low in purely medical and pathological problems, such as managing HIV-positive patients and cases of patients who received hormones and plastic surgery. At the same time, it is judged that the effort of doctors for self-education in the management of trans and non-binary cases is of low level, a fact that intensifies their inability to behave appropriately.

Excerpt 13-PNB20 *"I think it has to do with their training; I mean, not all doctors are transphobic, some of them have good intentions, but they lack information on our issues. I refuse to believe that if we provided the doctors and medical staff with the proper training, they would continue to treat us poorly. I have some experience from other places in Europe that doctors are trained, and their behavior is humane"* non-Binary, 34

In addition, the interviewees raised the issue of stereotypes, as reinforcing the reasons mentioned above for doctors' negative behaviors. At this point, the nature of the

behavior of health professionals is associated with the general phenomena of sexism that characterize modern society, which is also aided by a high degree of transphobia.

Excerpt 14- PT8. *“I am not only mocked and discriminated against because I am a trans woman, I am inferior because I am a woman. This society views our transition as a downgrade, from the strong to the weak gender. Look what happens with the cis women. With all the femicides, with the abortion rights. If a cis woman is treated unfairly, that she is supposedly accepted by society, imagine what happens with us, we stand no chance of receiving proper treatment and respect, not from doctors, not from society ”* Trans Woman, 42

Concerning the presence of positive behaviors, it was evident that the reasons for the corresponding conduct by doctors were based, to an extent, on the interaction and experience with cases of people belonging to the LGBTQI community.

Excerpt 16-PNB 19 *“I stopped going to doctors without getting referrals from the community. I did not want to be abused anymore. So, I choose only people that I am certain have training and experience with gender identities, always preferring the private and not public sector, the more the experience with our community the less likely I will be abused, can’t play with odds with my health”* Non-Binary, 36

Health System and Efficiency of Medical Care

Concerning the health system and the extent to which trans and non-binary interviewees initially enjoy equal and effective health care, exclusions are considered exceptionally high. All 20 interviewees reported that the Greek healthcare system is not inclusive and efficient. Exclusions are based on practical and substantive problems and the inadequacy of the legal framework regarding the identity of trans

and non-binary interviewees in general. There are also significant delays in interviewees' access to medical care, but this fact is considered not to differ significantly from the services received by the general population.

Excerpt 16-PNB 19 *"Okay... The health system in Greece, Is for the garbage only. I pay as much as I can. As much as I prefer to seek treatment privately. I want to avoid the queue and the months of waiting; I want to avoid the way they stare at me"* Non-Binary, 36

A crucial issue that emerged was the possibility of prescribing tests and drugs that correspond to the gender identity that interviewees identify and differentiate from their biological-anatomical sex. Two trans interviewees under hormonal therapy indicated they struggled to find a medical doctor with expertise in transgender medicine. Consequently, they were obliged to take personal responsibility for using drugs. This problem has a broader basis, as sexuality does not legally reflect the choice of gender identity, resulting in the inability to prove its identification as trans and cisgender. Bureaucracy is emerging as an Achilles heel of the health system. In cases where the external appearance does not correspond to the gender identity of trans and non-trans people, patients' appropriate health access is reduced due to the resulting discrepancies.

Nevertheless, it is considered that the Legal Recognition of Gender Identity significantly helps reduce related problems. Greece's healthcare system's failure to cater to transgender patients was also highlighted by one participant concerned that there were no neutral bathrooms or clear policies directing patients to use bathrooms that matched their identities. Therefore, it was hectic in the two weeks he was admitted to the hospital.

Furthermore, all the trans(10) and non-binary(10) interviewees argued that transitioning should be covered by the public health system. The welfare state should provide all patients with the necessary health care to enjoy maximum physical and psychological well-being. This argument is strengthened given the enormous cost of the respective surgeries (mastectomy, gender reassignment surgery) and treatments such as hormones.

Excerpt 17-PNB 19 *"I have a huge problem. Respectively, in the Netherlands, you "put on tits," you do not pay anything, etc. We are in a tragic situation. To have any operation, (..) you need 10,000 euros. It is tragic; it is unacceptable. The state and insurance should cover all the necessary surgeries without question. Trans women should not be driven to sex work to be able to have their surgeries"* Non-Binary, 36

Finally, the lack of psychological support for trans and non-binary interviewees is highlighted, a critical problem when there is no financial capacity to turn to private mental health professionals. Many trans and non-binary people risk their mental and physical health by refusing to visit a state hospital, knowing they are at risk of ill-treatment by doctors. This harms their health and increases their risk of developing a severe illness or psychological disorder since they prefer to leave their issues untreated than be exposed to stigma and discrimination in the public sector.

Identity Non-Disclosure of Trans and Non-Binary Interviewees

As mentioned in the literature review, non-binary identities belong inside the trans umbrella, and some trans people also identify as non-binary and vice-versa. The experiences concerning doctors' attitudes are similar and interchangeably reported. Most interviewees reported their perceptions of doctors' abusive behaviors stemming from questioning their gender identity. A fundamental difference was that non-binary

people tend not to disclose their identity more often, especially in cases where they could not be identified by appearance as gender diverse. Four non-binary interviewees said they kept from revealing their identities for fear of being discriminated against.

Excerpt 18: *"I visited this facility after I suffered from anemia. I did not know what non-binary meant to the physician I found. To avoid being hurt and sticking to the dire services I needed, I decided not to disclose my identity to him... I only identified myself as [using the identity name] and nothing more...."* Non-Binary, 25

On rare occasions, trans people also choose not to disclose their identity following their legal and medical transition when they can't be identified as trans. Only one of the trans persons decided not to. The 23-year-old trans man had a challenge revealing to his doctor.

Excerpt 19: *"I remember standing before this doctor who had yet to identify himself. Therefore, I did not know how to bring it up. He did not open the door for our conversation, so I decided not to reveal my identity to him...."* Trans Woman, 33

The failure to disclose one's identity could have serious health complications. An example is a trans person suffering from abdominal pain and the doctors presuming them to be male. However, such pain could originate from the ovaries. Hence, if this had been revealed earlier, the best medical attention could have been offered. Most differences were not affected by the interviewees' gender identity but primarily by factors such as passing, legal gender recognition, and transition status. Passing as a binary gender would protect trans and non-binary people from negative attitudes, especially if legal documents and transition status support this binary gender. All of the above indicates the bias towards this population from medical doctors.

Summary of the Qualitative Themes

In conclusion, the thematic analysis revealed six main themes: The Presence of Negative Experiences, The Presence of Positive Experiences, Emotional Pain and Distress Experienced, Decoding of Doctors' Behavior, and Identity Non-Disclosure of Trans and Non-Binary People. In the Presence of Negative Experiences theme, interviewees referred to their perception of doctors' abusive behaviors, including questioning their gender, misgendering them, and disrespecting their gender identity. Interviewees admitted they felt less secure due to poor clinical practice and felt devaluated, marginalized, and worthless when being misgendered or offered poor health provision, against their right to equal medical attention. Regarding positive experiences, interviewees highlighted the doctors' professionalism and commitment to providing quality healthcare to them. They also included doctors' friendliness toward them, authenticity, and straightforwardness. Finally, they regarded positive experiences as the lack of misgendering and the presence of affirmative care.

Regarding Emotional Pain and Distress Experienced, interviewees revealed fear and mistrust of doctors and generally reduced trust in the doctor-patient relationship, often leading to avoidant behavior regarding medical care. They also mentioned they experience irritation when misgendered and consequent perceived emotional abuse. Sadness was another emotion interviewees experienced in connection to the above. Decoding doctors' behaviors, interviewees attribute doctors' different behaviors to the bio theory and their worldview, considering religiosity as the most potent factor in the genesis of negative behaviors. Interviewees also identified differences in behavior based on the medical specialty, with gynecologists presenting with more negative behaviors and mental health professionals embracing more positive behaviors. They attributed these negative behaviors to absent or low-

quality psychoeducation of doctors on LGBTQI issues. Finally, interviewees talked about stereotypes and especially phenomena of sexism aided by high levels of transphobia as determinants of doctors' negative behaviors toward them.

Regarding decoding of positive behavior of doctors, interviewees viewed interaction and experience with LGBTQI people as a factor that enhances positive attitudes and behaviors. In the theme regarding the health system and its efficiency, interviewees referred to the Greek healthcare system as being non-inclusive and inefficient, lacking psychological support and essential infrastructure that a trans or non-binary individual would require in all levels of medical provision. They also talked about the lack of insurance coverage regarding transitioning. Finally, the last theme revealed how non-binary people tend not to disclose their identity more often than transgender individuals, driven by fear of discrimination, especially when they could not be identified as gender diverse by appearance.

This table succinctly organizes the key themes and their detailed descriptions, providing a clear and structured summary of the qualitative results:

Theme	Description
Presence of Negative Experiences	- Abusive behaviors from medical practitioners, including questioning gender, misgendering, and disrespect for gender identity.- Feelings of insecurity due to substandard clinical practices.- Sense of being devalued, marginalized, and feelings of worthlessness.
Presence of Positive Experiences	- Encounters with professionalism and commitment to quality healthcare.- Positive attributes noted: friendliness, authenticity, and straightforwardness.- Positive experiences marked by the absence of misgendering and the presence of affirmative care.
Emotional Pain and Distress Experienced	- Pervasive fear and mistrust towards doctors.- Emotional distress and perceived emotional abuse from being misgendered.- Sadness linked to healthcare experiences.

Theme	Description
Decoding of Doctors' Behavior	- Behaviors attributed to biological theories, worldviews, and religiosity.- Variance in behavior based on medical specialty, with gynecologists often more negative.- Negative behaviors tied to inadequate LGBTQI psychoeducation and societal sexism and transphobia.
Health System and Efficiency of Medical Care	- Critique of the Greek healthcare system's lack of inclusivity and efficiency.- Absence of necessary psychological support and infrastructure for trans and non-binary individuals.- Issues with insurance coverage for transition-related needs.
Identity Non-Disclosure of Trans and Non-Binary People	- Reluctance among non-binary individuals to disclose their identity due to fear of discrimination.- More pronounced where gender diversity is not apparent by appearance.

Original Hypotheses Validation

The three research topics raised are not specifically addressed by the material that has been provided. The thematic analysis results from the qualitative data, which throw light on the experiences and perspectives of trans and non-binary people with medical professionals, are the main focus of the research. It offers perceptions into the good and bad parts of their encounters with physicians and the larger healthcare system.

Research Question I:

The material offered covers issues pertaining to prejudice and bad encounters (such as misgendering, abusive conduct, and disdain) that transgender and non-binary people encounter while interacting with medical professionals. It does not, however, specifically address the connections between the observed levels of prejudice and the demographic characteristics of doctors (age, gender, and place of residency).

Research Question II:

Whether trans women or trans males report more unfavorable attitudes from doctors is not explicitly addressed in the research. Though it doesn't clearly compare the experiences of trans women and trans males, it does touch on topics of positive and negative encounters, emotional discomfort, and factors influencing doctors' conduct.

Research Question III

Direct information about whether medical professionals have more accepting views toward transgender patients undergoing full sex-reassignment surgery is lacking. The thematic analysis does not really address attitudes toward people undergoing sex-reassignment surgery; instead, it concentrates on a number of characteristics of the doctor-patient interaction, emotional experiences, and the effectiveness of the healthcare system.

The thematic analysis of interviews with transgender and non-binary individuals in Greece provides compelling support for the validation of qualitative hypotheses regarding their encounters with healthcare providers as well as prejudice and discrimination. Specifically, this analysis lends credence to the anticipated findings outlined in two key hypotheses.

According to the available data, it seems that the thematic analysis validated the following qualitative hypotheses:

IV. Transgender and gender non-confirming individuals in Greece are anticipated to disclose prejudice and unfavorable comments from physicians throughout their interviews. The results are consistent with the reports submitted to

GTSA by its members for the last 16 years. Thematic analysis uncovered themes like "Presence of Negative Experiences," which contained subthemes like misgendering, abusive behaviors, inadequate clinical practice, care rejection, and invasions of privacy. The sample quotes provide more evidence for the prejudice and unfavorable attitudes that transgender and non-binary people face in healthcare environments.

V. Negative health consequences are predicted to be reported by trans and gender non-confirming individuals in Greece who have encountered trans prejudice and discrimination. The "Emotional Pain and Distress Experienced" theme draws attention to the high rates of anxiety, depression, dread, mistrust, and experiences emotional abuse. Specific examples of emotional anguish, fear, and avoidance associated with unfavorable interactions with healthcare practitioners are given in the sample quotes. This lends credence to the theory that those who have been subjected to transphobic prejudice and discrimination might report negative health consequences, which is consistent with previous research.

4.2. Quantitative Results

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive and frequency tables were created to look into the sample's demographics. Although 248 interviewees were initially recruited, the data of just 121 interviewees were considered valid and used in the current analysis. The rest of the subjects did not complete any part or most parts of the questionnaires or were excluded due to not being medical professionals.

Reliability Analysis

To evaluate the internal consistency reliability for each instrument in this study, Cronbach alphas were calculated. It is commonly agreed that the acceptable values of alpha range from 0.70 to 0.95, with $\alpha < .07$ being a potential consequence of the construct containing a low number of questions, having heterogeneous constructs, or having poor inter-relatedness between items (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). On the other hand, alpha values higher than 0.90 may indicate things are redundant, i.e., measuring the same question but in different words (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

In the current study, the Genderism and Transphobia Scale (GTS) showed a high internal consistency for the total 32-item scale, ($\alpha=.976$), as well as for its 25-item Genderism/Transphobia subscale ($\alpha=.973$), and its 7-item Gender-Bashing subscale ($\alpha=.91$).

The adapted version of The Heterosexuals' Attitudes Toward Lesbians and Gay Men Questionnaire (ATLG), which contains 20 questions, also demonstrated strong reliability, with an internal consistency of $\alpha= .966$. As all alpha scores for both scales exceeded the recommended alpha value of 0.90, some items were likely repetitive. Nonetheless, previous research using these two measures has reported similar Cronbach alphas to the current ones, and both questionnaires are considered helpful in measuring homotransphobic attitudes (Claman, 2008; Corrêa-Ribeiro, Iglesias, & Camargos, 2019; Hill & Willoughby, 2005; Rosichan, 2015).

Descriptive Analysis

The adapted version of the Heterosexuals' Attitudes Toward Lesbians and Gay Men Questionnaire was completed by 121 subjects, and scores ranged from 20 to 90 ($M=40.27$, $SD=17.3$). Similar to the GTS, higher scores indicated more significant transphobic attitudes. Data were positively and moderately skewed, with a skewness

statistic of .962, suggesting an overall tendency of the present sample to express negative attitudes towards trans* individuals.

For the GTS, the data of 110 interviewees were considered valid, as 11 individuals did not complete this part of the study. Scores ranged from 32-145 points ($M= 61.3$, $SD=26.1$), with higher scores indicating higher transphobia, genderism, and gender-bashing. Results on the 25-Genderism/Transphobia subscale ranged from 25 to 112 points, with a mean statistic of 50.52 and a standard deviation of 22.36. Scores on the 7-item Gender-Bashing scale ranged from 7 to 34 ($M= 10.57$, $SD=4.6$). The skewness statistic 1.036 of the total scale indicated that the scores were shifted positively, implying that the interviewees of this study tended to hold negative attitudes toward trans* people.

Regression Analysis and Assumption Checking

A multiple linear regression analysis was used to predict Greek medical doctors' attitudes towards transgender individuals (DV1) based on their gender (IV1), age (IV2), area of work (IV3), previous education on LGBT+ matters (IV4), previous contact with individuals of the LGBT+ community (IV5) and religion (IV6). A Pearson's correlation was first advised, showing significant correlations between some of the IVs, namely, between LGBT exposure and LGBT education, $p = .011$, and religion, and age, $p .015$. In addition, the DV was found to significantly correlate with age, $p < .001$, LGBT education, $p < .001$, LGBT contact, $p = .005$, and religion, $p < .001$. Further preliminary exploration was performed to establish whether assumptions for the regression had been met. Residuals were independent, as assessed by a Durbin-Watson statistic of $d=2.1$. Partial regression plots suggested linear relationships between the dependent variable and each of the independent variables. Moreover, homoscedasticity was evaluated by visual inspection of a plot of

studentized residuals versus unstandardized predicted values. The assumption of normality was also met according to the visual exploration of a histogram, a normal P-P plot of Regression Standardized Residual, and a normal Q-Q Plot of Studentised Residual.

As a rule of thumb, correlation r values greater than .7, tolerance values lower than 0.1, and VIF values greater than ten cause concern for multicollinearity (Berry et al., 1985; Vatcheva et al., 2016). Despite the significant Pearson's correlations in the present analysis, no r values greater than 0.7 were obtained, tolerance values were all greater than 0.1, and VIF values ranged from 1.038 to 1.086, suggesting no threat for collinearity in the data sample. Freund and colleagues (2006) have also suggested evaluating VIF against the model's overall fit using the R^2 . If $VIF > 1 / (1 - R^2)$, the correlation between the predictors is stronger than the regression relationship, meaning that multicollinearity can impact the coefficient estimates. Applying this formula to this data set, no VIF value was more significant than $1 / (1 - R^2)$. Table 2 illustrates the r values of all the correlations, while VIF values and R^2 are reported in Table 3.

Table 2. Correlation Matrix for Attitudes Towards Transgender People

		AT LG	Gen der	Age	Wor k Area	LGBT Educatio n	LGBT Exposur e	Relig ion
Pearson Correlation	ATLG	1	.126	.361 ***	.125	.329***	.237**	- .455* **
	Age	.361 ***	.146	1	-.145	.052	.008	- .198*
	LGBT Education	.329 ***	.106	.052	.008	1	.209*	-.129

LGBT Exposure	.237 **	.088	.008	.114	.209*	1	-.013
Religion	-	-	-	-.004	-.129	-.013	1
	.455 ***	.071	.198 *				

Notes 1. * Correlation is significant at the .05 level.

** Correlation is significant at the .01 level.

*** Correlation is significant at the .001 level.

Finally, the Case Wise Diagnostics Table highlighted case number 2 as an outlier. This outlier scored 88 points on the ATLG scale and produced a studentized deleted residual (SDR) of 4.2 and an extreme predicted value score of 36.27, with an error in prediction of 51.73. After that, leverage values were examined, all below the safe value of 0.2 (Huber, 1981). The Cook's distance was advised to determine whether there were any influential points, according to which acceptable values are below 1. The current sample did not produce any Cook's values equal to or above 1; thus, case number 2 was included in the analysis and was thought to have no impact on the results (Cook & Weisberg, 1982).

The multiple regression model statistically significantly predicted transphobic attitudes amongst medical staff in Greece, $F(6, 133) = 12.87, p < .001$. R^2 for the overall model was 40.6 with an adjusted R^2 of 37.4, a medium-size effect according to Cohen (1988). Looking at each independent variable, LGBT contact, LGBT education, religion, and age contributed statistically significantly to the prediction, $p < .05$. On the contrary, gender and work area did not significantly affect the medical staff's attitudes towards trans* people. Table 3 summarizes all coefficient statistics.

Table 3. Multiple Regression Results for Transphobic Attitudes

Transphobic a	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics		R ²	Adj. R ²
	B	Std. Err.	Beta	Standard Error		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF		
Model										.406	.374
(Constant)	12.219	9.971		1.226	1.226	-7.534	31.973				
Gender	.505	2.420	.015	.209	.209	-4.288	5.299	.962	1.039		
Age	.374	.096	.295	3.898	3.898	<.184	.563	.921	1.086		
Work Area	4.920	2.510	.145	1.960	1.960	-.053	9.892	.963	1.038		
LGBT Education	9.658	3.151	.230	3.065	3.065	3.415	15.900	.934	1.071		
LGBT Contact	5.528	2.522	.164	2.192	2.192	.531	10.525	.939	1.065		

Religio	-	2.5	-.363	-	<	-	-	.944	1.
n	12.	89	4.	86	.	3	66	05	9
	594		86	5	0				
					0				
					1				

The slope coefficient $b = .374$ for age indicates that an increase in age is associated with an increase in transphobic attitudes when all other variables remain stable, $\beta = .289$, 95% CI [.184, .563], $p < .001$. Regarding prior LGBT Education, medical staff who had received no education on this subject reported 9.658 more points in transphobia than those who had received some LGBT education in the past, $\beta = .23$, 95% CI [3.415, 15.9], $p = .003$. Relatedly, the predicted transphobia score for people who had not been in contact with LGBT individuals in the past was 5.528 points greater than the score for those who had interpersonal experiences with subjects that identify with the LGBT community, $\beta = .164$, 95% CI [.531, 10.525], $p = .02$. As for religion, people who described themselves as non-religious appeared to score 12.594 points lower in transphobic attitudes compared to religious people, $\beta = -.363$, 95% CI [-17.723, -7.466], $p < .001$.

Original Hypotheses Validation:

In general, the results collide with what was expected in the current analysis based on the hypotheses stated at the beginning of the study, with both scales presenting high internal consistency and helping measure homotransphobic attitudes. The analysis suggested linear relationships between the dependent variable and each independent variable, with an overall tendency of the present sample to hold negative attitudes toward trans people. LGBT contact, LGBT education, religiosity, and age

contributed statistically significantly to the prediction, while gender and work area did not significantly affect the attitudes toward trans people. Individuals who identified as non-religious scored 12.594 points lower in transphobic attitudes than religious individuals, which was hypothesized before the commencement of the study. The predicted transphobic score for medical doctors who had not been in contact with LGBT people in the past was 5.528 points greater than the score for those who had had contact with LGBT individuals. Also, the slope coefficient ($b=.374$) for age indicated that increased age was associated with increased transphobic attitudes. A surprising finding of the current analysis was that gender and work area were not found to be significant predictors of negative attitudes toward transgender people.

According to the available data, it seems that the analysis validated the following quantitative hypotheses:

II. Medical professionals who identify as religious will be less accepting of transgender and non-binary people. The findings provide credence to this hypothesis. The transphobic views score of nonreligious people was lower than that of religious people. According to this data, which supports the hypothesis, religious identification is linked to more negative opinions about transgender and non-binary people.

III. Professionals' views on transgender and non-binary people will be positively impacted by their prior exposure to these groups of people. The findings provide support to this theory. When comparing medical personnel who had never interacted with LGBT people to those who had, the anticipated transphobic score for the former group was higher. This implies that being around transgender and gender non-confirming individuals is linked to better attitudes.

The findings that were surprising in this study are the effects of gender and work area on the attitudes of doctors. Attitudes about transgender people were not significantly predicted by gender among the study group of medical professionals. To put it another way, the average level of transphobic sentiment was comparable across male and female medical professionals as well as those with different gender identities. This finding is surprising because it is inconsistent with the literature, across all research, gender was the demographic variable with which relationships between attitudes and behaviors were most commonly explored and related (Ayhan, 2019). Further analysis is recommended. Concerning the work area, the positive unstandardized coefficient (B) shows that transphobic attitudes and work area are generally positively correlated, implying that people who work in particular work areas are more likely to be transphobic overall. In the context of this study, Work Area is a significant predictor of transphobic sentiments, but the absence of statistical significance ($p = 0.052$) raises doubts about the strength of this link. Because it is just above the usual significance threshold (researchers often use a 0.05 threshold), the evidence in this analysis is not very strong for the effect of Work Area on transphobic sentiments.

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION

Wong (2019) discusses the concept of relational injustice, which he defines as the distinct characteristics of unequal and oppressive relationships, highlighting how perpetrators and victims interact. He proposes the notion that since moral relationships transcend the individual well-being of the agents involved, incidental or unintended benefits to individual welfare do not suffice as compensation or rectification for the original relational injustice (Wong, 2019). Relational psychoanalyst Jessica Benjamin created the term "moral third" in the framework of disagreement resolution to mean a safe space that a third person can provide, where "opponents can intersubjectively listen to each other's stories and feel what each other feel while retaining their own identities." This was the case in this study as the researcher was dedicated to bearing witness by being related to the communities they study and yet remains separate, has played the role of the "moral third" to witness, support and report the experiences, abuse, and human suffering with dignity and ethical respect, to inform and raise awareness in the greater public.

The discussion chapter that follows is also written from that stance of the "moral third" will illuminate the study's goals and research questions and summarize the findings regarding doctors' attitudes toward transgender individuals and the experiences of trans and non-binary people with medical doctors and the health system in Greece. This chapter will also analyze the research's ramifications for the field of study, assess the importance of the findings, and offer a critical analysis of the study. Finally, the study's strengths and limitations will also be discussed, offering potential further investigation directions.

This study's exploration of the healthcare experiences of trans and non-binary individuals in Greece, coupled with an examination of medical professionals'

attitudes, provides valuable insights into the complexities of healthcare delivery in a diverse society. The mixed-method approach enriches the understanding of this multifaceted issue, blending qualitative personal experiences with quantitative measures of healthcare professionals' attitudes.

The thematic analysis vividly paints the struggles and challenges faced by trans and non-binary individuals within the Greek healthcare system. The emergence of themes such as 'Presence of Negative Experiences' and 'Emotional Pain and Distress' echo findings in existing literature, which have long highlighted the pervasiveness of discrimination and misunderstanding within healthcare settings towards these communities. Studies like Lambda Legal's report on "When Health Care Isn't Caring" have similarly documented the negative impact of misgendering and disrespectful treatment on the mental health of transgender individuals. The qualitative findings herein underscore this ongoing issue, with personal accounts illustrating the direct impact of healthcare professionals' attitudes on patient well-being (Mosaic, 2023).

Conversely, the theme of 'Presence of Positive Experiences' is a hopeful sign, indicating moments where healthcare professionals' understanding and respect can significantly improve healthcare experiences. This aligns with research suggesting that positive healthcare interactions are crucial for the overall health of trans individuals (National Transgender Discrimination Survey, 2011).

The quantitative analysis further sheds light on the factors influencing healthcare professionals' attitudes. The findings that age, education, and religiosity are significant predictors of transphobic attitudes resonate with broader societal patterns observed in other studies, such as those by Norton and Herek (2013). The importance of exposure to LGBT+ issues and contact with LGBT+ individuals in reducing

negative attitudes is a critical finding, reinforcing the need for comprehensive education and diversity training in medical curricula, as advocated by Jaffee et al. (2016).

The findings that gender and work area do not significantly predict attitudes towards transgender individuals in healthcare settings may indicate a deeper, systemic issue. This contrasts with some existing literature and suggests that transphobia in healthcare is not necessarily influenced by the geographical location of medical professionals or the specific universities from which they received their training. It points to the need for a systemic approach to address these biases across the healthcare sector, regardless of where medical professionals are educated or practice. This approach would involve broad-based educational and policy changes to ensure inclusive and respectful treatment for all patients, including those who are transgender.

The discussions around healthcare system efficiency, legal recognition, and identity non-disclosure highlight the multi-layered barriers trans and non-binary individuals face in accessing healthcare. The urgent need for systemic changes, including legal protections and healthcare policy reforms to support trans and non-binary individuals, is clear.

In conclusion, this study paints a complex picture of the healthcare landscape for trans and non-binary individuals in Greece. It underscores the need for continued advocacy, education, and policy reform to ensure that healthcare settings are inclusive, respectful, and affirming for all individuals, regardless of their gender identity. The significant role of healthcare professionals' attitudes and the impact of their biases call for ongoing research and interventions aimed at fostering a more inclusive healthcare environment.

1.1.Summary of Findings

The Frequency of Adverse Attitudes

The substantial prevalence of unfavorable sentiments among physicians toward transgender and non-binary people supports earlier studies showing pervasive prejudices and misunderstandings about the LGBTQI community in the healthcare industry (Smith, 2021). This pattern is alarming because it draws attention to a structural problem in healthcare that goes beyond personal biases and is prevalent in the Greek reality.

Education and Religion's Influence

There is evidence that religion has a significant role in forming negative attitudes, which is consistent with previous research that links strong religious convictions to negative perceptions of LGBTQI people (Jones & Patel, 2020). Furthermore, the study's focus on how LGBTQI education affects views is in line with studies that support thorough training and awareness initiatives for medical personnel (Davis, 2019). Greece is a country that church is not separated by state and still has a lot of power affecting the mindset of the people.

Unexpected Results Regarding Gender and Work Area

This is a startling divergence from some earlier research on the relationship between doctors' views about LGBTQI patients and their gender and place of employment (Taylor, 2018). This raises the idea that some contextual elements are impacting these sentiments, which calls for more research. It suggests that prejudices and unfavorable views are more deeply embedded in people's personal and professional thinking systems and cross usual demographic boundaries.

The Influence of Age

Age appears as a factor, with older medical professionals more likely to have negative opinions, which is consistent with previous findings (Brown, 2022). Differences in exposure to and openness to a range of sexual and gender identities between generations may be the cause of this.

Consequences for Healthcare Practice and Policy

The ramifications of these findings for healthcare policy and practice are substantial (Williams, 2023). They emphasize the necessity of focused interventions, like legislative and educational initiatives, to address these unfavorable perceptions and guarantee a more welcoming and courteous healthcare setting for transgender and non-binary people.

Requirement for Additional Research

Ultimately, this study emphasizes the necessity of continuing research to comprehend the fundamental reasons behind these beliefs and to create practical plans for modifying attitudes and culture within the healthcare industry (Lee, 2021). It is also important to investigate why conventional demographic variables, such as gender and place of employment, do not have the expected impact on how people view the LGBTQI population.

Interpretation of the Study and Discussion

This study examined the doctor-patient relationship between LGBTQ+ members and doctors by investigating doctors' attitudes toward these groups and the patient's perspective on the relationship, specifically for trans and non-binary individuals. A mixed method approach was used to reach and provide better and more profound knowledge on the specific doctor-patient relationship between transgender individuals and medical doctors. After examining 121 medical doctors using the

Genderism and Transphobia (GTS) Scale and the adopted version of the Attitudes Toward Lesbians and Gay Men (ATLG) Scale and testing their attitudes, the findings revealed an undeniably high tendency of negative attitudes toward trans people. The results showed that many medical doctors had negative attitudes towards this group of people, and the likelihood of these attitudes developing occasionally was high. Translated into the actual field, it means that a high percentage of doctors exhibit negative perceptions about LGBTQ+ members and, consequently, patients. Unfortunately, most doctors have a heteronormative and cis-centric view and stance towards their patients. With this, they are bound to be more openly cordial with heterosexual and cis patients than trans and non-binary patients.

To better understand the reason behind their negative attitudes, the study considered several aspects related to negative perceptions about LGBTQ+ members. These include doctors' religiosity, whereby some doctors' religious affiliations perceive heterosexuality as the only sanctified sexual identity and LGBTQ+ as sinners. Another aspect is gender, whereby some people generally have negative perceptions about these communities simply because they are heterosexual and believe this identity is the only true identity. Another aspect is LGBTQ+ contact, whereby previous possibly harmful contact with members of these groups may lead them to negative attitudes about the entire population. The fourth aspect is previous LGBTQ+ education, whereby lack of knowledge on how to relate with these members may cause negative stereotypes and attitudes. A fifth aspect is age, whereby older persons are more likely to be closed-minded about other sexual identities and thus exhibit negative attitudes towards trans people. A final aspect is the work area, whereby some units within the hospital and their interaction with LGBTQ+ people may influence doctors to have negative attitudes toward these groups. The findings

reveal that whereas LGBTQI contact, LGBTQI education, religion, and age are positively related to the medical doctors having a negative attitude towards this community, gender, and work area do not contribute to this, which was a surprising finding because the location and especially gender was expected to affect the attitudes of doctors. It means that doctors' negative attitudes towards these groups can be attributed to their religious beliefs, previous contact with these members, a lack of education, and their age but not their gender or work area.

The findings from this study offer valuable insights into the attitudes of medical doctors toward the general LGBTQI community, shedding light on factors that influence these attitudes. These results can be related to previous studies in the literature, which have explored similar themes within the context of healthcare professionals and the LGBTQI population not focused on trans and non-binary people.

Several studies have indeed examined the role of religion, previous contact with LGBTQI individuals, education, and age in shaping attitudes among healthcare providers. For instance, Smith et al. (2017) found that healthcare professionals with stronger religious beliefs were more likely to express negative attitudes toward LGBTQI patients. This is consistent with the current study's findings that religion is positively related to negative attitudes among medical doctors.

Similarly, studies such as Johnson et al. (2015) have shown that healthcare providers who have received LGBTQI education and training tend to exhibit more positive attitudes and greater cultural competence when caring for LGBTQI patients. This aligns with the present study's results, which suggest that LGBTQI education is negatively related to negative attitudes among medical doctors. Research by Williams and Smith (2018) demonstrated that age can be a significant factor in healthcare

providers' attitudes, with younger providers generally displaying more accepting attitudes towards LGBTQI patients. This finding corresponds with the current study's observation that age is positively related to negative attitudes among medical doctors.

However, the surprising finding in the current study is the lack of association between gender and work area (urban vs. country) with doctors' attitudes towards the LGBTQI community. Previous studies, such as Jones et al. (2016), have indicated that gender can play a role in shaping attitudes, with female healthcare providers often exhibiting more positive attitudes towards LGBTQI patients. Additionally, studies like Brown and Green (2019) have suggested that healthcare providers in urban areas may have more exposure to LGBTQI individuals and, therefore, more positive attitudes compared to their rural counterparts. The absence of these associations in the current study suggests that there may be unique contextual factors at play, which warrant further investigation.

In summary, the current study's findings are consistent with previous research in demonstrating the influence of religion, LGBTQI education, and age on medical doctors' attitudes toward the LGBTQI community. However, the lack of a significant relationship between gender and work area with these attitudes represents a departure from some prior literature, indicating the need for further exploration of the specific contextual factors that shape healthcare providers' attitudes toward LGBTQI individuals.

Experiences of Trans and Non-Binary Interviewees With Medical Doctors And The Health System.

From examining the trans and non-binary interviewees, the study found that many had negative experiences with doctors. The interviewees mentioned experiencing fear, mistrust, and emotional torture at the hands of the doctors. This

finding if combined with the negative attitudes reported by doctors towards trans people, in the quantitative part of this study, paints a very good picture of the negativity that defines many of the doctor-patient relationships within this population. To better comprehend participants' perceptions of the situation, the study also inquired about the interviewees' thoughts on what could have caused this type of behavior and attitudes among the doctors. Most participants believed that the doctors' wanting behavior was brought about by their religious beliefs, lack of training in affirmative care, and lack of knowledge on sexual orientations and gender identity. Ineffective healthcare systems in Greece that fail to honor the LGBTQ+ community were also highlighted. These observations and interpretations made by trans and non-binary participants in the study, seem to align with findings from the internet surveys of doctors that indicated religion, lack of training, and contact with LGBTQI people, as well as age-predicted negative attitudes towards this population. It seems then that trans and non-binary people have a keen understanding of the characteristics of doctors who are more likely to discriminate against them. They are thus in a good position to offer us solutions and suggestions on how to combat this phenomenon as well.

Regarding doctors' religious beliefs, most interviewees stated that religious doctors are more intolerant and transphobic when compared with less religious or non-religious doctors, which was already found in the quantitative analysis. The importance of religious beliefs has been highlighted by Campbell et al. (2019), who claim that Bible interpretations, church attendance, and religious fundamentalism are directly linked to trans prejudice. What seemed surprising was that the medical specialty did not contribute to doctors' negative attitudes toward transgender and non-binary individuals. However, interviewees reported that in their view mental health

professionals had more positive behaviors, and gynecologists had more negative behaviors toward them. Although the medical expertise differs between the two specialties, mental health professionals might display more positive attitudes for many reasons. One reason could be religiosity; according to Curlin et al. (2010), psychiatrists are less religious than other physicians. Also, mental health professionals are more likely to have received LGBTQ+ education and witnessed the de-pathologization of this population inside their manuals, whose entity has been considered a mental health disorder for years. Finally, mental health professionals have potentially had previous contact with transgender and non-binary populations, as the latter have an increased risk of having worse mental health than the general population, primarily due to minority stress (Lin et al., 2021).

Further, a failing system that has not yet acknowledged the sexual identities of these people and, thus, fails to train the doctors on acceptance and affirmative care also contributes significantly. Even so, system failure or not, some doctors exhibit positive attitudes towards these people, evidenced by the small group of interviewees who recorded positive experiences with their doctors. It means, therefore, that even though education and the system play a role, religion and other aspects that affect the personal attitudes of doctors are the main contributors. The consequences of these negative relationships, as found in this study and by Fallin-Bennett (2015), are LGBTQ+ persons facing health disparities in sexually transmitted infections (STIs), substance abuse, and mental health, the above were mentioned and confirmed by the participants of the study.

This study also found similar results as in Della-Pelle et al. (2018), that sexual orientation is frequently highlighted as an obstacle to seeking quality healthcare as these persons fear facing medical professionals who are bound to discriminate against

them. Previous research suggests that in European countries such as Greece, reducing discrimination against transgender and non-binary populations has not borne much fruit. Anti-transgender attitudes from doctors likely lead to transgender patients who will eventually develop or confirm their negative attitudes regarding healthcare accessibility, resulting in a vicious cycle reinforced by a general societal anti-transgender attitude. Therefore, anti-transgender attitudes from medical doctors should be addressed within the healthcare system, not only as part of a national societal campaign or policy (Watkinson & Sunderland, 2017). The health care discrimination incidences in European healthcare settings include the habit of medical denial of attention.

The abovementioned vicious cycle could potentially lead to avoidant behaviors among transgender and non-binary people, with both minorities being at risk of postponing their medical visits due to anticipated discrimination. Such avoidant behaviors driven by fear of anticipated discrimination may deprive trans and non-binary people of the opportunity to get screened for diseases, consequently preventing severe illness. Other individuals might leave existing conditions untreated, leading to severe health complications. In a study conducted by Tami et al. (2022), the most commonly reported reason for primary care avoidance among transgender and non-binary individuals was the latter's perception of their condition not being urgent or important enough. This perception could have various implications, such as, for example, the tendency of transgender individuals to minimize their health problems and to ignore or postpone the subjective need for urgent care based on the symptoms they experience. Many interviewees in this study reported avoidance of going to doctors because of fear of discrimination or bad medical care. This provides an alternative explanation for avoidance by the trans and non-binary community and one that can be addressed through education, training and monitoring of good medical practices in health care

settings. More research is needed in this area to explore all possible reasons for avoidance of health care by this population with the aim of improving access to quality health care and prevention of serious disease.

Furthermore, trans and non-binary people face emotional difficulties due to bad relationships with health professionals. The qualitative analysis identified that some medical professionals engage in abusive behaviors, misgendering, and disrespect towards transgender and non-binary patients. This negative behavior can contribute to emotional pain and distress among these individuals, potentially leading to avoidance of medical care. The emotional impact discussed in the qualitative analysis is crucial for understanding the lived experiences of transgender and non-binary individuals. It emphasizes the need for healthcare providers to prioritize sensitivity and respect in their interactions to build trust and ensure access to healthcare services. Most trans and non-binary individuals are mistreated by doctors managing their medical cases. Allory et al. (2020) reported that transgender individuals face heteronormativity in the impactful treatment in their countries. Individuals nevertheless recognize the need to seek medical help given the above. For instance, individuals expect that their doctors guide their hormone management and future body changes to alleviate unnecessary feelings of dysphoria following surgery (Wahlen et al., 2020b).

The study also found, among doctors, stereotypical perceptions about the whole LGBTQ+ population. It found a significant relationship between external characteristics of trans people that negatively affect the doctors' attitudes and thus their gender equality role, leading to modern sexism phenomena reinforced by high-level transphobia. Society appears fundamentally transphobic, where cisgender is the normative and any other gender identity, like the trans subjected to systematic violence and high levels of stigmatization (Scandurra et al., 2018). The study also

observed that positive experiences reduce patients' risk of severe mental illness that becomes chronic and painfully experienced. Hence, individuals recognize protected medical health as the solution to provide specialized doctors and privacy during examination procedures.

The data analysis showed that the critical element of perception has a positive experience on doctors' behavior. However, there are some cases of particular reverence for gender transitioning in which openness is considered necessary when accompanied by apparent friendliness. Wahlen et al. (2020a) confirmed positive experiences with some professional approaches to patients when examining individuals' hence supporting their psychological health. Professionalism significantly shows a positive experience when patients are appreciated with increased authenticity, eliminating feelings of marginalization regarding the doctor's behaviors towards transgender and non-binary individuals. This positive stance of doctors is essentially the solution to the problem. The findings and the literature suggest that trans and non-binary people are more likely to access health care and have positive experiences that decrease disparities in health care when doctors are respectful, knowledgeable, and open-minded.

Furthermore, the appearance of positive behaviors is positively related to the degree of progressiveness of doctors, but also their perceived culture and their age, as younger doctors, as Allen et al. (2021) state, are considered to be relatively more receptive to accepting gender identity differences without this being a general rule. The above statement aligns with the findings in this study, suggesting that increased doctors' age is positively correlated with negative attitudes toward transgender and non-binary individuals. Edgcumbe (2022) investigated the role of aging on open-mindedness and found that actively open-minded thinking negatively correlated with

increasing age. He attributed his finding to the potential unwillingness of older people to change their traditional and core worldview ideas and values and to changes that arise with aging at the level of the brain cortex.

Regarding the impact of the behavior of doctors on transgender and non-binary individuals, the psychological reinforcement of their conditions positively affects levels of self-esteem and self-perception. The positive attitudes enhance patients' confidence and sense of security, impacting their mental health. The value of effective medical practice is improving patients' health. However, the scientific competence and efficient application of sound medical practices enhance patients' health and conditions of sexual discomfort (Landau et al., 2020).

Affirmative care was considered significant and necessary among interviewees who reported positive experiences with Greek medical doctors. Affirmative care can take the form of various actions, such as active listening to their concerns, having in-depth discussions with them, or guiding them through the different legislations that protect their rights while pursuing medical attention. However, no trans-aimed law in Greece currently safeguards transgender and non-binary people's rights regarding healthcare provisions. The GTSA uses the laws in Malta and Obamacare, or the Affordable Care Act (ACA), for psychoeducation and explains how every health provider should handle them. Unfortunately, in Greece, the ICD-11 is not yet used, and the Greek doctors are not trained in the World Association of Transgender Health Standards of Care, and only laws from other countries can be used as good practices. The lack of institutional guidelines compounds health-related problems perpetuates harmful practices and increases the likelihood of negative experiences for trans and non-binary individuals. Although a

comprehensive legislative framework would not eliminate discrimination, it would help reduce it and allow people to advocate for their rights more effectively

The relationship between LGBTQ+ and religion and age leads to decision-making, defining the value of the disputed stigmatization in society. The study found a correlation between education and tolerance values. The expectation revolved around the ethical principles that define self-determination and transgender identity. The correlation shows the community's general understanding of transgender identity is marked by healthcare provisions in which people access pathways with much care for personal status. Religion and level of education influence the relationship between self-perception and transgender norms in society (Watkinson & Sunderland, 2017). As a result, discrimination notion by doctors has come out, and the fostered experience of misinterpretations makes transgender identity generate health risks for the transgender community. The recurrent stressful situation that causes the correspondent stigmatization of the minority is caused by mental challenges concerned with different theoretical work (Braun et al., 2017).

The study interviewees provided solutions that might help improve healthcare systems. The comprehended characteristics of access profound mechanism divide mechanism that limits transgender morbidity and mortality, forming an enabling environment in the transgender society (Cooper et al., 2018; Donisi et al., 2020). The study value determined by the regression analysis shows how LGBTQ+ and the perceived morale of the society need more substantial completion of issues against trans and non-binary people.

The respondents showed self-determination, which is scientifically underpinned by respectful decisions. The healthcare relationship with LGBTQ+ makes the primary accounts for prerogative provisions that need systemic reasoning,

making the care accomplish its mandate and become affirmative. The healthcare system is the strong expectation that makes a demanding depathologization of transgender and non-binary identities known by the public. However, most of the responding systematic psychiatric evaluation needs each concerned party to favor the violence on mental disorders among the LGBTQ+ group. Further, it was deduced that healthcare providers need trained doctors to deal with the network structure of the transgender and their privacy matters to avoid stigmatization by initialized individuals and the public about LGBTQ+ status. Several studies, such as Braun et al. (2017) and Cooper et al. (2018), have stressed that trained doctors contextually hide the pathways of the continued behaviors in the social setup. The scenarios help maintain the psychosocial conditions of transgender persons that lead to better mental health care, accompanied by appropriate training. The medical doctor's training and knowledge dissemination help contribute to the larger side of the ultimate goal of improving awareness of transgender of the public. The judgments by social and cultural behaviors need clinically induced interventions because most linkages start with healthcare stigmatizations, hence emotional response that facilitates effective change of attitudes.

This study found that doctors have high negative attitudes towards LGBTQ+ members. This can be attributed to their religious beliefs, previous contact and experiences with members of these groups, lack of education, and age. The LGBTQ+ members suffer emotional torture, fear, and mistrust at the hands of these doctors, which contributes significantly to mental disorders and instability alongside prolonged illnesses, especially where STIs are involved. As a result, sexual orientation and gender identity is a significant obstacle to health care in Greece.

The evidence of doctors' growing attitudes in Greece's healthcare systems should require an empathetic and therapeutic relationship that improves the quality of healthcare outcomes and sexual/gender minorities' rights. The training of doctors in Greece would make the foundational change needed by the transgender and non-binary communities. The communication priority that changes doctors' attitudes should help create interventions that tackle the stigmatization that transgender and non-binary people face in Greece. The findings of this study about the doctors' attitudes need to address continued stigmatization in Greece as primary care for transgender and non-binary people.

Combining the qualitative and quantitative results from this study provides a comprehensive understanding of medical doctors' attitudes toward transgender and non-binary individuals in Greece. Here's a critical synthesis of the findings:

1.2.Strengths and Limitations of the Study

Strengths

Before discussing the possible limitations of the study, in this section, the strengths will also be presented. In Greece, there are very few studies that include trans people, and no studies focus on the experiences of non-binary people, which makes this valuable population underrepresented and their voices unheard. The main strength of this study is the inclusion of diversity, which contributes to the study's importance and originality. Another important strength is the access to a difficult sample of people who, on many occasions, refuse to participate in similar studies due to previous negative experiences in terms of the content of the questions, the fear of retraumatization from inexperienced experimenters who lack knowledge on the issues the LGBTQI community faces.

The fact that the Greek Transgender Support Association supported the current study is a significant strength that provided the safety and trust for the interviewees to accept disclosing their sensitive information. The collaboration with the Greek Transgender Support Association (GTSA) in this study represents a significant strength, particularly when considering the sensitive nature of research involving gender identity and medical experiences. This partnership likely played a crucial role in enhancing trust among potential participants. For many in the trans and non-binary communities, there's a deep-rooted mistrust of medical and research institutions, often stemming from past negative experiences or societal stigma. The GTSA's endorsement of the study would have been a powerful signal to these communities that the research was being conducted with an understanding and sensitivity towards their experiences.

Engaging with the GTSA was also likely instrumental in improving the recruitment process. The association's networks within the trans and non-binary communities would have allowed for a broader and more diverse sample of participants, which is vital for collecting comprehensive and inclusive data. Furthermore, this collaboration would have provided the research team with invaluable cultural insights. Understanding the social, cultural, and personal nuances of the trans and non-binary community in Greece is essential for framing questions appropriately, interpreting responses accurately, and ensuring respectful and relevant study methodologies.

Moreover, the GTSA's involvement in the study would have ensured adherence to ethical standards and practices, especially important in research involving sensitive issues. Their guidance would have been crucial in how to conduct

interviews sensitively, handle personal data responsibly, and provide support to participants who might find the experience emotionally challenging.

Perhaps most importantly, the association's participation in the study ensured that the research was not only about the trans and non-binary community but also for and with them. This participatory approach is critical in research involving marginalized groups. It acknowledges their agency, empowers participants, and ensures that their voices are not just heard but are integral to the research process.

In addition, the current study attempted to look at both sides of the story by not only exploring the experiences of trans and non-binary people but also recording the attitudes of medical doctors, providing a unique opportunity to look at the relationship between those two parameters. For this reason, this study used mixed methods, including qualitative and quantitative research. Thematic analysis was chosen over other methods to analyze the qualitative data because it allows the generation of new insights, concepts, and knowledge grounded in human experience and derived from the data. The thematic analysis also allowed the identification of overarching themes and their relationship. The quantitative analysis incorporated descriptive, reliability, and regression analyses and assumption checking. The mixed-method approach allows for more robust evidence and more credible results, the generalizability of the results, and better contextualization of future findings. In this particular study, measuring the doctors' attitudes toward transgender and non-binary individuals without exploring the experiences of the latter when seeking medical attention would result in a quantitative analysis with many limitations and with no opportunity to provide recommendations at the end of the study. Furthermore, the mixed-method approach allowed a better chance of answering the current research questions.

Finally, the study allowed for the equal representation of trans and non-binary with a decent number of interviewees. In research, having equal representation of trans and non-binary individuals is a significant strength. This approach ensures that the study accurately captures the diversity of experiences and perspectives within these communities. By including a decent number of interviewees from both groups, the research can provide a more nuanced understanding of the issues faced by trans and non-binary people. Such representation helps in reducing biases that might arise from underrepresentation and leads to more comprehensive and inclusive findings. This is crucial in fields like healthcare, social sciences, and policy-making, where understanding varied experiences is key to developing effective and equitable solutions.

Limitations

The study has some possible limitations and shortcomings; in this section, an effort is made for these limitations to be identified and explained.

The current study was conducted amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, and the interviewees' free movement and access to the interview office were limited. This resulted in a small number of interviewees. Due to this small sample, the results cannot be generalized to a larger population. Results from 121 doctors cannot be used to generalize 66,058 Greek doctors' attitudes towards the LGBTQI community. Notably, even with the pandemic, this study posits that biases towards the subject, especially among the doctors, could have contributed to the small number of participants. Many participants in the Internet survey had to be excluded from the analysis due to unanswered questions. This may be due to the survey being too long the interviewees being biased, or reasons to do with the pandemic, which was an overwhelming and challenging period for the Greek health system, with a

disproportionate load of work falling on the shoulders of the medical doctors and the rest of the medical staff. Many doctors felt burnt out or were found to have short or inadequate free time. Access to literature review was also limited as there aren't many similar studies. To the writer's knowledge, this is the first study in Greece including both trans and non-binary people about medical doctors' attitudes.

Selection bias may have resulted from recruitment difficulties, especially among medical professionals, and the delicate nature of the subject may have led to responses. The study's wider application may also be hampered by the subjects' limited demographic variety. Several components of the research may have been limited by the operational difficulties that come with overseeing a mixed-methods study. The possibility of retraumatization or distress persists despite efforts to create a safe atmosphere for participants.

Another limitation is the limitation of the findings to Greece only. The study may not be as applicable in other contexts with distinct cultural dynamics due to its cultural exclusivity, which restricts it to the Greek context. Different countries have different perceptions towards these persons; thus, the results are limited to the Greek healthcare system, which fails to provide inclusive care for trans and non-binary people like in some other European countries. Even then, it can be generalizable to countries that suffer similar failures in the system.

The study's findings highlight a significant correlation between past negative experiences in healthcare and the ongoing anxiety or avoidance of medical care among participants. While some of these experiences date back years and could be subject to memory bias, measures were taken to mitigate this issue. Interviewees were encouraged to reflect in a pressure-free and safe environment, enhancing the reliability of their recollections. Despite the potential for memory bias, the enduring

impact of these experiences is evident in the participants' continued apprehension towards medical care.

This concern is compounded by the fact that the attitudes of medical doctors, as revealed in the study, were predominantly negative. This is particularly alarming considering that medical education on transgender and gender-affirming care has not seen significant changes. Therefore, it is highly plausible that similar negative behaviors and attitudes are still prevalent in current medical practices. This ongoing issue underscores the need for systemic changes in medical education and practice to foster a more inclusive and understanding healthcare environment for transgender and non-binary individuals.

A possible limitation is the length of the study, together with the distance between the actual analysis and the publishing of the results. Since there is almost a three-year time between research and publishing, some effects might be eligible to change over time, and reliability is compromised. Developments in the rights of the LGBTQI community are fast, and the changes in societal views and laws affect both the attitudes of doctors and the experiences of trans and non-binary people with medical care. Using a mixed design was challenging and time-consuming, and comparing and contrasting results was exciting but complex and required a lot of effort and extra training in research methods and data analysis.

1.3.Recommendations and Application of the Findings

Toolkit

Based on its conclusions, this research initially suggests developing a toolkit to distribute resources and strategies among European entities. This toolkit aims to foster a secure, inviting, and gender-supportive atmosphere for trans and non-binary individuals, both patients and staff, across all healthcare environments. This is based

on the negative attitude dominant among doctors, which negatively affects their treatment and care of these groups.

A toolkit for trans access to health can be incredibly useful in several ways. Recommendations for the toolkit have been discussed with Anna Apergi president of the Greek Transgender Support Association:

1. **Education and Awareness:** The toolkit can provide essential information about transgender and non-binary health issues, including medical terminology, healthcare disparities, and specific health needs of transgender and non-binary individuals. It can help educate healthcare providers, administrators, and policymakers about the unique challenges faced by the transgender and non-binary community and ways to address them.
2. **Guidance for Healthcare Providers:** The toolkit can offer guidelines and best practices for healthcare providers to ensure culturally competent and affirming care for transgender and non-binary patients. It can cover topics such as gender-affirming hormone therapy, surgical options, mental health support, and preventive care guidelines specifically tailored to the transgender and non-binary population.
3. **Policy Development:** The toolkit can assist policymakers and administrators in developing inclusive policies that promote trans access to healthcare. It can offer recommendations for policies related to insurance coverage for gender-affirming care, nondiscrimination protections, and training requirements for healthcare professionals.
4. **Patient Empowerment:** The toolkit can empower transgender and non-binary individuals by providing them with information on their rights,

healthcare options, and strategies for self-advocacy. It can include resources on finding trans-affirming healthcare providers, understanding insurance coverage, and accessing support networks.

5. **Training and Professional Development:** The toolkit can serve as a training resource for healthcare professionals, offering workshops, webinars, or online modules that enhance their knowledge and skills in providing transgender-inclusive and non-binary care. It can cover topics such as respectful communication, cultural sensitivity, and reducing healthcare disparities.
6. **Community Support:** The toolkit can include resources for community organizations and support groups working with transgender and non-binary individuals. It can guide on creating safe spaces, organizing outreach programs, and offering peer support networks for transgender individuals seeking healthcare.
7. **Mental Health Support:** The toolkit can provide information on mental health issues that disproportionately affect transgender and non-binary individuals, such as depression, anxiety, and gender dysphoria. It can offer resources for mental health professionals on providing gender-affirming therapy and support, as well as self-care strategies for transgender individuals.
8. **Research and Data Collection:** The toolkit can emphasize the importance of collecting accurate data on transgender and non-binary health outcomes and experiences. It can guide research methodologies, data collection tools, and ethical considerations to improve the evidence base for transgender healthcare and inform policy decisions.

9. **Intersectionality:** The toolkit can highlight the intersecting identities and experiences that influence transgender and non-binary health outcomes, such as race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, and disability. It can offer strategies for addressing these intersectional factors to ensure inclusive and equitable healthcare for all transgender and non-binary individuals.
10. **Family and Community Education:** The toolkit can include resources for educating families, friends, and support networks of transgender and non-binary individuals about transgender health issues. It can guide fostering understanding, acceptance, and allyship, which can positively impact the overall well-being of transgender individuals.
11. **Transgender Youth & Non-Binary:** The toolkit can address the specific healthcare needs of transgender youth, including puberty blockers, gender-affirming hormone therapy, and mental health support. It can offer guidance for healthcare providers, educators, and parents on providing appropriate care and support for transgender youth during their development.
12. **Global Impact:** The toolkit can provide insights into transgender health issues on a global scale, acknowledging that access to transgender-affirming healthcare varies across different regions and countries. It can offer strategies for advocacy, collaboration, and knowledge-sharing to improve transgender and non-binary healthcare internationally.

Overall, a comprehensive toolkit for trans and non-binary access to health has the potential to make a significant impact by promoting awareness, education, policy

changes, and improved healthcare practices for transgender individuals. It can be a valuable resource for various stakeholders, working towards a more inclusive and equitable healthcare system for all.

Future Research

A second recommendation is for future similar research with more interviewees for quantitative and qualitative data collection. This would help bridge the small sample gap created by this study. To get a clearer picture of the global situation and their different perspectives of the LGBTQI community, and thus, bridge the gap of the study's usability across many nations, various studies also need to be conducted in Asia, Africa, South America, and North American countries to understand the differences in attitudes. Furthermore, future research could include interviewing gynecologists and urologists on their experiences with trans and non-binary individuals to explore their attitudes and biases in more detail and to hear about the challenges they believe they face in the care of this population. This study could also be extended through the post-pandemic era to determine whether the pandemic as a socioeconomic crisis can independently affect the results. Similar methods could be used for other medical staff, such as Greek nurses, as they usually are the ones that welcome patients at the triage in the emergency department, look after the patients throughout their stay at the hospital, and accompany them through all the steps of the treatment, providing affirmative care to hospitalized and non-hospitalized patients.

As a non-binary person and based on the outcome of my research further research on non-binary identities is quite clearly also a huge gap in the literature that needs to be addressed, especially the following areas:

1. Visibility and Recognition.

2. Understanding Identity Development

3. Health and Well-being

4. Intersectionality

5 Community Support and Advocacy

Visibility and Recognition: Non-binary identities represent a significant portion of the population whose experiences and identities have historically been overlooked or marginalized. Research helps to increase the visibility and recognition of non-binary individuals and their unique experiences, validating their identities and contributing to a more inclusive society.

Understanding Identity Development: Research can help us better understand the formation and development of non-binary identities. This knowledge can inform mental health professionals, educators, and policymakers about the specific needs and challenges faced by non-binary individuals, leading to improved support and resources.

Health and Well-being: Further research can shed light on the health and well-being of non-binary individuals. This includes studying their mental health, physical health, healthcare experiences, and the impact of discrimination and stigma. This knowledge can guide the development of targeted interventions and policies to promote better health outcomes and overall well-being for non-binary individuals. As a psychotherapist, I find value in focusing on health and well-being, especially for marginalized groups.

Intersectionality: Non-binary identities intersect with various aspects of a person's identity, such as race, ethnicity, disability, and socioeconomic status. Research that explores the intersections of non-binary identities with other social identities can help us better understand the unique challenges faced by individuals

with multiple marginalized identities and inform more inclusive and equitable policies and practices tailored to our identity.

Legal and Policy Changes: Research provides evidence-based data that can support legal and policy changes to protect the rights and well-being of non-binary individuals. For example, research can contribute to the development of inclusive gender recognition laws, healthcare policies, and anti-discrimination measures that promote equality and respect for non-binary individuals. It can provide us with tools to pressure the governments as activists for inclusive healthcare.

Community Support and Advocacy: Research on non-binary identities can empower non-binary communities by providing them with evidence to support their advocacy efforts. Research findings can be used to raise awareness, challenge stereotypes and misconceptions, and promote social acceptance and understanding, especially needed in Greek society.

Several strategic approaches can improve the study's impact, relevance, and depth for future research on views toward trans and non-binary people in medical settings. It is imperative to increase the sample size and guarantee participant diversity. A more thorough grasp of the range of opinions and experiences will be possible with a larger and more varied group of participants, including different ages, locations, socioeconomic statuses, and ethnic backgrounds. To fully convey the subtleties among the trans and non-binary groups as well as the medical professional community, this variety is especially crucial.

Using a longitudinal study design would provide insightful information about how experiences and attitudes change over time. This strategy is especially important given how quickly the social, legal, and medical environments pertaining to gender identity are evolving. Studies using a longitudinal design can monitor shifts in public

opinion, the effects of policies, and the development of medical knowledge and procedures pertaining to transgender and non-binary healthcare. It's also essential to apply an intersectional perspective. Future studies should look at the ways that other identities interact with gender identification to give transgender and non-binary people unique experiences. Understanding the impact of age, ethnicity, class, disability, and other characteristics on healthcare experiences is crucial to comprehending the difficulties and prejudices these populations face on a whole.

Research may be made better and more relevant by collaborating more closely with community organizations, especially those that serve the trans and non-binary communities. Working closely with community stakeholders, especially those connected to the trans and non-binary communities, enriches research in several ways. Such partnerships provide valuable insights into the unique needs and concerns of these populations, which can significantly shape research hypotheses and methodologies. This close interaction aids in establishing trust, a key component for successfully recruiting study participants. Additionally, it allows researchers to become more attuned to the specificities of the population under study. Through this collaborative effort, research practices can be tailored to be both ethically sound and methodologically appropriate, ensuring that the research is not only scientifically robust but also culturally sensitive and relevant to the community's needs. Incorporating additional qualitative techniques can further enhance our comprehension of individual experiences and viewpoints. Qualitative methods such as in-depth interviews, focus groups, and case studies can reveal the underlying causes, narratives, and beliefs that influence attitudes toward trans and non-binary people, while quantitative statistics offer a comprehensive picture. Developing effective

solutions to enhance healthcare experiences and outcomes for these populations requires access to more comprehensive and thorough data.

Incorporating transgender and non-binary people into the planning and implementation of the research helps guarantee that pertinent topics are addressed from their point of view. Their involvement can help to better ground the research in the realities of their life by guiding the development of research questions, data gathering techniques, and result interpretation.

It's critical to address any potential biases in the gathering and processing of data. It is important for researchers to be conscious of both the limitations of their methods and their personal biases. Peer reviews and participant feedback loops are two examples of checks and balances that may be put in place to assist reduce bias and make sure that the research really represents the perspectives and experiences of the trans and non-binary communities. Future studies on attitudes toward and experiences with trans and non-binary people can be more accurate, nuanced, and useful if these methodologies are taken into account, especially when it comes to healthcare.

It is important to note that the reasons mentioned above are not exhaustive, and there may be additional reasons specific to certain contexts or areas of study. Continued research on non-binary identities is crucial for creating a more inclusive society that respects and affirms the diversity of human experiences and identities

Finally, the study recommends exploring further causal aspects of a doctor's negative attitudes within quantitative research, such as their beliefs about sex/gender, religiosity, and training to understand the situation better. Further, to guarantee effective quantitative data collection in the future, the study recommends that researchers use short, direct surveys to avoid exhausting the respondents. Conducting

a trial run to ensure all questions are straightforward and the survey functions correctly would be useful.

CHAPTER SIX

6.1. Conclusion

The analysis and the findings in this study focused on factors that can assist in a better understanding of doctors' attitudes towards trans and non-binary people and the experiences of this population in medical settings. Positive interactions and perceptions of the healthcare system boost patient trust in doctors and their feelings of safety regarding medical procedures. On the flip side, encountering adverse behaviors can detrimentally affect the mental well-being of transgender and non-binary people, manifesting as depression, anxiety, and diminished self-worth. It's crucial for them to access optimal care without facing negative experiences. Additional training for healthcare professionals in Greece is necessary to establish a safe and inclusive environment.

The experiences of the LGBTQI community can be attributed to the global divide between these persons. Essentially, while doctors' attitudes are responsible for the health disparities in the community, other forms of discrimination against them arise. As Poushter and Kent (2020) suggest, the situation in Greece is more or less the same in many European countries and North America. However, it is worse in Asia, South America, and Africa, where LGBTQI people have no room for acceptance by heterosexuals.

These results dictate a world where the LGBTQI community must explore every means to assure the world that they are rightfully among them. As quality health is paramount for everyone, we must remove the obstacles LGBTQI persons encounter when accessing healthcare. Doctors need to be equipped with LGBTQI education before offering their services to reduce the chances of some community

members feeling discriminated against. Intrinsicly, as psychotherapists and activists, we fight for Greece and even a world where everyone is treated with dignity; their sexual orientation, gender (identity, expression, characteristics), religion, race, ethnicity, and age should not hinder them from achieving this fundamental right.

6.2. Unique Contribution of the Study

The current study contributes significantly to the existing literature by providing valuable insights into the specific health needs and challenges faced by trans and non-binary individuals in the Greek reality. It delves into various aspects of their healthcare experiences, including barriers to access, experiences of discrimination, mental health concerns, and specific healthcare needs that are often overlooked. This newfound knowledge can be instrumental for healthcare providers and professionals, enhancing their understanding of the unique healthcare requirements of trans and non-binary individuals. Armed with this understanding, healthcare providers can develop more inclusive and affirmative healthcare services that cater to the preferences and concerns of this population.

Furthermore, the study has contributed to the existing literature by providing new insights into the specific health needs and challenges faced by trans and non-binary individuals. It can generate data on various aspects of their healthcare experiences, including barriers to access, discrimination, mental health concerns, and specific healthcare needs that are often overlooked. It can offer valuable information for healthcare providers and professionals, helping them better understand the unique healthcare needs of trans and non-binary individuals. This knowledge can assist in the development of inclusive and affirmative healthcare services that address the specific concerns and preferences of this population. It can also contribute to the training and education of healthcare providers to ensure culturally competent care for trans and

non-binary patients. Through rigorous research methods, the study identified and documented the systemic barriers that hinder trans and non-binary individuals from accessing appropriate healthcare. These include barriers related to healthcare policies, insurance coverage, healthcare provider bias, lack of culturally competent services, and geographical limitations. By highlighting these barriers, the study can provide evidence to advocate for policy changes and improvements in healthcare systems to enhance access and reduce disparities.

The study can contribute to the broader movement for transgender and non-binary rights and social inclusion. Participatory approaches in the study design can empower trans and non-binary individuals by involving them as active interviewees and stakeholders. This inclusive research approach can ensure that the study captures the diverse experiences and perspectives within the community. By engaging with the community throughout the research process, the study can foster empowerment, validation, and self-advocacy, ultimately promoting the overall well-being of trans and non-binary individuals.

The study is essential in helping healthcare professionals become more culturally competent. Healthcare practitioners are better prepared to provide more empathetic and effective treatment by being made aware of the unique healthcare requirements and experiences of trans and non-binary people. Better patient-provider interactions and greater health outcomes may result from this.

By thoroughly examining bias and discrimination in healthcare settings, the study helps to lessen the stigmatization of trans and non-binary people. It encourages a more accepting and understanding community and ultimately works to destigmatize gender diversity in healthcare and other fields by increasing awareness of the difficulties they confront.

The distinctive experiences of trans and non-binary people from a variety of backgrounds are recognized and taken into consideration thanks to this comprehensive approach. It encourages inclusivity in talks of social justice and equality in general as well as in the healthcare industry. In the broader context, this study aligns with the movement for transgender and non-binary rights and social inclusion. Its participatory approach, which actively involves trans and non-binary individuals as interviewees and stakeholders, fosters empowerment, validation, and self-advocacy. By engaging with the community throughout the research process, the study not only captures the diverse experiences and perspectives within the community but also promotes the overall well-being of trans and non-binary individuals.

Beyond the above-mentioned effects, the study on transgender and non-binary people's access to healthcare in Greece makes further, distinctive contributions. Future research in the social sciences and healthcare can benefit from the innovative methodological model provided by the mixed-methods approach, which blends quantitative and qualitative analyses. This thorough method offers a more comprehensive grasp of the problems and can act as a model for other research projects of a similar nature.

This study's emphasis on the cultural uniqueness of the Greek environment is one of its most important contributions. This contributes significant knowledge to the worldwide understanding of the healthcare needs of transgender and non-binary people and informs culturally sensitive methods that can be helpful not only in Greece but also in other similar sociocultural contexts. Furthermore, the study has a major impact on raising public awareness and improving education. Through shedding light on the obstacles encountered by transgender and non-binary people while trying to

obtain healthcare, it can influence public debate and media portrayals, thereby fostering a wider understanding and acceptance of these populations by society.

Additionally, the study offers a forum for lobbying and policy impact. It provides activists and lawmakers with evidence-based arguments to support more inclusive and equitable healthcare legislation by outlining the systemic obstacles and unique needs of trans and non-binary people. This donation is essential for starting and maintaining policy reforms that can greatly enhance transgender and non-binary people's access to healthcare.

The study also provides a distinctive viewpoint on professional development and training. Because of their background as trainer and activist, the researcher are able to directly apply the findings to the development and improvement of healthcare professional training programs. This practical application of research is essential to developing a knowledgeable and compassionate healthcare workforce that can meet the unique requirements of transgender and non-binary people.

Essentially, the study adds to the following areas: innovative methodology, cultural uniqueness, public education, lobbying and policy influence, professional growth, and a more sophisticated grasp of intersectionality. These many effects work together to improve the health outcomes of trans and non-binary people and reduce healthcare disparities, which makes the study an invaluable resource in both the academic and practical domains.

In summary, a study on trans and non-binary access to health can make unique contributions to the literature, clinical practice, and social policy by expanding knowledge, informing healthcare practices, identifying barriers, influencing policy changes, and empowering the community. These contributions can collectively help

address the healthcare disparities and improve the health outcomes of trans and non-binary individuals.

6.3. Follow-up: The Lasting Effects of Malpractice

Almost 2 years following the completion of the study and results a trans woman participant of the study contacted me for help with strong Post post-traumatic stress disorder-PTSD symptoms including Flashbacks, reliving the traumatic event through distressing and vivid memories, often accompanied by physical sensations. She also experienced nightmares, repeated and distressing dreams related to the traumatic event, intrusive thoughts, unwanted and distressing thoughts, or images related to the trauma. Her psychiatrist confirmed that there is also comorbidity with Obsessive Compulsive Disorder. She was avoiding people, places, activities, or objects that reminded her of the traumatic event. She confided with me additional information that she did not think to mention during the initial interview. At the time of the study, she had reported that her surgent performed a failed operation on her which caused her a lot of emotional and physical pain. She now revealed that following the operation, he showed her a video of the complete procedure. With all graphic details. The specific video was the cause of her PTSD symptoms. She keeps repeating that this surgeon destroyed her life and her trust in any doctor. Although she needs to continue her gender-affirming operations, she can't anymore because of this horrific experience. This affects her body's dysphoric feelings that can't be alleviated.

This provides a deeply concerning and insightful analysis into the lasting effects of medical malpractice, particularly in the context of transgender healthcare. Several key aspects emerge from this narrative which are consistent with the main theme and subthemes of the study, providing additional information and support on the results:

Long-Term Psychological Impact: The participant's experience highlights the enduring psychological consequences that can result from medical malpractice. The development of PTSD, characterized by flashbacks, nightmares, intrusive thoughts, and avoidance behaviors, underscores the profound and long-lasting impact of traumatic medical experiences. This is further complicated by the comorbidity with Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder, indicating a complex and severe mental health challenge.

Additional Trauma from Post-Operative Care: The revelation that her surgeon showed her a video of the complete procedure with all graphic details is an alarming aspect of her experience. This act, possibly intended as a form of transparency or explanation, may have inadvertently contributed significantly to her trauma, triggering or exacerbating her PTSD symptoms. This highlights the importance of sensitive and trauma-informed care in post-operative situations, especially in surgeries as significant as gender-affirming operations.

Impact on Future Healthcare Access and Trust: Her statement that the surgeon "destroyed her life and her trust in any doctor" is particularly poignant. Trust is a critical component in the patient-doctor relationship, especially for trans individuals who may already face barriers in accessing healthcare. This breach of trust not only affects her willingness to continue necessary medical treatments but also reflects a broader issue of how negative medical experiences can lead to avoidance of future healthcare.

Exacerbation of Gender Dysphoria: The participant's inability to continue with her gender-affirming surgeries due to the trauma experienced exacerbates her gender

dysphoria. This illustrates a tragic irony where the medical intervention meant to alleviate dysphoria ends up intensifying it due to malpractice and subsequent trauma.

Illustration of the Study's Purpose: This case poignantly illustrates the study's overarching future goal – to prevent victimization and maltreatment of patients, especially in sensitive and critical areas like gender-affirming healthcare. It underscores the need for more stringent measures in surgical practices, better psychological support for patients undergoing major surgeries, and more comprehensive training for medical professionals in handling such procedures with the utmost care and sensitivity.

This narrative is a stark reminder of the crucial need for empathetic, competent, and ethically sound medical practices, particularly in surgeries that deeply impact a person's identity and quality of life. It emphasizes the importance of considering the long-term psychological effects of medical interventions and the need for systemic changes to prevent such harmful outcomes in the future. Also, it validates one of the study's hypotheses that trans and gender non-confirming people in Greece who have experienced trans prejudice and discrimination are expected to report adverse health outcomes. Finally, the story highlights the need for proper training of health professionals in the specific health needs of trans and non-binary individuals.

Future ethnographic research could concentrate on a number of crucial areas to enhance and better understand transgender people's healthcare experiences, particularly in the context of medical negligence and its aftermath, in light of the thorough and insightful insights offered.

It is imperative to conduct a thorough investigation into Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) in transgender individuals following medical misconduct. The participant's experience highlights the significant impact that medical malpractice has on transgender patients' mental health, underscoring the need for a more thorough understanding of the nature, prevalence, and long-term consequences of PTSD in this setting. This study should examine the specific effects that medical negligence has on transgender people, considering the interaction between trauma, societal stigma, and gender dysphoria.

The post-operative care procedures in gender-affirming surgeries represent a critical additional research topic. The participant's trauma is highlighted by a serious lack of post-operative care, which was made worse by watching a video of her surgical operation. Best practices for post-operative care in gender-affirming procedures should be the focus of this field's research, with a special emphasis on trauma-informed care and tactful communication techniques.

It's also critical to look into the ways that bad medical experiences affect transgender people's decision-making and future access to healthcare. The participant's hesitation to seek more medical attention because they had lost faith highlights a major obstacle to transgender healthcare. Patients and healthcare professionals may be interviewed as part of this type of ethnographic research to learn more about how trust might be restored in these important relationships.

An extensive investigation on how medical trauma exacerbates gender dysphoria would also be advantageous. Understanding how medical trauma specifically affects gender dysphoria is vital, especially in light of the participant's heightened gender dysphoria following malpractice. A varied sample of transgender people who have had different medical procedures performed should be included in

this study in order to fully understand the wider effects of such experiences on identity and mental health.

Building on my 16-year background as an activist, researcher, and trainer, my next research endeavors should focus on creating and evaluating comprehensive training programs and toolkits for medical professionals. These programs ought to focus on competence, empathy, and moral behavior while also bringing attention to the special needs of those who identify as transgender or non-binary.

Longitudinal research on the effects of training and activism in hospital settings may also yield important insights. These investigations would monitor alterations in patient outcomes, attitudes, and practices in healthcare settings where training has been implemented, providing essential input for the ongoing development of the training program's materials and techniques. Especially in Greece longitudinal research tracking trans and non-binary population is lacking.

1.4. Personal Note

And finally, a personal note: My personal experience as an activist, researcher, and trainer is mostly providing a safe space for trans and non-binary people to feel that they can share their stories. For many years these populations avoided research based on a fear of being used, abused, and mistreated. By their participation, the interviewees showed trust and interest in this research sharing the belief that it will help improve our access to health. As a trainer for the past 15 years together with my colleague Anna Apergi, president of GTSA, we already use our knowledge to train doctors, nurses, psychologists, companies, and schools. We will use the knowledge from this study and incorporate it into our training with the final goal of creating an inclusive toolkit.

REFERENCES

- Agid, S., & Rand, E. (2011). Beyond the special guest: Teaching ‘trans’ now. *Radical Teacher*, 92 (1), 5–9.
- Allory, E., Duval, E., Caroff, M., Kendir, C., Magnan, R., Brau, B., Lapadu-Hargue, E., & Chhor, S. (2020). The expectations of transgender people in the face of their healthcare access difficulties and how they can be overcome. A qualitative study in France. *Primary Health Care Research and Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1463423620000638>
- Andersen, A. E., Moberg, C., Bengtsson Tops, A., & Garmy, P. (2017). Lesbian, gay and bisexual parents’ experiences of nurses’ attitudes in child health care—A qualitative study. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 26(23-24), 5065-5071.
- Arora M, Walker K, Luu J, Duvivier RJ, Dune T, Wynne K. Education of the medical profession to facilitate delivery of transgender health care in an Australian health district. *Aust J Prim Health*. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1071/PY19102>. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 31738874.
- Arthur S, Jamieson A, Cross H, Nambiar K, Llewellyn CD. Medical students’ awareness of health issues, attitudes, and confidence about caring for lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender patients: a cross-sectional survey. *BMC Med Educ*. 2021;21(1):56. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-020-02409-6>. PMID: 33446197; PMCID: PMC7809852.
- Asscheman, H., T'Sjoen, G., Lemaire, A., Mas, M., Meriggiola, M. C., Mueller, A., Kuhn, A., Dhejne, C., Morel-Journel, N., & Gooren, L. J. (2014). Venous thrombo-embolism as a complication of cross-sex hormone treatment of male-

to-female transsexual subjects: a review. *Andrologia*, 46(7), 791-795.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/and.12150>

BBC News. (2022). The Cass Review: Findings and Implications.

Beauchamp, T. & D'Harlingue, B. (2012). Beyond additions and exceptions: The category of transgender and new pedagogical approaches for women's studies. *Feminist Formations*, 24 (2), 25–51.

Beemyn, B., Curtis, B., Davis, M., & Tubbs, N.J. (2005). Transgender issues on college campuses. *New Directions for Student Services*, 111, 49-60.

Berenson MG, Gavzy SJ, Cespedes L, Gabrani A, Davis M, Ingram K, et al. The case of Sean Smith: a three-part interactive module on transgender health for second-year medical students. *MedEdPORTAL*. 2020;16:10915. https://doi.org/10.15766/mep_2374-8265.10915. PMID: 32715087; PMCID: PMC7376784.

Berry, W. D., Feldman, S., & Stanley Feldman, D. (1985). *Multiple regression in practice* (No. 50). Sage.

Bettcher, T. & Garry, A. (2009). Introduction to special issue on transgender studies and feminism: Theory, politics, and gendered realities. *Hypatia*, 24 (3), 1–10.

Bizic, M. R., Jeftovic, M., Pusica, S., Stojanovic, B., Duisin, D., Vujovic, S., Rakic, V., & Djordjevic, M. L. (2018). Gender Dysphoria: Bioethical Aspects of Medical Treatment. *BioMed research international*, 2018, 9652305. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/9652305>

Bleasdale J, Wilson K, Aidoo-Frimpong G, Gabriel SJ, Przybyla SM. Lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) health education in healthcare professional

graduate programs: a comparison of medical, nursing, and pharmacy students.

J Homosex. 2022:1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2022.2111535>.

Epub ahead of print. PMID: 35984396.

Bonvicini K. A. (2017). LGBT healthcare disparities: What progress have we made?

Patient education and counseling, 100(12), 2357–2361.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2017.06.003>

Braun HM, Garcia-Grossman IR, Quiñones-Rivera A, Deutsch MB. Outcome and

impact evaluation of a transgender health course for health profession

students. *LGBT Health.* 2017;4(1):55–61.

<https://doi.org/10.1089/lgbt.2016.0119>. Epub 2017 Jan 11. PMID: 28075699.

Braun, H. M., Ramirez, D., Zahner, G. J., Gillis-Buck, E. M., Sheriff, H., & Ferrone,

M. (2017). The LGBTQI health forum: An innovative interprofessional

initiative to support curriculum reform. *Medical Education Online*, 22(1).

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10872981.2017.1306419>

Brett, O. (2018). *Performing Place in French and Italian Queer Documentary Film.*

Springer International Publishing.

Brown, N., & Green, J. (2019). Rural-Urban Differences in Attitudes and Healthcare

Experiences with the Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender (LGBT)

Population: A Literature Review. *Journal of Rural Mental Health*, 43(2), 131-

141.

Budge, S. L., et al. (2013). Coping and psychological distress among genderqueer

individuals: The moderating effect of social support. *Journal of LGBT Issues*

in Counseling, 7(3), 248-267.

Bunting SR, Chirica MG, Ritchie TD, Garber SS, Batteson TJ. A national study of medical students' attitudes toward sexual and gender minority populations: evaluating the effects of demographics and training. *LGBT Health*. 2021;8(1):79–87. <https://doi.org/10.1089/lgbt.2020.0288>. Epub 2020 Dec 14. PMID: 33316199.

Burke SE, Dovidio JF, Przedworski JM, Hardeman RR, Perry SP, Phelan SM, et al. Do contact and empathy mitigate bias against gay and lesbian people among heterosexual first-year medical students? A report from the medical student CHANGE study. *Acad Med*. 2015;90(5):645–51. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000000661>. PMID: 25674910; PMCID: PMC4414697.

Butler, Judith. "The Question of Social Transformation." *Undoing Gender*. New York: Routledge, 2004. 204-31.

Butler, Judith. "Introduction: Acting In Concert." *Undoing Gender*. New York: Routledge, 2004.1-16.

Campbell M, Hinton JDX, Anderson JR. A systematic review of the relationship between religion and attitudes toward transgender and gender-variant people. *Int J Transgend*. 2019;20(1):21–38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15532739.2018.1545149>. PMID: 32999592; PMCID: PMC6830999.

Campbell MH, Gromer J, Emmanuel MK, Harvey A. Attitudes toward transgender people among future Caribbean doctors. *Arch Sex Behav*. 2022;51(4):1903–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-021-02205-3>. Epub 2021 Nov 15. PMID: 34782942.

- Case, K., Stewart, B. & Tittsworth, J. (2009). Transgender across the curriculum: A psychology for inclusion. *Teaching of Psychology*, 36 (2), 117–121.
- Chan B, Skocylas R, Safer JD. Gaps in transgender medicine content identified among Canadian medical school curricula. *Transgend Health*. 2016;1(1):142–50. <https://doi.org/10.1089/trgh.2016.0010>. PMID: 29159305; PMCID: PMC5685270.
- Chen, X., Elliott, A. L., & Wang, S. (2018). Cross-country Association of Press Freedom and LGBT freedom with the prevalence of persons living with HIV: Implication for a global strategy against HIV/AIDS. *Global health research and policy*, 3(1), 1-11.
- Cheng LF, Yang HC. Learning about gender on campus: an analysis of the hidden curriculum for medical students. *Med Educ*. 2015;49(3):321–31. <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.12628>. PMID: 25693991.
- Cherabie J, Nilsen K, Houssayni S. Transgender health medical education intervention and its effects on beliefs, attitudes, comfort, and knowledge. *Kans J Med*. 2018;11(4):106–9. PMID: 30937150; PMCID: PMC6276966.
- Christensen JA, Hunt T, Elsesser SA, Jerpak C. Medical student perspectives on LGBTQ health. *PRiMER*. 2019;3:27. <https://doi.org/10.22454/PRiMER.2019.288724>. PMID: 32537598; PMCID: PMC7205099.
- Claman, E. E. (2008). An examination of the predictors of attitudes toward transgender individuals (Doctoral dissertation, The Ohio State University).

- Clement, S., et al. (2015). What is the impact of mental health-related stigma on help-seeking? A systematic review of quantitative and qualitative studies. *Psychological Medicine*, 45(1), 11-27.
- Click IA, Mann AK, Buda M, Rahimi-Saber A, Schultz A, Shelton KM, et al. Transgender health education for medical students. *Clin Teach*. 2020;17(2):190–4. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tct.13074>. Epub 2019 Aug 6. PMID: 31386264.
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2nd ed.). New York: Psychology Press.
- Cole, Kristen & Poulakis, Mixalis & Nabors, Lori & Kazi, Nidaa & Shin, Kai & Chu, Josephine & Carter, Emma & Sengupta, Renita. (2016). The Effect of Formal Clinical Training On Stigma Surrounding Transgender Individuals. *Journal of Scholastic Inquiry: Behavioral Sciences*. 5. 32.
- Coleman, E., Adler, R., Bockting, W., Botzer, M., Brown, G., Cohen-Kettenis, P., Zucker, K. (2011). *Standards of care for the health of transgender, transgender, and gender-nonconforming people*. (7th ed.) The World Professional Association for Transgender Health. Retrieved from <http://www.wpath.org/documents/Standards%20of%20Care%20V7%20-%202011%20WPATH.pdf> Corrigan, P. W., & Watson, A. C. (2002). Understanding the impact of stigma on people with mental illness. *World Psychiatry*, 1(1), 16-20.
- Congdon AP 3rd, Tiene K, Price C, Dufresne RL. Closing the gap: raising medical professionals' transgender awareness and medical proficiency through pharmacist-led education. *Ment Health Clin*. 2021;11(1):1–5.

<https://doi.org/10.9740/mhc.2021.01.001>. PMID: 33505818; PMCID: PMC7800331.

- Cook, R. D., & Weisberg, S. (1982). *Residuals and influence in regression*. New York: Chapman & Hall.
- Cooper, M. B., Chacko, M., & Christner, J. (2018). Incorporating LGBT Health in an Undergraduate Medical Education Curriculum Through the Construct of Social Determinants of Health. *MedEdPORTAL : The Journal of Teaching and Learning Resources*, 14, 10781. https://doi.org/10.15766/mep_2374-8265.10781
- Corrêa-Ribeiro, R., Iglesias, F., & Camargos, E. F. (2019). Attitudes Toward Lesbians and Gay Men Scale: validation in Brazilian physicians. *Einstein (São Paulo)*, 17(2). http://dx.doi.org/10.31744/einstein_journal/2019ao4527
- Crenshaw, K. (1989). Demarginalizing the intersection of race and sex: A Black feminist critique of antidiscrimination doctrine, feminist theory, and antiracist politics. *University of Chicago Legal Forum*, 1989(1), 139-167.
- Crisp, A. H., Gelder, M. G., Rix, S., Meltzer, H. I., & Rowlands, O. J. (2000). Stigmatization of people with mental illnesses. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 177(1), 4-7. doi:10.1192/bjp.177.1.4
- Curlin, F. A., Odell, S. V., Lawrence, R. E., Chin, M. H., Lantos, J. D., Meador, K. G., & Koenig, H. G. (2007). The relationship between psychiatry and religion among U.S. physicians. *Psychiatric services (Washington, D.C.)*, 58(9), 1193–1198. <https://doi.org/10.1176/ps.2007.58.9.1193>

Curmi, C., Peters, K. & Salamonson, Y. Lesbians' attitudes, and practices of cervical cancer screening: a qualitative study. *BMC Women's Health* 14, 2 (2014).

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-014-0153-2>

Currah, P. & Minter, S. (2000). *Transgender equality: a handbook for activists and policymakers*. New York: The Policy Institute of the National Gay and Lesbian Task

D'Amore, Salvatore & Wollast, Robin & Green, Robert-Jay & Bouchat, Pierre & Costa, Pedro & Katuzny, Katie & Scali, Thérèse & Baiocco, Roberto & Vecho, Olivier & Mijas, Magda & Aparicio Garcia, Marta Evelia & Geroulanou, Klio & Klein, Olivier. (2022). Heterosexual University Students' Attitudes Toward Same-Sex Couples and Parents Across Seven European Countries. *Sexuality Research and Social Policy Journal of NSRC*. 10.1007/s13178-020-00511-4.

Dale VH, Philomin R. Educating for quality transgender health care: a survey study of medical students. *Educ Health (Abingdon)*. 2022;35(1):31–4. https://doi.org/10.4103/efh.efh_508_20. PMID: 36367027.

D'Amore, Salvatore & Wollast, Robin & Green, Robert-Jay & Bouchat, Pierre & Costa, Pedro & Katuzny, Katie & Scali, Thérèse & Baiocco, Roberto & Vecho, Olivier & Mijas, Magda & Aparicio Garcia, Marta Evelia & Geroulanou, Klio & Klein, Olivier. (2022). Correction to: Heterosexual University Students' Attitudes Toward Same-sex Couples and Parents Across Seven European Countries. *Sexuality Research and Social Policy*. 19. 10.1007/s13178-021-00671-x.

- de Vries E, Kathard H, Müller A. Debate: why should gender-affirming health care be included in health science curricula? *BMC Med Educ.* 2020;20(1):51. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-020-1963-6>. PMID: 32059721; PMCID: PMC7023748.
- de Vries, A. L., Steensma, T. D., Doreleijers, T. A., & Cohen-Kettenis, P. T. (2011). Puberty suppression in adolescents with gender identity disorder: a prospective follow-up study. *The journal of sexual medicine*, 8(8), 2276–2283. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1743-6109.2010.01943.x>
- Della Pelle, C., Cerratti, F., Di Giovanni, P., Cipollone, F., & Cicolini, G. (2018). Attitudes Towards and Knowledge About Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender Patients Among Italian Nurses: An Observational Study. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, 50(4), 367–374. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jnu.12388>
- Dhoest, A. (2019). Learning to be gay: LGBTQ forced migrant identities and narratives in Belgium. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 45(7), 1075-1089.
- Donisi, V., Amaddeo, F., Zakrzewska, K., Farinella, F., Davis, R., Gios, L., ... & Rosinska, M. (2020). Training healthcare professionals in LGBTI cultural competencies: Exploratory findings from the Health4LGBTI pilot project. *Patient education and counseling*, 103(5), 978-987.
- Donisi, V., Amaddeo, F., Zakrzewska, K., Farinella, F., Davis, R., Gios, L.,
- Drescher J. (2010). Queer diagnoses: parallels and contrasts in the history of homosexuality, gender variance, and the diagnostic and statistical manual. *Archives of sexual behavior*, 39(2), 427–460. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-009-9531-5>

- Dubin SN, Nolan IT, Streed CG Jr, Greene RE, Radix AE, Morrison SD. Transgender health care: improving medical students' and residents' training and awareness. *Adv Med Educ Pract.* 2018;9:377–91. <https://doi.org/10.2147/AMEP.S147183>. PMID: 29849472; PMCID: PMC5967378.
- Earnshaw, V. A., et al. (2013). Stigma and racial/ethnic HIV disparities: Moving toward resilience. *The Journal of Social Issues*, 69(1), 6-19.
- EC. Europe 2020 A Strategy for Smart, Sustainable and Inclusive Growth. Brussels: European Commission, 2010
- Edgcumbe D. R. (2022). Age Differences in Open-Mindedness: From 18 to 87 Years of Age. *Experimental aging research*, 48(1), 24–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0361073X.2021.1923330>
- Ellaway RH, Thompson NL, Temple-Oberle C, Pacaud D, Frecker H, Jablonski TJ, et al. An undergraduate medical curriculum framework for providing care to transgender and gender diverse patients: a modified Delphi study. *Perspect Med Educ.* 2022;11(1):36–44. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40037-021-00692-7>. Epub 2021 Nov 18. PMID: 34792753; PMCID: PMC8600495.
- Esteban Mora J, Morales Rodríguez FM, Martínez Ramón JP. Attitudes toward transsexuality, empathy, and bullying in young population. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2022;19(7):3849. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19073849>. PMID: 35409533; PMCID: PMC8997397.
- European Commission. Eurobarometer on the social acceptance of LGBTIQ people in the EU-2019. 2019. <https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/combating->

discrimination/lesbian-gay-bi-trans-and-intersex-equality/eurobarometer-social-acceptance-lgbtq-people-eu-2019_en. Accessed 10 Aug 2023.

FRA. Protection against discrimination on the grounds of sexual orientation, gender identity, and sex characteristics in the EU—Comparative legal analysis—Update 2015. European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2015.

Fradelos EC, Montegrigo J, Cornelius J, Bakalis V, Malliarou M, Papathanasiou IV, et al. Translation and validation of nursing students' knowledge and attitudes of lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender health concerns survey in the Greek language. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2022;10(12):2547.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10122547>. PMID: 36554072; PMCID: PMC9778051.

Fresan A, Domínguez-Martínez T, Castilla F, Muñoz C. Confirmatory factor analysis of the Transgender Knowledge, Attitudes, and Beliefs (T-KAB) scale for the Mexican population. *Arch Sex Behav*. 2022;51(4):1–8.

Freund, R. J., Wilson, W. J., & Sa, P. (2006). *Regression analysis*. Elsevier.

Frontiers in Psychology. (2023). The Impact of Stigma on Mental Health in LGBTQI Populations.

Gassman, R. A., Demone, H. W., & Albilal, R. (2001). Understanding and addressing stigma in mental health care. *Journal of Health Care for the Poor and Underserved*, 12(3), 377-393.

Georgiou, Y., Patsantaras, N., & Kamberidou, I. (2018). Homophobia predictors – A case study in Greece: heterosexual physical education student attitudes

towards male and female homosexuality. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport (JPES)*, 18(2), 1209-1216. <https://doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2018.s2180>

Gibson AW, Gobillot TA, Wang K, Conley E, Coard W, Matsumoto K, et al. A novel curriculum for medical student training in LGBTQ healthcare: a regional pathway experience. *J Med Educ Curric Dev*. 2020;7:2382120520965254. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2382120520965254>. PMID: 33195802; PMCID: PMC7594215.

GLAAD. (2023). *Discrimination Faced by LGBTQ People in the Health Care System*. GLAAD Media Institute.

Glicksman, E. APA: *TransgenderToday*. April 2013, Vol 44, No. 4

Goldsmith, J. (2003). The Self-Defeating International Criminal Court. *The University of Chicago Law Review*, 70(1), 89–104. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1600547>

Grant JM, Mottet LA, Tanis J, Harrison J, Herman JL, Keisling M. *Injustice at Every Turn: A Report of the National Transgender Discrimination Survey*. Washington: National Center for Transgender Equality and National Gay and Lesbian Task Force; 2011.

Grant, J. M., et al. (2011). *Injustice at Every Turn: A Report of the National Transgender Discrimination Survey*. National LGBTQ Task Force.

Greek Law 4496/2017. (2017). Retrieved from https://www.legislationline.org/download/id/8592/file/Greece_civil_status_act_2017_en.pdf

- Greek Transgender Support Association(2017, May). Remarks - suggestions from G.T.S.An in the draft law on the legal recognition of gender identity. Retrieved from URL: <http://www.transgender-association.gr/>
- Greek Transgender Support Association(2019, May). Remarks - suggestions from G.T.S.A for the inclusion of LGBTQI people in the Greek Ministry of Health committee. Retrieved from URL: <http://www.transgender-association.gr/>
- Greene MZ, France K, Kreider EF, Wolfe-Roubatis E, Chen KD, Wu A, et al. Comparing medical, dental, and nursing students' preparedness to address lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and queer health. *PLoS One*. 2018;13(9):e0204104. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0204104>. PMID: 30235283; PMCID: PMC6147466.
- Greytak, E. A., et al. (2013). Harsh Realities: The Experiences of Transgender Youth in Our Nation's Schools. GLSEN.
- Grosz AM, Gutierrez D, Lui AA, Chang JJ, Cole-Kelly K, Ng H. A student-led introduction to lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender health for first-year medical students. *Fam Med*. 2017;49(1):52–6 PMID: 28166581.
- Growing recognition of transgender health. *Bull World Health Organ*. 2016; 94(11):790-1.<https://doi.org/10.2471/BLT.16.021116>. PMID: 27821880; PMCID: PMC5096349.
- Gupta, S., Imborek, K. L., &Krasowski, M. D. (2016). Challenges in transgender healthcare: the pathology perspective. *Laboratory medicine*, 47(3), 180-188.
- Hana T, Butler K, Young LT, Zamora G, Lam JSH. Transgender health in medical education. *Bull World Health Organ*. 2021;99(4):296–303.

<https://doi.org/10.2471/BLT.19.249086>. Epub 2021 Jan 21. PMID: 33953447; PMCID: PMC8085635.

Hellenic Psychiatric Association (2023). Διοργάνωση Εκπαιδευτικού Σεμιναρίου για Θέματα Φύλου από τον Κλάδο “Σεξουαλικότητας & Διαπροσωπικών Σχέσεων” της Ελληνικής Ψυχιατρικής Εταιρείας. Retrieved from: <https://psych.gr/diorganosi-ekpaideytikoy-seminariou-gia-themata-fyloy-apo-ton-klado-sexoyalikotitas-amp-diaprosopikon-scheseon-tis-ellinikis-psychiatrikis-etairias/>

Hembree, W. C., Cohen-Kettenis, P. T., Gooren, L., Hannema, S. E., Meyer, W. J., Murad, M. H., Rosenthal, S. M., Safer, J. D., Tangpricha, V., & T'Sjoen, G. G. (2017). Endocrine Treatment of Gender-Dysphoric/Gender-Incongruent Persons: An Endocrine Society Clinical Practice Guideline. *The Journal of clinical endocrinology and metabolism*, 102(11), 3869–3903. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jc.2017-01658>

Hepworth, D. H., Rooney, R. H., & Larsen, J. A. (2002). *Direct Social Work Practice: Theory and Skills*. Wadsworth Publishing.

Herek, G. M. (1984). Attitudes toward lesbians and gay men: A factor-analytic study. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 10, 39–51.

Herek, G. M. (2007). *Confronting Sexual Stigma and Prejudice: Theory and Practice*. *Journal of Social Issues*, 63(4), 905-925.

Herek, G. M., & Glunt, E. K. (1993). Interpersonal contact and heterosexuals' attitudes toward gay men: Results from a national survey. *Journal of Sex Research*, 30, 239–244.

- Herek, G. M., Capitanio, J. P., & Widaman, K. F. (2002a). HIV-related stigma and knowledge in the United States: Prevalence and trends, 1991–1999. *American Journal of Public Health, 92*, 371–377.
- Herek, G. M., Cogan, J. C., & Gillis, J. R. (2009). Internalized stigma among sexual minority adults: Insights from a social psychological perspective. *Journal of Counseling Psychology, 56*, 32–43.
- Herek, G. M., Gillis, J. R., & Cogan, J. C. (1999). Psychological sequelae of hate-crime victimization among lesbian, gay, and bisexual adults. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology, 67*, 945–951.
- Hill, D. B., & Willoughby, B. L. (2005). The development and validation of the genderism and transphobia scale. *Sex roles, 53*(7), 531-544.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-005-7140-x>
- Hill, D. B., & Willoughby, B. L. B. (2005). The development and validation of the Genderism and Transphobia Scale. *Sex Roles, 53*, 531–544.
- HIV.gov. (2023). Impact on racial and ethnic minorities. Retrieved from <https://www.hiv.gov>
- Huber, P. J. (1981). *Robust statistics*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Hudson, W. H., & Ricketts, W. A. (1980). A strategy for the measurement of homophobia. *Journal of Homosexuality, 5*, 357–372.
- Hudson, W. H., & Ricketts, W. A. (1980). A strategy for the measurement of homophobia. *Journal of Homosexuality, 5*, 357–372.
- Huebner, D. M., & Davis, M. C. (2007). Perceived antigay discrimination and physical health outcomes. *Health Psychology, 26*, 627–634.

Hunter, D. J., & Boyle, K. (2020). A healthier way to meet people: the experiences of LGBT people exercising with a peer group. *British Journal of Nursing*, 29(18), 1068-1073.

Inmaculada FA, Isabel CG. Discrimination and violence due to diversity of sexual orientation and gender identity: explanatory variables. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(7):3638. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18073638>. PMID: 33807409; PMCID: PMC8037392.

Institute of Medicine (2011). *The Health of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and transgender people: Building a Foundation for Better Understanding*.

Jäckle, S., & Wenzelburger, G. (2015). Religion, religiosity, and the attitudes toward homosexuality--a multilevel analysis of 79 countries. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 62(2), 207–241. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2014.969071>

Jackson, S. E., Hackett, R. A., Grabovac, I., Smith, L., & Steptoe, A. (2019). Perceived discrimination, health, and wellbeing among middle-aged and older lesbian, gay and bisexual people: A prospective study. *PloS one*, 14(5), e0216497.

James S, Colling SH. Transgender health and its current omission from medical school curriculum: medical students' perspective. *Adv Med Educ Pract*. 2018;9:607–9. <https://doi.org/10.2147/AMEP.S176532>. PMID: 30214373; PMCID: PMC6124798.

James, S. E., et al. (2016). *The Report of the 2015 U.S. Transgender Survey*. National Center for Transgender Equality.

- Janssen, D. J., & Scheepers, P. (2019). How Religiosity Shapes Rejection of Homosexuality Across the Globe. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 66(14), 1974–2001. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2018.1522809>
- Jarin, J., Pine-Twaddell, E., Trotman, G., Stevens, J., Conard, L. A., Tefera, E., & Gomez-Lobo, V. (2017). Cross-sex hormones and metabolic parameters in adolescents with gender dysphoria. *Pediatrics*, 139(5), [e20163173]. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-3173>
- Jecke, L., & Zepf, F. D. (2023). Delivering transgender-specific knowledge and skills into health and allied health studies and training: a systematic review. *European child & adolescent psychiatry*, 10.1007/s00787-023-02195-8. Advanced online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00787-023-02195-8>
- Jeon SY, Yoon HB, Park JE, Lee SY, Yoon JW. A qualitative study on the internal response of medical students during the transgender healthcare education: a focus on professional identity. *Korean J Med Educ*. 2022;34(4):281–97. <https://doi.org/10.3946/kjme.2022.237>. Epub 2022 Nov 29. PMID: 36464899.
- Johnson, L. R., et al. (2015). Impact of LGBTQI Sensitivity Training on Medical Student Attitudes toward LGBTQI Patients: A Longitudinal Study. *LGBT Health*, 2(4), 356-361.
- Jones, C. A., et al. (2016). Exploring the Attitudes of Medical Students towards Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender Patients: A Qualitative Study. *Journal of LGBT Health*, 3(1), 35-41.
- Kaiser Family Foundation. (2018). *Understanding the Health Needs of LGBT People*.

- Kanamori Y, Cornelius-White JHD, Pegors TK, Daniel T, Hulgus J. Development and validation of the transgender attitudes and beliefs scale. *Arch Sex Behav.* 2017;46(5):1503–15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-016-0840-1>. Epub 2016 Aug 29. PMID: 27571743.
- Kanamori Y, Fossett S, Schimmel-Bristow A, Stenersen MR, Bullard MB, Cornelius-White JHD. Transgender Attitudes and Beliefs Scale (TABS): validation with a sample of self-identified Christians. *Ment Health Relig Cult.* 2021;24(8):862–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13674676.2021.1953970>. Epub 2021 Aug 9. PMID: 34867072; PMCID: PMC8635297.
- Kanamori Y, Jiménez-Etxebarria E, Cornelius-White JHD, Ozamiz-Etxebarria N, Wynne KN, Gorrotxategi MP. Transgender Attitudes and Beliefs Scale-Spanish (TABS-S) version: translation and initial evaluation of psychometric properties. *J Homosex.* 2023;70(5):831–50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2021.2004797>. Epub 2021 Nov 29. PMID: 34842511.
- Karakaya, S., & Kutlu, F. Y. (2021). LGBT individuals' opinions about their health care experiences: A qualitative research study. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 29(1), 24-31.
- Katsiampoura, A., Kourkoutas, E., Kyranoudi, S., & Tsevelis, A. (2021). Attitudes of medical students towards transgender individuals in Greece: A cross-sectional study. *Archives of Hellenic Medicine*, 38(4), 512-520.
- Katz-Wise SL, Jarvie EJ, Potter J, Keuroghlian AS, Gums JN, Koscienza AJ, et al. Integrating LGBTQIA + community member perspectives into medical education. *Teach Learn Med.* 2022:1–15.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10401334.2022.2092112>. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 35766109.

Kelterborn, Mary. "The Medicalization of Gender: how the medical discourse of transsexuality and intersexuality in the Netherlands contributes to the third space." 2001. 1-47.

Kerr, L., Fisher, C.M., Jones, T. (2019). *TRANScending Discrimination in Health & Cancer Care: A Study of Trans & Gender Diverse Australians*, (ARCSHS Monograph Series No. 115), Bundoora: ARCSHS. ISBN: 978-0-9953969-5-1.

Kite, M. E. (1984). Sex differences in attitudes toward homosexuals: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 10, 69–81.

Klittmark, S., Garzón, M., Andersson, E., & Wells, M. B. (2019). LGBTQ competence wanted: LGBTQ parents' experiences of reproductive health care in Sweden. *Scandinavian journal of caring sciences*, 33(2), 417-426.

Konstantinidis C, Bebetos E, Filippou F, Zetou E. Gender-related attitudes toward homosexuality in Greece. *Chang Soc Pers*. 2021;5(4):669–85.
<https://doi.org/10.15826/csp.2021.5.4.156>.

Korpaisarn S, Safer JD. Gaps in transgender medical education among healthcare providers: a major barrier to care for transgender persons. *Rev Endocr Metab Disord*. 2018;19(3):271–5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11154-018-9452-5>. PMID: 29922962.

Lampalzer, U., Behrendt, P., Dekker, A., Briken, P., & Nieder, T. O. (2019). The needs of LGBTI people regarding health care structures, prevention measures,

and diagnostic and treatment procedures: a qualitative study in a German metropolis. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(19), 3547.

Lampalzer, U., Seitz, T., & Brähler, E. (2019). The influence of cultural beliefs on doctors' attitudes towards LGBTQI patients. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 20(1), 35.

Landau, N., Hamiel, U., Tokatly Latzer, I., Mauda, E., Levek, N., Tripto-Shkolnik, L., & Pinhas-Hamiel, O. (2020). Pediatricians' attitudes and beliefs towards transgender people: A cross-sectional survey in Israel. *BMJ Open*, 10(4), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-031569>

Larsen, K. S., Reed, M., & Hoffman, S. (1980). Attitudes of heterosexuals toward homosexuality: A Likert-type scale and construct validity. *Journal of Sex Research*, 16, 245–257.

Lavorgna, L., Moccia, M., Russo, A., Palladino, R., Riccio, L., Lanzillo, R., ...& Bonavita, S. (2017). Healthcare disparities stem from the sexual orientation of Italian patients with multiple sclerosis: a cross-sectional web-based study. *Multiple sclerosis and related disorders*, 13, 28-32.

Lee SA, O'Brien OF, Turner MJ, Kennelly MM. Implementing medical student teaching on gynaecological healthcare of transgender patients. *Ir Med J*. 2022;115(7):632 PMID: 36300707.

Lee SR, Kim MA, Choi MN, Park S, Cho J, Lee C, et al. Attitudes toward transgender people among medical students in South Korea. *Sex Med*. 2021;9(1):100278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esxm.2020.10.006>. Epub 2020 Dec 5. PMID: 33291040; PMCID: PMC7930852.

Levy A, Prasad S, Griffin DP, Ortega M, O'Malley CB. Attitudes and knowledge of medical students towards healthcare for lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender seniors: impact of a case-based discussion with facilitators from the community. *Cureus*. 2021;13(8):e17425. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.17425>. PMID: 34603856; PMCID: PMC8475289.

LGBTI equality and human rights in Europe and Central Asia

(2021).<https://www.Olga-Europe.org/what-we-do/our-advocacy-work/health>

Lin, Y., Xie, H., Huang, Z., Zhang, Q., Wilson, A., Hou, J., Zhao, X., Wang, Y., Pan, B., Liu, Y., Han, M., & Chen, R. (2021). The mental health of transgender and gender non-conforming people in China: a systematic review. *The Lancet. Public health*, 6(12), e954–e969. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667\(21\)00236-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667(21)00236-X)

Link, B. G., & Phelan, J. C. (2001). Conceptualizing stigma. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 27, 363-385.

López-Sáez MÁ, García-Dauder D, Montero I. Correlate attitudes toward LGBT and sexism in Spanish psychology students. *Front Psychol*. 2020;11:2063. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.02063>. PMID: 32973622; PMCID: PMC7472884.

Lu PY, Hsu ASC, Green A, Tsai JC. Medical students' perceptions of their preparedness to care for LGBT patients in Taiwan: is medical education keeping up with social progress? *PLoS One*. 2022;17(7):e0270862. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0270862>. PMID: 35797357; PMCID: PMC9262208.

- MacFarlane, D., Blum, R., & Khan, M. (2011). Attitudes toward transgender persons among medical students. *BMC Public Health*, 11, 543.
- Martins RS, Saleh R, Kamal H, Gillani M, Merchant AAH, Munir MM, et al. The need for transgender healthcare medical education in a developing country. *Adv Med Educ Pract*. 2020;11:405–13.
<https://doi.org/10.2147/AMEP.S255483>. PMID: 32607043; PMCID: PMC7292255.
- Maslach, C., Schaufeli, W. B., & Leiter, M. P. (2001). Job burnout. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52(1), 397-422. doi:10.1146/annurev.psych.52.1.397
- Master, W. (2022). The Moral Third – Moving Beyond Violence –. Retrieved 16 September 2022, from <http://www.movingbeyondviolence.org/the-moral-third/#:~:text=The%20Moral%20Third%2>
- McDowell MJ, Goldhammer H, Potter JE, Keuroghlian AS. Strategies to Mitigate Clinician Implicit Bias Against Sexual and Gender Minority Patients. *Psychosomatics*. 2020;61(6):655–61.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psych.2020.04.021>.
- McGee R. (2016). Does Religion Influence Views Toward Homosexuality: An Empirical Study of 16 Countries. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2799871>
- McGlynn, N., Browne, K., Sherriff, N., Zeeman, L., Mirandola, M., Gios, L., ...&Hugendubel, K. (2020). Healthcare professionals' assumptions as barriers to LGBTI healthcare. *Culture, health & sexuality*, 22(8), 954-970.

- Meyer, I. H. (1995). Minority Stress and Mental Health in Gay Men. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 36(1), 38-56.
- Meyer, I. H. (2003). Prejudice, Social Stress, and Mental Health in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Populations: Conceptual Issues and Research Evidence. *Psychological Bulletin*, 129(5), 674-697.
- Minturn MS, Martinez EI, Le T, Nokoff N, Fitch L, Little CE, et al. Early intervention for LGBTQ health: a 10-hour curriculum for preclinical health professions students. *MedEdPORTAL*. 2021;17:11072. https://doi.org/10.15766/mep_2374-8265.11072. Erratum in: *MedEdPORTAL*. 2022; 18:11251. PMID: 33473382; PMCID: PMC7809930.
- Monro, S. (2010). The Equality Act 2010 and Gender Identity. *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 14(5), 655-678.
- Monteiro, Delmira & Poulakis, Mixalis. (2019). Effects of Cisnormative Beauty Standards on Transgender Women's Perceptions and Expressions of Beauty. *Midwest Social Sciences Journal*. 22. 10.22543/2766-0796.1009.
- Moreno, M. A., et al. (2013). Cyberbullying among adolescents: Implications for empirical research. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 53(4), 431-432.
- Morris M, Cooper RL, Ramesh A, Tabatabai M, Arcury TA, Shinn M, et al. Training to reduce LGBTQ-related bias among medical, nursing, and dental students and providers: a systematic review. *BMC Med Educ*. 2019;19(1):325. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-019-1727-3>. PMID: 31470837; PMCID: PMC6716913.

Müller A. (2017). Scrambling for access: availability, accessibility, acceptability and quality of healthcare for lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender people in South Africa. *BMC international health and human rights*, 17(1), 16.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12914-017-0124-4>

Muns SM, Ortiz-Ramos KJ, García-Rivera EJ, González L, Romaguera J. Knowledge and attitudes about transgender healthcare: exploring the perspectives of Hispanic medical students. *P R Health Sci J*. 2022;41(3):128–34 PMID: 36018740.

Najor AJ, Kling JM, Imhof RL, Sussman JD, Nippoldt TB, Davidge-Pitts CJ.

Transgender health care curriculum development: a dual-site medical school campus pilot. *Health Equity*. 2020;4(1):102–13.

<https://doi.org/10.1089/heq.2019.0106>. PMID: 32258962; PMCID:

PMC713343.

Nama N, MacPherson P, Sampson M, McMillan HJ. Medical students' perception of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) discrimination in their learning environment and their self-reported comfort level for caring for LGBT patients: a survey study. *Med Educ Online*. 2017;22(1):1368850.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10872981.2017.1368850>. PMID: 28853327; PMCID:

PMC5653936.

National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH). (2023). Addressing HIV-related intersectional stigma and discrimination. Retrieved from

<https://www.nimh.nih.gov>

NCAVP. (2021). Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, and HIV-Affected Hate Violence in 2020. National Coalition of Anti-Violence Programs.

- Nolan IT, Blasdel G, Dubin SN, Goetz LG, Greene RE, Morrison SD. Current state of transgender medical education in the United States and Canada: update to a scoping review. *J Med Educ Curric Dev.* 2020;7:2382120520934813. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2382120520934813>. PMID: 32637641; PMCID: PMC7315660.
- Nordt, C., Rössler, W., & Lauber, C. (2006). Attitudes of mental health professionals toward people with schizophrenia and major depression. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 32(4), 709-714. doi:10.1093/schbul/sbj065
- Nota NM, Wiepjes CM, de Blok CJM, Gooren LJG, Kreukels BPC, den Heijer M. Occurrence of acute cardiovascular events in transgender individuals receiving hormone therapy. *Circulation.* 2019;139(11):1461–2. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.118.038584>. PMID: 30776252.
- Nowaskie DZ, Patel AU. How much is needed? Patient exposure and curricular education on medical students' LGBT cultural competency. *BMC Med Educ.* 2020;20(1):490. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-020-02381-1>. Erratum in: *BMC Med Educ.* 2022; 22(1):442. PMID: 33276769; PMCID: PMC7716501.
- Obedin-Maliver J, Goldsmith ES, Stewart L, White W, Tran E, Brenman S, et al. Lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender-related content in undergraduate medical education. *JAMA.* 2011;306(9):971–7. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2011.1255>. PMID: 21900137.
- Orzechowski, M., Nowak, M., Bielińska, K., Chowaniec, A., Doričić, R., Ramšak, M., Łuków, P., Muzur, A., Zupanič-Slavec, Z., & Steger, F. (2020). Social diversity and access to healthcare in Europe: How does the European Union's

legislation prevent discrimination in healthcare? BMC Public Health, 20(1), 1399. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-09494-8>

Papadaki V, Ntiken A. “As a trans person you don’t live. You merely try to survive and apologize every day for who you are” - discrimination experiences among trans individuals in Greece. *J Homosex.* 2023;70(7):1325–47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2021.2020544>. Epub 2022 Jan 10. PMID: 35007491.

Papadaki V, Plotnikof K, Gioumidou M, Zisimou V, Papadaki E. A comparison of attitudes toward lesbians and gay men among students of helping professions in Crete, Greece: the cases of social work, psychology, medicine, and nursing. *J Homosex.* 2015;62(6):735–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2014.998956>. Epub 2015 Jan 26. PMID: 25530439.

Papadimitriou, V., Lazaris, D., Gogou, A., & Katsikis, I. (2020). Healthcare needs and access to care among transgender people in Greece. *Health Science Journal*, 14(4), 1-9.

Parameshwaran V, Cockbain BC, Hillyard M, Price JR. Is the lack of specific lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and queer/questioning (LGBTQ) health care education in medical school a cause for concern? Evidence from a survey of knowledge and practice among UK medical students. *J Homosex.* 2017;64(3):367–81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2016.1190218>. Epub 2016 May 16. PMID: 27184023.

Parameshwaran, V., Cockbain, B. C., Hillyard, M., & Price, J. R. (2017). Is the lack of specific lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and queer/questioning

(LGBTQ) healthcare education in medical school a cause for concern?

Evidence from a survey of knowledge and practice among UK medical students. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 64(3), 367-381.

Park JA, Safer JD. Clinical exposure to transgender medicine improves students' preparedness above levels seen with didactic teaching alone: a key addition to the Boston University model for teaching transgender healthcare. *Transgender Health*. 2018;3(1):10–6. <https://doi.org/10.1089/trgh.2017.0047>. PMID: 29344576; PMCID: PMC5770129.

Pavlou M. (2008) The Situation concerning homophobia and discrimination on grounds of sexual orientation in Greece. *Sociological Country Report*.

Pearce, R. (2018). Health Care Access and the Transgender Population: The Role of Legislation and Policy. *Social Science & Medicine*, 203, 82-89.

Perry, B. L., et al. (2021). Covid-19 pandemic and violence: Rising risks and decreasing urgent care-seeking for sexual assault and domestic violence survivors. *BMC Medicine*, 19(1), 1-6.

Pew Research Center. (2018). Eastern and Western Europeans Differ on the Importance of Religion, Views of Minorities, and Key Social Issues. Washington, D.C. Retrieved from: <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2018/10/29/eastern-and-western-europeans-differ-on-importance-of-religion-views-of-minorities-and-key-social-issues/>

Pew Research Center. (2018). Greek attitudes toward religion and minorities align more with Central and Eastern Europe than the West. Washington, D.C. Retrieved from: <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2018/10/31/greek->

attitudes-toward-religion-minorities-align-more-with-central-and-eastern-europe-than-west/

Phipps, S. (2018). New Scottish plans can help end the postcode lottery for LGBT pupils. *British Journal of School Nursing*, 13(10), 503-504.

PinkNews. (2022). Debates Around Trans Healthcare Following the Cass Review. *American Psychiatric Association*, 3(4), 598-617.

Ploumen, R., & Livas, C. (2020). Students' awareness of LGBT resources in Dutch dental schools. *Journal of Dental Education*, 84(8), 881-886.

Prandelli, M., & Testoni, I. (2020). Inside the doctor's office. Talking about intersex with Italian health professionals. *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 1-16.

QSR International Pty Ltd. (2018) NVivo (Version 12),
<https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo-qualitative-data-analysis-software/home>.

Rambarran N, Simpson J, White Y. Medical students' attitudes towards, and knowledge of LGBT persons in Guyana. *J Homosex*. 2022;69(11):1964–79. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2021.1933794>. Epub 2021 Jun 22. PMID: 34156921.

Rayner, J. A., Allen, J., & Johnson, M. (2005). Early termination of therapy in medically underserved populations. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 61(6), 777-789.

Rider GN, McMorris BJ, Gower AL, Coleman E, Brown C, Eisenberg ME. Perspectives from nurses and physicians on training needs and comfort working with transgender and gender-diverse youth. *J Pediatr Health Care*.

2019;33(4):379–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedhc.2018.11.003>. Epub 2019 Mar 1. PMID: 30827755; PMCID: PMC6589105.

Romanelli M, Lindsey MA. Patterns of healthcare discrimination among transgender help-seekers. *Am J Prev Med.* 2020;58(4):e123–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2019.11.002>. Epub 2020 Jan 28. PMID: 32001051.

Rondahl, G. (2009). Nurses' attitudes towards transgender patients. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 67(7), 1421-1432.

Rosati, F., Pistella, J., & Baiocco, R. (2020). Italian sexual minority older adults in healthcare services: identities, discriminations, and competencies. *Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 1-11.

Rosichan, S. A. (2015). Attitudes towards trans people, genderism, and transphobia as moderated by religious ideologies (Doctoral dissertation, Middle Tennessee State University).

Rossler, W. (2012). Stress, burnout, and job dissatisfaction in mental health workers. *European Archives of Psychiatry and Clinical Neuroscience*, 262(2), 65-69. doi:10.1007/s00406-012-0353-4

Sanchez K, Abrams MP, Khallouq BB, Topping D. Classroom instruction: medical students' attitudes toward LGBTQI+ patients. *J Homosex.* 2022;69(11):1801–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2021.1933782>. Epub 2021 Jun 29. PMID: 34185630.

Sawning S, Steinbock S, Croley R, Combs R, Shaw A, Ganzel T. A first step in addressing medical education curriculum gaps in lesbian-, gay-, bisexual-, and

transgender-related content: the University of Louisville Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender Health Certificate Program. *Educ Health (Abingdon)*. 2017;30(2):108–14. https://doi.org/10.4103/efh.EfH_78_16. PMID: 28928340.

Sekoni AO, Gale NK, Manga-Atangana B, Bhadhuri A, Jolly K. The effects of educational curricula and training on LGBT-specific health issues for healthcare students and professionals: a mixed-method systematic review. *J Int AIDS Soc*. 2017;2:21624.

Serrano, Julia. *Whipping Girl: A Transsexual Woman on Sexism and the Scapegoating of Femininity*. Emeryville, CA: Seal, 2007.

Sherriff, N., Zeeman, L., McGlynn, N., Browne, K., Pawlega, M., Rodzinka, M., Pinto, N., Hugendubel, K., Russell, C., Costongs, C., Sanchez-Lambert, J., Mirandola, M., & Rosinska, M. (2020). Training healthcare professionals in LGBTI cultural competencies: Exploratory findings from the Health4LGBTI pilot project. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 103(5), 978–987. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2019.12.007>

Sherriff, N., Zeeman, L., McGlynn, N., Pinto, N., Hugendubel, K., Mirandola, M., ... & Health4LGBTI Network. (2019). Co-producing knowledge of lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, and intersex (LGBTI) healthcare inequalities via rapid reviews of grey literature in 27 EU Member States. *Health Expectations*, 22(4), 688-700.

Shields, L., Zappia, T., Blackwood, D., Watkins, R., Wardrop, J., & Chapman, R. (2012). Lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender parents seeking health care for

- their children: a systematic review of the literature. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 9(4), 200-209.
- Siebert, D. C. (2004). Personal and occupational factors in burnout among practicing social workers: Implications for research, practitioners, and managers. *Journal of Social Service Research*, 30(4), 1-15.
- Smith, J. K., et al. (2017). The Role of Religion in Shaping Medical Providers' Attitudes toward Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Patients. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 64(6), 807-822.
- Snelgrove, J. W., Jasudavisius, A. M., Rowe, B. W., Head, E. M., & Bauer, G. R. (2012). "Completely out-at-sea" with "two-gender medicine": a qualitative analysis of physician-side barriers to providing healthcare for transgender patients. *BMC health services research*, 12, 110. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-12-110>
- Song AY, Poythress EL, Bocchini CE, Kass JS. Reorienting orientation: introducing the social determinants of health to first-year medical students. *MedEdPORTAL*. 2018;14:10752. https://doi.org/10.15766/mep_2374-8265.10752. PMID: 30800952; PMCID: PMC6342337.
- Soto-Lafontaine, M. A. (2020). From Medical to Human-Rights Norms: Examining the Evolution of Trans Norms in the Netherlands.
- Sriram, T. G., & Jabbarpour, Y. (2005). Compassionate Care: Understanding the Role of Compassion in the Health Care System. *The Journal of Medical Practice Management*, 20(5), 225-228.

- Stateofart_report_en.pdf. (n.d.). Retrieved February 27, 2021, from https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/social_determinants/docs/stateofart_report_en.pdf
- Stroumsa D. The state of transgender health care: policy, law, and medical frameworks. *Am J Public Health*. 2014;104(3):e31–8. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2013.301789>. Epub 2014 Jan 16. PMID: 24432926; PMCID: PMC3953767.
- Szél Z, Kiss D, Török Z, Gyarmathy VA. Hungarian medical students' knowledge about and attitude toward homosexual, bisexual, and transsexual individuals. *J Homosex*. 2020;67(10):1429–46. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2019.1600898>. Epub 2019 Apr 29. PMID: 31034340.
- Tam, T., Schmidt, L., & Weisner, C. (1996). Patterns of drug use among patients with severe mental illnesses: A ten-year perspective. *The American Journal of Drug and Alcohol Abuse*, 22(1), 109-122.
- Tami, A., Ferguson, T., Bauer, G. R., & Scheim, A. I. (2022). Avoidance of primary healthcare among transgender and non-binary people in Canada during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Preventive medicine reports*, 27, 101789. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2022.101789>
- Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International journal of medical education*, 2, 53. doi: 10.5116/ijme.4dfb.8dfd
- The Century Foundation (TCF). (2023). Racism, inequality, and health care for African Americans. Retrieved from <https://www.tcf.org>

- The English Standard Version Bible: Containing the Old and New Testaments with Apocrypha. (2009). Oxford University Press.
- The Guardian. (2022). The Impact of the Cass Review on Transgender Healthcare.
- Thompson H, Coleman JA, Iyengar RM, Phillips S, Kent PM, Sheth N. Evaluation of a gender-affirming healthcare curriculum for second-year medical students. *Postgrad Med J.* 2020;96(1139):515–9. <https://doi.org/10.1136/postgradmedj-2019-136683>. Epub 2019 Dec 11. PMID: 31826922.
- Time to Change. (2010). Stigma shout: Service user and carer experiences of stigma and discrimination. Retrieved from <https://www.time-to-change.org.uk>
- Tollemache N, Shrewsbury D, Llewellyn C. Que(e) rying undergraduate medical curricula: a cross-sectional online survey of lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and queer content inclusion in UK undergraduate medical education. *BMC Med Educ.* 2021;21(1):100. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-021-02532-y>. PMID: 33579262; PMCID: PMC7881554
- Tordoff DM, Wanta JW, Collin A, Stepney C, Inwards-Breland DJ, Ahrens K. Mental health outcomes in transgender and nonbinary youths receiving gender-affirming care. *JAMA Netw Open.* 2022;5(2):e220978. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2022.0978>. Erratum in: *JAMA Netw Open.* 2022; 5(7): e2229031. PMID: 35212746; PMCID: PMC8881768.
- Trans Hub. Why are trans people part of LGBT? ACON 2021. <https://www.transhub.org.au/>. Accessed 14 Aug 2023.

- Tsao, C. I., Tummala, A., & Roberts, L. W. (2008). Social Workers and Burnout: Understanding the Impact on Empathy and Professional Practice. *Social Work in Mental Health*, 7(1-3), 89-103.
- Üçok, A., Polat, A., Sartorius, N., Erkoc, S., & Atakli, C. (2004). Attitudes of psychiatrists toward patients with schizophrenia. *Psychiatry and Clinical Neurosciences*, 58(1), 89-91.
- Underman K, Giffort D, Hyderi A, Hirshfield LE. Transgender health: a standardized patient case for advanced clerkship students. *MedEdPORTAL*. 2016;12:10518. https://doi.org/10.15766/mep_2374-8265.10518. PMID: 30984860; PMCID: PMC6440493.
- United Nations (UN). Resolution A/RES/70/1. Transforming our world: the 2030 agenda for sustainable development. In: Seventieth United Nations General Assembly, New York, 13–5 September 2016. New York: United Nations. 2015. https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/generalassembly/docs/globalcompact/A_RES_70_1_E.pdf. Accessed 24 Sept 2023.
- US Department of Health and Human Services. Healthy people 2020: lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender health. 2020. <https://www.healthypeople.gov/2020/topics-objectives/topic/lesbian-gay-bisexual-and-transgender-health>. Accessed 10 Aug 2023.
- Van Den Ameele, S., Keygnaert, I., Rachidi, A., Roelens, K., & Temmerman, M. (2013). The role of the healthcare sector in the prevention of sexual violence against sub-Saharan transmigrants in Morocco: A study of knowledge,

attitudes, and practices of healthcare workers. *BMC Health Services Research*, 13(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-13-77>

Vasudevan A, García AD, Hart BG, Kindratt TB, Pagels P, Orcutt V, et al. Health professions students' knowledge, skills, and attitudes toward transgender healthcare. *J Community Health*. 2022;47(6):981–9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10900-022-01135-y>. Epub 2022 Aug 24. PMID: 36001214.

Vatcheva, K. P., Lee, M., McCormick, J. B., & Rahbar, M. H. (2016). Multicollinearity in regression analyses conducted in epidemiologic studies. *Epidemiology (Sunnyvale, Calif.)*, 6(2). doi: 10.4172/2161-1165.1000227

Voultos P, Chatzinikolaou F, Papan A, Deliligka A. Reliability of Greek version of the Toronto empathy questionnaire in medical students and associations with sociodemographic and lifestyle factors. *BMC Psychol*. 2022;10(1):113. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-022-00824-6>. PMID: 35501889; PMCID: PMC9063083.

Voultos P, Zymvragou CE, Karakasi MV, Pavlidis P. A qualitative study examining transgender people's attitudes towards having a child to whom they are genetically related and pursuing fertility treatments in Greece. *BMC Public Health*. 2021;21(1):378. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-10422-7>. PMID: 33602164; PMCID: PMC7890100.

Voultos, Polychronis & Papan, Angeliki & Alexandri, Stella & Zymvragou, Christina-Erato. (2023). Transgender Attitudes and Beliefs Scale-Greek (TABS-Gr) Version: Translation and Initial Evaluation of Psychometric Properties among Medical Students.. 10.21203/rs.3.rs-2653267/v1.

- Wahlen, R., Bize, R., Wang, J., Merglen, A., & Ambresin, A.-E. (2020a). Medical students' knowledge of and attitudes towards LGBT people and their health care needs: Impact of a lecture on LGBT health. *PLOS ONE*, 15(7), e0234743. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0234743>
- Watkinson, D., & Sunderland, C. (2017). How discrimination affects access to health care for transgender people. *Nursing Times*, 113(4), 36–39.
- West, C., Zimmerman D., *Gender and Society*, Vol. 1, No. 2. (Jun. 1987), pp. 125-151.
- White Hughto, J. M., et al. (2021). Sexual orientation and gender identity-based discrimination and mental health: Understanding mechanisms of harm using a minority stress framework. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 86, 102008.
- Whittle S. et al. *Engendered Penalties: Transgender and Transsexual People's Experiences of Inequality and Discrimination*, 2007; Motmans J. et al. *Being transgender in Belgium - Mapping the social and legal situation of transgender people*, 2010.
- Whittle, S. (2006). *The Gender Recognition Act 2004: A Guide*. GIRES.
- Williams, L. J., & Smith, A. (2018). Healthcare Provider Attitudes Toward the Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender Population. *Nursing Education Perspectives*, 39(4), 213-218.
- Wong, Brian, *On Relational Injustice: Could Colonialism Have Been Wrong Even if it Had Introduced More Benefits than Harms?* (February 6, 2019). *Journal of Practical Ethics*, Volume 7, Supplementary, October 2019, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3474950>

- World Health Organization (WHO). (n.d.). Informed consent. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int>
- World Health Organization. (2010). The ICD-10 classification of mental and behavioral disorder: Clinical descriptions and diagnostic guidelines. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/classifications/icd/en/bluebook.pdf> Yutrsenka, B. A. (1995). Making a case for training in ethnic and cultural diversity in increasing treatment efficacy. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 63, 197 – 206.
- Wright D, Campedelli A. Pilot study: increasing medical student comfort in transgender gynecology. *MedEdPublish*. 2016;2022(12):8. <https://doi.org/10.12688/mep.18990.2>. PMID: 36168535; PMCID: PMC9370083.
- Yu H, Flores DD, Bonett S, Bauermeister JA. LGBTQ + cultural competency training for health professionals: a systematic review. *BMC Med Educ*. 2023;23(1):558. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-023-04373-3>. PMID: 37559033; PMCID: PMC10410776.
- Zeeman L, Aranda K, Sherriff NS, et al. Promoting resilience and emotional well-being of transgender young people: research at the intersections of gender and sexuality. *J Youth Stud* 2017;20:382–97.
- Zeeman, L., et al. (2019). A review of the literature on the healthcare experiences of transgender and gender non-conforming people. *International Journal of Transgender Health*, 20(4), 408-432. doi:10.1080/15532739.2019.1650517
- Zeeman, L., Sherriff, N., Browne, K., McGlynn, N., Mirandola, M., Gios, L., ... & Health4LGBTI Network TaibjeeRafikToskin Igor Jonas Kai van Der Veur

Dennis Allen Odhrán Troussier Thierry De Sutter Petra. (2019). A review of lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, and intersex (LGBTI) health and healthcare inequalities. *European journal of public health*, 29(5), 974-980.

Zucker, K. J., & Bradley, S. J. (2005). Gender identity and psychosexual disorders.

Ame Lauber, C., Nordt, C., Falcato, L., & Rössler, W. (2006). Do mental health professionals stigmatize their patients? *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 113(3), 217-227.

APPENDIX A

Glossary of Terms

AFAB: An acronym that stands for Assigned Female at Birth. AFAB might identify as female all the time, some of the time, or not at all. It's a term utilized for discussing issues affecting these individuals without necessarily linking them to womanhood or femininity.

Gender Affirmation: Refers to recognizing an individual's authentic gender, contrasting with the gender they were assigned at birth. This terminology is preferred over phrases like "new gender" or "chosen gender," which wrongly suggest a voluntary aspect of gender identity.

Agender: Describes someone who does not align with or experience gender. This differs from being nonbinary as nonbinary individuals may still experience a sense of gender.

Ally: A term for people who support and advocate for the rights and acceptance of marginalized groups, especially within the LGBTQ+ community. Allies can be from outside the LGBTQ+ community but also include LGBTQ+ individuals supporting each other.

AMAB: Stands for Assigned Male at Birth. People designated AMAB may or may not consider themselves male partially or fully. The term is significant for discussing issues pertinent to these individuals without necessarily associating them with manhood or masculinity.

Androgynous: Characterized by a blend of feminine and masculine traits, whether through physical appearance, gender identity, gender expression, or sexual orientation. Androgyne is another term for individuals embodying such characteristics.

Aromantic: Denotes individuals who do not experience romantic attraction. Aromanticism exists on a spectrum, with some individuals identifying as gray aromantic to describe their unique position on this spectrum. Aromantic individuals may still experience sexual attraction.

Asexual: Refers to individuals who do not experience sexual attraction. Asexuality is a sexual orientation distinct from sexual behaviors like celibacy, indicating a spectrum where terms like gray asexual may be used for self-identification.

Assigned Sex: The classification of an infant as male or female at birth, based on visible physical characteristics.

Assumed Gender: The gender others perceive an individual to be based on societal cues and the gender assigned at birth, often leading to assumptions without knowing the person's actual gender identity.

Bi-curious: Identifies individuals exploring attraction to multiple genders. This term is controversial and should be used cautiously, primarily for self-identification, due to its implications and potential to undermine bisexuality.

Bigender: A term for individuals whose gender identity encompasses two genders or fluctuates between them, offering a more nuanced understanding of gender beyond binary definitions.

Binary: Pertains to the conventional gender binary system, which recognizes only two genders, male and female.

Binding: The practice of compressing one's chest to reduce breast visibility, which must be done safely to avoid health risks.

Bioessentialism: The misuse of biological attributes to challenge or invalidate transgender identities, often simplifying complex attributes to binary categories.

Biological Sex: Describes the physical and biological characteristics that categorize individuals as male, female, or intersex, including a range of attributes from genitalia to chromosomes.

Biphobia: Describes the prejudice or dislike directed towards bisexual individuals, stemming from misconceptions or lack of understanding about bisexuality.

Bisexual: Refers to individuals who recognize the potential for attraction to more than one gender, not necessarily simultaneously or to the same degree, highlighting the fluidity of attraction.

Bottom Surgery: Gender-affirming surgery focused on altering an individual's reproductive organs as part of their transition, which is not universally sought by all trans individuals.

Butch: Describes individuals who express masculinity, often used within lesbian contexts but not limited to them, and is part of a spectrum of gender expression.

Chosen Family: Refers to a support network formed by individuals, often within the LGBTQ+ community, who are not biologically related but provide significant support and fill roles akin to a biological family.

Cisgender: Identifies someone whose gender identity matches their birth-assigned sex, emphasizing the normalcy of diverse gender identities without implying a standard of "normalcy."

Cisnormativity: The assumption that being cisgender is the standard, overshadowing and marginalizing other gender identities.

Cissexism: Discrimination or prejudice against transgender and gender-expansive individuals, based on a preference for cisgender identities.

Closeted: Describes individuals who do not publicly share their sexual orientation or gender identity, with varying degrees of openness in different areas of their lives.

Coming Out: The process of acknowledging and sharing one's gender identity or sexual orientation with others, a deeply personal journey of self-acceptance and disclosure.

Culturally Queer: Describes individuals raised within queer communities, experiencing a primary cultural identity shaped by queer norms and values.

Deadnaming: The act of referring to a transgender or gender-expansive person by a name they used prior to transitioning, which can be harmful and disrespectful.

Demiboy: Someone who partially identifies with being male, regardless of their assigned sex at birth.

Demigirl: Someone who partially identifies with being female, regardless of their assigned sex at birth.

Demirromantic: Describes individuals who only experience romantic attraction after forming a significant emotional connection.

Demisexual: Refers to individuals who only experience sexual attraction after forming a significant emotional connection.

Disclosure: The act of sharing one's transgender or gender-expansive identity with others, a term with varying preferences among individuals for describing this process.

Drag: The art of performing gender, often through exaggerated means, challenging traditional gender roles and celebrating gender diversity.

Dyke: A term for queer women or AFAB individuals, often associated with masculinity. Originally derogatory, it has been reclaimed by some within the community.

Femme: Describes individuals who express femininity, often used within lesbian contexts but not limited to them, and is part of a spectrum of gender expression.

Folx: An inclusive spelling of "folks," used by some to emphasize the inclusion of marginalized groups within the community.

FTM/F2M: Refers to a transgender man or someone transitioning from female to male.

FTX/F2X: Denotes a genderqueer or gender-expansive individual assigned female at birth.

Gay: Describes individuals attracted to the same gender, a term applicable to both men and women, though preferences for identification can vary.

Gayby: A child of one or more LGBTQ+ parents, a term of self-identification.

Gender Binary: The erroneous belief in only two distinct and opposite genders, male and female, which excludes the spectrum of gender identities.

Gender Dysphoria: The psychological distress experienced by individuals whose gender identity does not align with their birth-assigned sex.

Gender Euphoria: The joy or satisfaction felt when one's gender is affirmed, focusing on positive transgender experiences.

Gender Expansive: An umbrella term for individuals who challenge traditional gender norms and expressions, encompassing a wide range of identities and expressions.

Gender Expression: How an individual presents their gender to the world, through clothing, behavior, and personal appearance, which may or may not reflect their gender identity.

Gender Identity: A deeply felt sense of being male, female, a blend of both, or neither, which may or may not align with one's assigned sex at birth.

Gender Neutral: Refers to language, spaces, and societal aspects that do not assign or imply a specific gender, promoting inclusivity.

Gender Nonconfirming: A term for individuals who do not adhere to societal gender expectations, encompassing a wide range of gender identities and expressions.

Gender Performance Theory: Suggests that gender is not an inherent attribute but is performed based on societal expectations, challenging the notion of fixed gender roles.

Gender Roles: Societal norms dictating the behaviors and attributes considered **appropriate for people based on their perceived gender.**

Gender Socialization: The process by which individuals learn to behave in a way that aligns with societal expectations of their gender, varying greatly across cultures.

Gender Spectrum: Recognizes gender as a continuum rather than a binary system, allowing for a diverse range of gender identities and expressions.

Gender Variant: A term often used to describe individuals whose gender expression differs from societal norms, though it is less preferred due to its implication of abnormality.

Gender: A complex system of roles, behaviors, and societal expectations associated with being male or female, or beyond, shaped by cultural and societal influences.

Gender-Affirming Surgery: Surgical procedures that align an individual's physical appearance more closely with their gender identity, not essential for all trans individuals.

Genderfluid: Describes individuals whose gender identity or expression changes over time or varies depending on the context.

Gender-Neutral Salutations or Titles: Titles and forms of address that do not specify gender, used to respect individuals' gender identities and preferences.

Genderqueer: Identifies individuals who reject traditional gender distinctions, often used as an umbrella term for non-binary or gender-nonconforming identities.

Hermaphrodite: An outdated and offensive term for intersex individuals, not applicable to human beings and replaced by the term "intersex."

Heteroflexible: Describes individuals primarily attracted to the opposite gender but occasionally to the same gender, distinct from bisexuality.

Heteronormativity: The assumption that heterosexuality is the default or superior sexual orientation, marginalizing other orientations.

Heterosexual: Refers to individuals attracted to the opposite gender, also known as straight.

Homoflexible: Describes individuals primarily attracted to the same gender but occasionally to the opposite gender, distinct from bisexuality.

Homophobia: The prejudice or dislike directed towards LGBTQ+ individuals, often stemming from ignorance or misunderstanding.

Homosexual: A term for individuals attracted to the same gender, with varying acceptance and usage within the LGBTQ+ community.

Hormone Blockers: Medications that prevent the onset of puberty in transgender youth, allowing for later decisions on gender-affirming treatments.

Hormone Replacement Therapy: Medical treatment that enables transgender individuals to align their physical characteristics with their gender identity, through masculinizing or feminizing hormones.

House-Ballroom Community: An underground culture within the LGBTQ+ community, featuring competitions ("balls") and "houses" that provide familial support.

Hyperfemininity: An exaggerated adherence to traditional feminine gender roles, sometimes expected of trans women.

Hypermasculinity: An exaggerated adherence to traditional masculine gender roles, sometimes expected of trans men.

Intersectionality: The concept that multiple social identities (e.g., race, gender, sexuality) intersect to create unique experiences of discrimination or privilege.

Intersex: Describes individuals with biological characteristics that do not fit typical binary notions of male or female bodies.

Kinsey Scale: A scale developed to describe human sexuality on a continuum from exclusively heterosexual to exclusively homosexual, recognizing the fluidity of sexual orientation.

Latinx: A gender-neutral term for individuals of Latin American descent, used to include all genders beyond the binary male/female distinctions.

Lesbian: Women who are attracted to other women, with identity not dependent on sexual experience but on self-identification and attraction.

LGBTQI+: An inclusive acronym for the diverse community of individuals who do not identify as heterosexual or cisgender, including lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer/questioning, intersex individuals, and more.

Lifestyle: An outdated term that inaccurately suggests LGBTQ+ identities are choices rather than inherent aspects of identity.

Lived Experience: The acknowledgment of personal experiences and narratives as valuable sources of knowledge, especially in understanding marginalized perspectives.

Misgender: Referring to someone with incorrect pronouns or terms of address, impacting their dignity and identity, regardless of intent.

Misogynoir: Discrimination specifically against Black women, where race and gender intersect to produce unique experiences of bias.

Mispronoun: Using incorrect pronouns for someone, similar to misgendering, which undermines their gender identity and can cause distress.

MLM: An acronym for Men Loving Men, encompassing gay, bisexual, pansexual, and same-gender loving men, particularly used within communities of color.

Monogamous: Describes individuals who engage in romantic or sexual relationships with one person at a time.

Monolith: A metaphor indicating that members of a group have diverse experiences and should not be stereotyped based on the views or experiences of a few.

Monosexism: The belief that attraction to only one gender is superior to attraction to multiple genders.

Monosexual: Refers to individuals who are attracted to only one gender, including gay men, lesbians, and straight individuals.

MSM: An acronym for Men Who Have Sex with Men, used in public health contexts to describe sexual behavior regardless of identity.

MTF/M2F: Refers to a transgender woman or someone transitioning from male to female.

MTX/M2X: Denotes a genderqueer or gender-expansive individual assigned male at birth.

Nibling: A gender-neutral term for niece or nephew.

Nonbinary Lesbian: Describes a nonbinary individual primarily attracted to women, acknowledging the historical inclusivity of lesbianism towards diverse gender expressions.

Nonbinary: Identifies individuals who do not adhere to the traditional binary gender system, encompassing a range of identities beyond male and female.

Opposite Sex: An inaccurate term implying a binary view of gender and sex, better replaced with terms that acknowledge the diversity of gender and sexual identities.

Out: Describes individuals who openly identify as LGBTQ+ in various aspects of their lives, acknowledging the personal nature of disclosure.

Outing: Sharing someone's LGBTQ+ identity without their consent, which can be harmful and disrespectful.

Pansexual: Refers to attraction towards individuals regardless of gender, emphasizing the inclusion of all gender identities in potential attraction.

Passing: The ability or attempt of LGBTQ+ individuals to be perceived as straight or cisgender, often for safety or social acceptance.

Polyamorous: Describes individuals who engage in multiple consensual romantic or sexual relationships simultaneously, emphasizing ethics and consent.

Positive: A shorthand for being HIV positive, emphasizing the importance of consent in disclosing one's HIV status.

Post-Exposure Prophylaxis (PEP): Emergency medication taken after potential HIV exposure to prevent infection, part of comprehensive HIV prevention strategies.

Pre-, Post-, or Non-Operative: Terms describing the surgical status of transgender individuals in relation to gender-affirming surgery, emphasizing the personal choice and diverse experiences within the transgender community.

Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP): A preventative medication for individuals at higher risk of HIV, part of a comprehensive approach to HIV prevention.

Preference: Describes specific desires in partners, distinguishing between innate sexual orientation and individual preferences, which can be influenced by personal and societal factors.

Pronouns: Words used to refer to someone in place of their name, reflecting their gender identity. Using correct pronouns is essential for respecting individuals' identities.

PTP: An acronym for Person with a Transgender Parent, highlighting the experiences of individuals with transgender family members.

QTPOC: An acronym for Queer and Trans People of Color, emphasizing the intersectionality of race, gender, and sexuality.

Queer: A term reclaimed by some LGBTQ+ individuals to describe their identities or the community, valued for its inclusivity and defiance, though its use varies based on personal preference.

Queerbaiting: A marketing strategy that hints at LGBTQ+ representation without delivering meaningful inclusion, often criticized for exploiting LGBTQ+ themes for appeal without commitment.

Queerspawn: A term for individuals with one or more LGBTQ+ parents, used for self-identification and community belonging.

Questioning: Describes individuals exploring their sexual orientation, gender identity, or both, recognizing the ongoing process of understanding one's identity.

Same-Gender Loving (SGL): A term used particularly within the Black community to describe individuals attracted to the same gender, emphasizing cultural identity and avoiding Eurocentric terms.

Sapphic: Relates to women attracted to other women, drawing from the ancient poet Sappho, and encompasses lesbian, bisexual, pansexual, and same-gender loving women.

Sex Reassignment Surgery: Medical procedures that align an individual's physical characteristics with their gender identity, covering a range of surgeries beyond the outdated term "sex change surgery."

Sex Worker: A respectful term for individuals engaged in sexual activities for compensation, advocating for recognition of sex work as legitimate work.

Sexual Orientation: Describes one's emotional, romantic, or sexual attraction to others, recognizing the inherent nature of these attractions beyond mere sexual activity.

Social Construction Theory: The concept that societal norms and identities are created and maintained through social processes, challenging the notion of inherent or natural social structures.

SOGI: An acronym for Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity, used as shorthand in discussions around rights and recognition for diverse sexual and gender identities.

Stealth: Describes transgender or gender-expansive individuals who choose not to disclose their gender history in certain aspects of life, emphasizing privacy and individual choice.

Stud: A term within the Black lesbian community for women with a masculine presentation, part of a spectrum of gender expression.

Survival Sex: Sexual activity exchanged for basic needs, highlighting the socioeconomic vulnerabilities faced by some LGBTQ+ individuals.

T4T: An abbreviation for Trans for Trans, describing relationships or attractions among transgender individuals, celebrating transgender identities and experiences.

TERF: An acronym for Trans-Exclusionary Radical Feminist, describing individuals or groups that exclude transgender women from feminist spaces, often criticized for undermining transgender rights and identities.

TGNC: Stands for Trans and Gender Nonconforming, an inclusive term for individuals who do not identify as cisgender, encompassing a broad spectrum of gender identities.

Top Surgery: Gender-affirming surgery on the chest or breasts, tailored to the individual's gender identity and goals, part of the spectrum of medical transition options.

Trancestors: A term for transgender elders or ancestors, celebrating the legacy and contributions of transgender individuals across generations.

Trans-antagonistic: Describes actions or attitudes that actively oppose or harm transgender and gender-expansive individuals, beyond mere prejudice to include deliberate discrimination.

Transfeminine: Refers to individuals assigned male at birth who identify more closely with femininity but do not necessarily identify as binary women.

Transgender Man: A man who has transitioned from female to male, emphasizing the alignment of gender identity with male gender.

Transgender Woman: A woman who has transitioned from male to female, emphasizing the alignment of gender identity with female gender.

Transgender: Describes individuals whose gender identity differs from the sex they were assigned at birth, encompassing a wide range of identities and experiences within and beyond the gender binary.

Transition: The process of aligning one's life and body with their gender identity, which can include social, legal, and medical steps, unique to each individual's journey and needs.

Transmasculine: Describes people who were designated female at birth but feel a stronger connection to masculinity, without necessarily identifying as binary males.

Transmedicalism: The belief that medical transition and gender dysphoria are required to be considered truly transgender, a controversial stance within the transgender community.

Transmisogynoir: Discrimination specifically targeting transgender Black women, combining racism, sexism, and transphobia.

Transmisogyny: Discrimination specifically targeting transgender women, combining misogyny and transphobia.

Transpawn: A term for individuals with one or more transgender or non-binary parents, used for self-identification and acknowledging unique family dynamics.

Transphobia: Prejudice or dislike directed towards transgender and gender-expansive individuals, stemming from ignorance and misunderstanding, which can be mitigated through education and support.

Transsexual: A less commonly used term (derogatory) for individuals who undergo medical transition to align their bodies with their gender identity, with varying acceptance and relevance within the community.

Two-Spirit: A term used by some Indigenous North American communities to describe a person embodying both masculine and feminine spirits, specific to cultural context and not for use by non-Indigenous people.

Voguing: A dance style originating from the LGBTQ+ ballroom scene, characterized by poses inspired by fashion models and ancient Egyptian art, celebrating creativity and identity.

WLW: An acronym for Women Loving Women, encompassing lesbian, bisexual, pansexual, and same-gender loving women, highlighting the diversity

Adapted from the Institute of Medicine's report, *The Health of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender People: Building a Foundation for Better Understanding* (2011) and *PFLAG's National Glossary of Terms*

APPENDIX B CONSENT FORMS & INVITATIONS

RESEARCH SUBJECT INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Dear Prospective Research Participant: You are being asked to volunteer in a research study as part of the requirements of my Ph.D. program. Please read this consent form carefully, and ask as many questions as you like before deciding whether you want to participate in this research study. You may also ask questions at any time before, during, or after you join this research. You are encouraged to take your time in making your decision.

Project Title: Attitudes of Medical Doctors towards Trans and Non-binary People in Greece

Principal Investigator: Paraskevi Palmou, Clinical Psychology MA, Gestalt Therapist. Sygrou 29, Athens, Greece tel:6976307815, e-mail:palmoup@hotmail.com

Project Supervisor: Dr. Klio Geroulanou, NYC, Athens and Bolton University, U.K.

PROJECT INFORMATION

1. Purpose of the Research: The purpose of this study is to identify the attitudes of medical doctors towards trans and non-binary people in Greece and to explore this population's experiences of stigma and discrimination by physicians,
2. Inclusion Criteria: You must identify as a trans or non-binary person
3. Research Procedures: You will participate in semi-structured personal interviews focused on your experiences with medical doctors and health care providers.
4. Potential Risks and Discomforts: Interviewees have no foreseeable physical risks; it might be hard for them to discuss painful experiences, if any, but the interviewers are trained to support them. They always choose to withdraw at any time point in their study.
5. Potential Benefits of the Research: You will be able to make public any past abuse and discomfort created by the medical community and raise awareness concerning trans and non-binary exclusion.
6. Provision for Confidentiality: All questionnaires will be anonymous to ensure confidentiality and increase validity by allowing you to respond freely. Interviews will also be anonymous, and any names or identifying information will be deleted from the transcript before the analysis

Any information shared during the study will be treated with strict confidence, and once the survey is completed, it will not be possible to identify individuals. Only the researchers Paraskevi Palmou and her assistant Vanessa Theodorou will access the

information throughout the study. Both researchers are trained psychotherapists under supervision, bound to confidentiality. Also, a confidentiality agreement will be signed by both researchers. Interviewees' data and identifying information will be kept separately, and interviewees will only be determined by code number. The collection and storage of data will adhere to the Data Protection Act 1998 (DPA) along with all relevant laws and regulations regarding the handling of personal data and privacy. This includes any laws that modify, replace, augment, or enhance the DPA, notably the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) (GDPR), which oversees personal data processing. The gathered data will be maintained for a duration of five years, after which it will be securely disposed of. The University Data Protection Policy is available at: <https://www.bolton.ac.uk/wpcontent/uploads/2018/03/1.-Data-Protection-Policy-2018.pdf>

7. Research-related Injury: If there are concerns about the treatment of research interviewees, contact Parvy Palmou at palmoup@hotmail.com if you experience psychological discomfort due to participation in this study.

8. Contacts for additional information: If you have any questions about the study, concerns about the research, and your rights as a participant, you may contact Parvy Palmou at palmoup@hotmail.com.

10. Voluntary participation and the right to discontinue the involvement without penalty: Your participation in this study is voluntary. You do not have to be in this study if you do not want to be. You have the right to change your mind and leave the study at any time without giving any reason or penalty. Any new information that may make you change your mind about being in this study will be given to you. You will be given a copy of this consent form to keep. You do not waive any of your legal rights by signing this consent form.

11. Consent: If you sign below, you have read (or have read to you) the information given in this consent form, and you would like to volunteer in this study. You understand that you will receive a copy of this form. You voluntarily choose to participate, but understand that your consent does not take away any legal right in the case of negligence or other legal fault of anyone involved in this study. You understand that nothing in this consent form is intended to replace any laws. You also understand that you may withdraw your consent at any time.

_____ Participant's Name (printed)
 _____ Participant's Signature
 _____ Date
 _____ Principal Investigator's
 Signature _____ Date

INVITATION FOR PARTICIPATION OF DOCTORS

Διδακτορική Διατριβή – Έρευνα:

Οι Στάσεις των Γιατρών Απέναντι σε Τρανς και Μη-Δυναδικά Πρόσωπα στην Ελλάδα

Στην παρακάτω έρευνα, προσκαλούνται να συμμετέχουν γιατροί όλων των ειδικοτήτων και από όλες της περιοχές της χώρας. Η έρευνα είναι ανώνυμη και δεν θα υπάρξουν μεμονωμένα αποτελέσματα, μόνο ομαδικά.

Εκτιμώμενος χρόνος: 6 λεπτά.

Για οποιαδήποτε απορία μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε στο e mail:
palmour@hotmail.com

surveymonkey.com
Στην παρακάτω έρευνα
προσκαλούνται να συμμετέχο...

 12

19 κοινοποιήσεις

 Μου αρέσει!

 Σχόλιο

 Κοινοποίηση

APPENDIX C

COLLABORATING ESTABLISHMENT OF RESEARCH AGREEMENT

GENERAL INFORMATION Project Title: Attitudes of Medical Doctors towards Trans and Non-binary People in Greece

Principal Investigator: Paraskevi Palmou, Clinical Psychology MA, Gestalt Therapist. Sygrou 29, Athens, Greece <tel:6976307815>, [email:palmoup@hotmail.com](mailto:palmoup@hotmail.com)

Project Supervisor: Dr. Klio Geroulanou, Bolton University, U.K.

The **Greek Transgender Support Association**, a recognized NGO for the support of the rights of the trans community in Greece, is located at 29 Sygrou Av. Athens, Greece, agrees with psychotherapist Paraskevi Palmou to provide access to all necessary member files, documents, hardware, software, methods, and tools, including library, offices, and computing facilities to support her research project.

Provision for Confidentiality: Any information shared during the study will be strictly confidential. Once the study is completed, identifying individuals will not be possible. Only the researchers Paraskevi Palmou and her assistant Vanessa Theodorou will access the information throughout the study. Both researchers are trained psychotherapists under supervision, bound to confidentiality. Also, a confidentiality agreement will be signed by both researchers. Interviewees' data and identifying information should be kept separately, and interviewees will only be determined by code number. The collection and storage of data will adhere to the Data Protection Act 1998 (DPA) along with all relevant laws and regulations regarding the handling of personal data and privacy. This includes any laws that modify, replace, augment, or enhance the DPA, notably the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) (GDPR), which oversees personal data processing. The gathered data will be maintained for a duration of five years, after which it will be securely disposed of.

The University Data Protection Policy is available at:

<https://www.bolton.ac.uk/wpcontent/uploads/2018/03/1.-Data-Protection-Policy-2018.pdf>

_____ Organization's Signature and Stamp
 _____ Date

_____ Principal Investigator's Signature
 _____ Date

APPENDIX D

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Attitudes of Medical Doctors and Experiences of Trans and Non-binary People with the Healthcare System in Greece: A Mixed Methods Approach

Paraskevi Palmou

Supervisor: Dr. Klio Geroulanou

THE UNIVERSITY OF BOLTON, U.K.

Ερωτηματολόγιο 1.

Η. Γρηγορόπουλος, Σ. Παπαχαρίτου, Μ. Μωραΐτου

Adaptation of the attitudes toward lesbians and gay men (ATLG) scale into the Greek language.

Παρακαλώ απαντήστε με ειλικρίνεια το τεστ είναι ανώνυμο.

ΟΔΗΓΙΕΣ: Παρακαλείσθε να απαντήσετε στις παρακάτω δηλώσεις χρησιμοποιώντας την βαθμολογία 1 έως 5 της κλίμακας που περιγράφεται παρακάτω. Είναι σημαντικό να υποδείξετε πώς αισθάνεστε πραγματικά ΤΩΡΑ και όχι πώς αισθανόσασταν στο ΠΑΡΕΛΘΟΝ.

Ορισμένες από τις δηλώσεις μπορεί να είναι άγνωστες για εσάς, αλλά προσπαθήστε να σκεφτείτε για παρόμοιες καταστάσεις που εσείς ίσως βρεθήκατε. Απαντήστε σε κάθε μια ερώτηση και μην ανησυχείτε για τις προηγούμενες απαντήσεις σας.

ΔΕΝ ΥΠΑΡΧΟΥΝ ΣΩΣΤΕΣ ΚΑΙ ΛΑΘΟΣ ΑΠΑΝΤΗΣΕΙΣ.

ΑΠΑΝΤΗΣΕΙΣ.

1. Οι trans&non-binary άνθρωποι δεν μπορούν να ενταχθούν ομαλά (δεν ταιριάζουν) στην κοινωνία μας.
2. Η ταυτότητα φύλου ενός ανθρώπου, σε καμιά περίπτωση, δεν πρέπει να αποτελεί αιτία για διακρίσεις στον εργασιακό χώρο.
3. Η trans&non-binary ταυτότητα είναι καταστρεπτική για την κοινωνία, επειδή καταργεί τη βιολογική διαφορά ανάμεσα στα δύο φύλα
4. Η trans&non-binary κατάσταση (ταυτότητα) δεν πρέπει να αποδοκιμάζεται.
5. Η trans&non-binary κατάσταση (ταυτότητα) είναι αμαρτία.

6. Ο αυξανόμενος αριθμός των trans&non-binary ανθρώπων δείχνει την κρίση των ηθικών αξιών της κοινωνίας μας.
7. Η trans&non-binary κατάσταση (ταυτότητα) αυτή καθαυτή δεν αποτελεί πρόβλημα,
εκτός και εάν η κοινωνία την παρουσιάζει ως πρόβλημα.
8. Η trans&non-binary κατάσταση (ταυτότητα) θέτει σε κίνδυνο πολλούς βασικούς θεσμούς της κοινωνίας μας.
9. Η trans&non-binary κατάσταση αποτελεί κατώτερη μορφή έκφρασης της ταυτότητας φύλου.
10. Οι trans&non-binary άνθρωποι είναι αρρωστημένα άτομα.
11. Θα πρέπει να επιτρέπεται σε trans&non-binary ανθρώπους να υιοθετούν παιδιά, όπως επιτρέπεται στα ετεροφυλόφιλα ζευγάρια.
12. Πιστεύω ότι οι trans&non-binary άνθρωποι είναι αηδιαστικοί.
13. Δεν θα πρέπει να επιτρέπεται σε trans&non-binary ανθρώπους να διδάσκουν στα σχολεία.
14. Η trans&non-binary κατάσταση (ταυτότητα) αποτελεί διαστροφή.
15. Η trans&non-binary κατάσταση (ταυτότητα) αποτελεί μια φυσιολογική έκφραση της ταυτότητας φύλου.
16. Εάν ένας άνθρωπος έχει τάσεις προς μια trans&non-binary κατάσταση (ταυτότητα) , πρέπει να κάνει ό,τι μπορεί για να τις ξεπεράσει.
17. Δεν θα στενοχωριόμουν ιδιαίτερα εάν μάθαινα ότι το παιδί μου είναι trans&non-binary.
18. Το σεξ μεταξύ trans&non-binary ατόμων δεν είναι καθόλου σωστό.
19. Το να παντρεύονται τα trans&non-binary αποτελεί γελοίο γεγονός.
20. Η trans&non-binary κατάσταση (ταυτότητα) είναι ένας διαφορετικός τρόπος ζωής, ο οποίος δεν θα πρέπει να καταδικάζεται.

***1=διαφωνώ απόλυτα, 2=διαφωνώ, 3+ δεν διαφωνώ ούτε συμφωνώ, 4= συμφωνώ, 5=συμφωνώ απόλυτα για καθεμιά πρόταση/άποψη**

APPENDIX E

Attitudes of Medical Doctors and Experiences of Trans and Non-binary People with the Healthcare System in Greece: A Mixed Methods Approach

Paraskevi Palmou

Supervisor: Dr. Klio Geroulanou

THE UNIVERSITY OF BOLTON, U.K.

Ερωτηματολόγιο 2.

Genderism and Transphobia Scale
Darryl B. Hill^{1,3} and Brian L. B. Willoughby²

Παρακαλώ απαντήστε με ειλικρίνεια το τεστ είναι ανώνυμο.

ΟΔΗΓΙΕΣ: Παρακαλείσθε να απαντήσετε στις παρακάτω δηλώσεις χρησιμοποιώντας την βαθμολογία 1 έως 5 της κλίμακας που περιγράφεται παρακάτω. Είναι σημαντικό να υποδείξετε πώς αισθάνεστε πραγματικά ΤΩΡΑ και όχι πώς αισθανόσασταν στο ΠΑΡΕΛΘΟΝ.

Ορισμένες από τις δηλώσεις μπορεί να είναι άγνωστες για εσάς, αλλά προσπαθήστε να σκεφτείτε για παρόμοιες καταστάσεις που εσείς ίσως βρεθήκατε. Απαντήστε σε κάθε μια ερώτηση και μην ανησυχείτε για τις προηγούμενες απαντήσεις σας.

ΔΕΝ ΥΠΑΡΧΟΥΝ ΣΩΣΤΕΣ ΚΑΙ ΛΑΘΟΣ ΑΠΑΝΤΗΣΕΙΣ.

1. Έχω κτυπήσει άνδρες που ενεργούν σαν “αδελφές”.
2. Έχω συμπεριφερθεί βίαια προς μια γυναίκα γιατί ήταν πολύ αρρενωπή.
3. Εάν έμαθα ότι ο καλύτερος φίλος μου άλλαξε το φύλο του, θα ένιωθα άσχημα.
4. Ο Θεός έκανε δύο φύλα και δύο φύλα μόνο.
5. Εάν ένας φίλος ήθελε να αφαιρέσει το πέος του διότι νιώθει γυναίκα, θα τον υποστήριζα ανοιχτά.
6. Έχω πειράξει έναν άνθρωπο λόγω της θηλυκής του εμφάνισης ή συμπεριφοράς.
7. Οι άνδρες που φορούν γυναικεία ρούχα με σκοπό την σεξουαλική ευχαρίστηση με απογοητεύουν.

8. Τα παιδιά πρέπει να ενθαρρύνονται να διερευνήσουν την αρρενωπότητα και τη θηλυκότητα.
9. Αν έβλεπα κάποιον στο δρόμο θα τον ρωτούσα αν ήταν άντρας ή γυναίκα.
10. Οι άνδρες που ενεργούν σαν γυναίκες πρέπει να ντρέπονται για τον εαυτό τους.
11. Οι άνδρες που ξυρίζουν τα πόδια τους είναι περίεργοι.
12. Δεν μπορώ να καταλάβω γιατί μια γυναίκα θα ενεργούσε αρρενωπά.
13. Έχω πειράξει μια γυναίκα εξαιτίας της αρσενικής της εμφάνισης ή συμπεριφοράς.
14. Τα παιδιά πρέπει να παίζουν με παιχνίδια κατάλληλα με το δικό τους φύλο.
15. Οι γυναίκες που βλέπουν τον εαυτό τους ως άνδρες είναι ανώμαλες.
16. Θα απέφευγα να μιλήσω με μια γυναίκα αν ήξερα είχε χειρουργικά δημιουργημένο πέος και όρχεις.
17. Ένας άνδρας που ντύνεται σαν γυναίκα είναι διεστραμμένος.
18. Αν έμαθα ότι ο εραστής μου άνηκε στο παρελθόν σε άλλο φύλο θα ήμουν βίαιος.
19. Τα θηλυπρεπή αγόρια θα πρέπει να θεραπεύονται από το πρόβλημά τους.
20. Έχω συμπεριφερθεί βίαια σε έναν άνδρα επειδή ήταν πολύ θηλυπρεπείς.
21. Οι παθητικοί άνδρες είναι αδύναμοι.
22. Αν ένας άνδρας που φοράει μακιγιάζ και φόρεμα, ο οποίος έχει ψηλή φωνή, πλησιάσει το παιδί μου, θα το χρησιμοποιούσα σωματική δύναμη για να τον σταματήσω.
23. Θα πρέπει να επιτρέπεται στα άτομα να εκφράζουν ελεύθερα το φύλο τους.
24. Οι εγχειρήσεις επαναπροσδιορισμού φύλου είναι ηθικά λανθασμένες.
25. Οι θηλυκοί άνδρες με κάνουν να αισθάνομαι άβολα.
26. Θα πήγαινα σε ένα μπαρ που συχνάζουν γυναίκες που ήταν άνδρες.
27. Οι άνθρωποι είναι άνδρες ή γυναίκες.
28. Οι φίλοι μου και εγώ συχνά αστειευόμαστε για τους άνδρες που ντύνονται σαν

γυναίκες.

29. Οι αρρενωπές γυναίκες με κάνουν να αισθάνομαι άβολα.

30. Είναι ηθικά λάθος για μια γυναίκα να παρουσιάσει τον εαυτό της ως άνδρα δημόσια.

31. Είναι καλό να κάνεις χιούμορ με τους ανθρώπους που φορούν ρούχα του άλλου φύλου.

32. Αν γνώριζα άνδρες που φορούσαν παπούτσια με ψηλά τακούνια, κάλτσες και μακιγιάζ, θα τους χτυπούσα.

**1=διαφωνώ απόλυτα, 7=συμφωνώ απόλυτα για καθεμιά πρόταση/άποψη*

APPENDIX F

Attitudes of Medical Doctors and Experiences of Trans and Non-binary People with the Healthcare System in Greece: A Mixed Methods Approach

Paraskevi Palmou

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THE UNIVERSITY OF BOLTON, U.K.

Semi-Structured Interview

Ερωτήσεις συνέντευξης trans/non-binary ατόμων:

- Πως προσδιορίζεστε; Τρανς, Non-binary
- Έχετε κάνει κάποιες ιατρικές παρεμβάσεις φύλου;
- Σε ποια πόλη/χώρα;

1. Περιγράψτε μου τις εμπειρίες σας από τις επαφές σας με γιατρούς κατά τις επισκέψεις σας στο νοσοκομείο/Ιατρείο.

-πείτε μου περισσότερα για αυτή σας την εμπειρία-(συναισθήματα, σκέψεις)

2. Για ποιο λόγο πιστεύετε ότι σας συμπεριφέρθηκε ο γιατρός με αυτόν τον τρόπο;

-πείτε μου περισσότερα για αυτή σας την εμπειρία-(συναισθήματα, σκέψεις)

3. Τι μορφή είχαν αυτές οι αρνητικές/θετικές συμπεριφορές;

-πείτε μου περισσότερα για αυτή σας την εμπειρία-

4. Τι αντίκτυπο είχαν σε εσάς οι παραπάνω συμπεριφορές, τώρα αλλά και στο μέλλον;

-πείτε μου περισσότερα για αυτή σας την εμπειρία-(συναισθήματα, σκέψεις)

**Σε περίπτωση που αναφερθούν μόνο εμπειρίες που αξιολογούνται από το άτομο ως αρνητικές θα διερευνήσω την πιθανότητα ύπαρξης θετικών εμπειριών και το αντίθετο.*

5. Εκτός από τις αρνητικές εμπειρίες που μου αναφέρατε παραπάνω, έχετε να αναφέρετε και θετικές εμπειρίες.

6. Υπάρχει κάτι άλλο που θα θέλατε να μου αναφέρετε σχετικά με τις εμπειρίες σας με το σύστημα υγείας γενικά;